

PROJECT DELIVERABLE

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Abbreviation List

Abbreviation	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BC	Blockchain
BCT	Blockchain Technology
CAGR	Compound Annual Growth Rate
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
D	Deliverable
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
B2B	Business-to-Business
B2C	Business-to-Consumer
BOF	Blockchain Observatory and Forum
CRM	Customer Relationship Management
DESI	Digital Economy and Society Index
DT	Digital Technologies
EBSI	European Blockchain Services Infrastructure
ERP	Enterprise Resource Planning
EU	European Union
EVOO	Extra Virgin Olive oil
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
GHG	Green House Gas
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IoT	Internet of Things
IT	Information Technology
M	Month
MNO	Mobile network operators
MS	Microsoft
MSME	Micro, small and medium enterprises
NFT	Non-Fungible Token
PA	Public Administration
PDO	Protected Designation of Origin
PGI	Protected Geographical Indication
Q	Question
QR code	Quick Response code
RDI	Rural digital index
RFID	Radio Frequency Identification
ROI	Return on Investment
SCM	supply chain management
SME	Small Medium Enterprise
T	Task
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UC	Use Case
VCM	Voluntary Carbon Market
VPN	Virtual Private Network
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

Along the first year of the project, *beneficiaries* have been involved in a series of activities addressed to map and collect information on currently existing blockchain solutions, use cases and projects. Peer-review publications, existing databases, library of papers, articles, and other qualified digital resources related to the use of BCT in the agri-food context have been consulted and the information most useful at the scope sorted and collected. Such work was related to Task 2.1 and Task 2.2 activities and ended with the submission of a Database (D2.2).

Task 2.3, to which this Deliverable refers, was related to the “assessment” of the huge amount of documents identified, read and sorted in the scope of previous WP2’s tasks. Where, in the phase of analysis, collected data showed gaps and missing details, the consortium operated through surveys and interviews to go more in deep on the study.

The main objective of this document is to report about findings emerging in relation to the current blockchain’s adoption in the agri-food sector, as a result of the above-mentioned “assessment” process of the data collected from different sources.

A SWOT analysis has been carried out and the patterns and anti-patterns have been identified.

Preliminary open questions emerging from this analysis have been shared with the colleagues in charge for organising further discussion with stakeholders to fill gaps and identify a pathway for a future wider application of blockchain in the agri-food sector.

1. Assessment of sector's adoption of blockchain technology

1.1. Introduction

Along the first year of the project, *beneficiaries* have been involved in a series of activities addressed to map and collect information on currently existing blockchain solutions, use cases and projects. Peer-review publications, existing databases, library of papers, articles, and other qualified digital resources related to the use of BCT in the agri-food context have been consulted and the information most useful at the scope sorted and collected. Such work was related to Task 2.1 and Task 2.2 activities and ended with the submission of a Database (D2.2).

Task 2.3, to which this Deliverable refers, was related to the “assessment” of the huge amount of documents identified, read and sorted in the scope of previous WP2's tasks.

Where, in the phase of analysis, collected data showed gaps and missing details, the consortium operated through surveys and interviews to go more in deep on the study.

1.2. Scope of the document

The main objective of this document is to report about findings emerging in relation to the current blockchain's adoption in the agri-food sector, as a result of the above-mentioned “assessment” process.

1.3. Methodology

Figure 1 shows the flow of the overall process. This Deliverable refers mainly to the part evidenced as “**T2.3**” in the picture. As we can see, there are a number of actions which all converge in the Deliverable 2.1:

- Analysis of the Database per se (more details in D2.2 and [Annexes 1 and 4](#))
- Survey and Interview to referents coming from some use cases selected from the Database (more details in [Annex 2](#))
- Data from publications, Reports, Associations (main takeaways available in [Annexes 2 and 5](#))
- Survey to food supply chain players (not familiar with BCT) using the Network of project's Associations (more details in D3.1 and [Annex 3](#))
- Digital maturity of agri-food sector preliminary assessment (more details in [Annex 3](#))

Figure 1 - flow of the overall process

1.4. Structure of the document

The core of the Deliverable is constituted by:

- Introduction
- Scope of the document
- Methodology
- Structure of the document
- Additional note
- Main findings and SWOT analysis
- Identification of patterns and anti-patterns
- Topics for further discussion with stakeholders

Through these paragraphs, the reader is able to immediately understand the process followed for mapping, collecting and assessing data and have direct access to the main findings. Five 'Annexes' follow, which represent a fundamental and integral part of the document itself, since each single Annex covers a partial phase of the analysis/assessment carried out, that is:

- Annex 1 – Database assessment
- Annex 2 – Assessment through digital resources, Surveys and Interviews
- Annex 3 – Digital maturity of the agri-food sector – preliminary findings
- Annex 4 – List of use cases mapped and collected
- Annex 5 – List of digital resources

However, being such analyses long, in order not to make the main document heavier, they are treated as separated Chapters.

1.5. Additional note

This document intends to maintain the analysis as much as possible at a neutral and objective level, avoiding positions taken from the consortium.

Opinions and recommendations in this regard will be postponed to the final Papers generated by the project: Roadmap and White Papers.

1.6. Main findings:

- **Blockchain applications are not very common in agri-food sector** (according to public data, it is currently implemented by only 22 % of companies), and are spread in EU and other countries with different levels of intensity [Annex 1 and Annex 3].
- While the Database and the survey were not able to reliably assess the per-country level of adoption of BCT, we have enough elements to think that most BCT-powered agri-food initiatives have a scope that reaches beyond Europe. We believe that **European lawmakers should pay attention to this matter of fact when designing future regulation** [Annex 2].
- **Most often, blockchain’s adoption is driven by ambitions that are not only related to profit.** What is more interesting is that business efficiency and revenue, together, represent less voted motivations compared to “common good” reasons (i.e., societal, **environmental** and public health issues, plus business transparency). Transparency is at the first position, strictly correlated with “business reputation”, meaning that the *BCT label* attached to a business is still considered a factor for adoption [Annex 2]. This is very much in line also with **B2C preponderant use cases: BCT as an enabler of trust of the customer is a much more prized asset** rather than enabler of trust between cooperating organizations. This evidence is confirmed by players both familiar and not with BCT [Annex 2 and Annex 3]. Also, the low consideration of BCT application for “finance and insurance” evidenced by use cases analysed [Annex 2] shows a slow transition from the *orthodoxy* of BCT as a tool for financial transactions towards – at least for agriculture-related applications – a new generation of adopters who see it as a more generic *enabler of trust for information exchange*.

Such dynamics should be better investigated.

- Where blockchains are deployed, citizens / consumers are nearly always involved. Purely B2B use cases are quite rare [Annex 2].

It would be interesting to know the opinion of consumers as the final users of these solutions, but also investigate the barriers to apply BCT for business efficiency (internal and along the supply chain) purposes.

- **BCT is currently deployed in food sectors characterized by high positioning products** (e.g., PGI, PDO, organic, certified products, etc), able to face and absorb costs related to the investment. Most of these use cases adopt QR-Code tags on their products that allow consumers to verify information provided by the producer from some blockchain source [Annex 1 and Annex 2].
- In terms of features of BCT, apparently **BCT is commonly used for its data immutability features rather than for anything else** [Annex 2].

We would like to understand if this feature, when evaluated together with the weak points, is enough to justify the adoption of a radically new technology.

- The support of public funds has been used by about half of the use cases [Annex 1 and Annex 2]. This could be related to the results coming from the digital maturity assessment, which shows the associated costs as the primary obstacle concerning investments in new technologies [Annex 3].

The role of public funds/financial support as a driver for investment should be better investigated.

- The European Public Administration (PA) footprint in the area under investigation is very light – except for the fact that the majority of BCT initiatives received public funds. Initiatives that directly target the PA sector are absent from our Database [Annex 1] and survey [Annex 2], but the partnership with some private company appears to be a precondition for the participation of PA agencies in BCT initiatives.

The opinion of PA stakeholders may shed some light on this matter.

- “End user awareness” is the **top hindering factor in solution’s delivery** [Annex 2]: it means that understanding what exactly BCT provides, and what its shortcomings are, is the key-factor for adoption from an agri-food end user. This outcome is even more exacerbated by the digital maturity assessment [Annex 3] which demonstrated as agri-food companies, in general within the EU (28), have a very low level of digital intensity and significant internal skill gaps. Also, the presence of an IT department does not guarantee the complete understanding of BCT features.

The consortium intends to go more in deep in this regard.

- Data interoperability and technical skills are confirmed as two technical hindering factors in delivering the solution [Annex 3].

Both topics are already scheduled to be better investigated and clarified along the Task Forces meetings, generating White Papers co-created with the support of experts in the field and published by the end of the project.

- The excessive formalization of processes imposed by blockchain often introduces excessive rigidity in the financial and/or methodological management of processes, which today are managed in a flexible manner with non-codified agreements between the parties [Annex 2].

To be more investigated the opinion of supply chain players in this regard.

- Our TRL analysis (page 31) shows that the ongoing applicative use cases are mainly classified as “prototype” use cases [Annex 1]. Some cases are in a “Pilot” phase, while “production” is the less populated area. This result is in line with current bibliographic data, which report **BCT applications still in a prototype/test level rather than in a fully operational industrial environment**. This does not exclude that mature operating cases exist. Most of the concept cases analysed are inactive, while production cases all are still active, validating the trend that increased maturity correlates with a reduced likelihood of failure.

- Blockchain is confirmed as a robust and trustworthy technology, both in a test-bed environment and in the regular operation of the solution [Annex 2]. Also, there is an overall users’ satisfaction in terms of its use (the level of performance meets and sometimes exceeds expectations) [Annex 2 and Annex 3], however:

- a) a large portion of users were not in the position to make an assessment on the topic of return on investment (ROI), due to their initiative being still in an early phase [Annex 2], **and this represents a key-point for decision, as we know that sometimes the cost may easily outweigh its benefits**,
- b) there is a “complexity of the systems” mentioned as major issue for application [Annex 2], suggesting that the BCT - even if mature enough for production use - remains still difficult to master for software developers and system integrators.

This lays the foundation for thinking that even a successful blockchain initiative may be hindered by BCT’s structural limitations.

Such limitations require more investigations, both from the technical and non-technical point of view.

- The overall low digital maturity of agri-food market, in particular **farmers** located in rural areas **and SMEs operating in agri-food**, hinders their shift towards digital platforms since they **still lack some of the basic capabilities in terms of digital transformation** [Annex 3]. All of these weaknesses need to be bridged, to build a plan for new technologies (blockchain included) wide adoption, both in EU and in less developed countries (e.g., Egypt and other Middle East countries).
- **Lack of trust in data**; BCT intervenes precisely where there is a lack of trust (between subjects) so it can be an opportunity. The problem is the food sector where the threat derives from the technological lack of maturity of the data acquisition systems (IoT) which should guarantee the detection "upstream" and automatically, while the data still transits between many databases and information systems. Interviewed players [Annex 2] acknowledge the existence of sensitive stages where manipulation of data along the supply chain could occur. These critical stages include data related to purchased raw materials, treatments in the field (e.g., fertilizers, pesticides), and logistics. Also, paper documentation is considered suitable for theft or manipulation. Another point highlighted was the data security (handle personal data, or legal data).

SWOT ANALYSIS

Strengths

- Robust and trustworthy technology, both in a test-bed environment and in the regular operation of the solution. There is an overall users' satisfaction in terms of its use (the level of performance meets and sometimes exceeds expectations)
- Transparency and Traceability: Blockchain offers a transparent and immutable ledger that allows to track the products' movement. This can enhance trust and reduce frauds.
- Efficiency: Blockchain can eliminate manual paperwork and redundant record-keeping, reducing administrative overhead and errors. IoT and Smart contracts can automate processes and enforce agreements
- Data Security: Blockchain's cryptographic techniques ensure data security, reducing the risk of tampering.

Weaknesses

- Adoption Challenges: Implementing blockchain technology across the agri-food supply chain can be a slow and complex process. "Complexity of the systems" is the most mentioned issue for application.
- Cost and Scalability: limited availability of reliable cost/benefit analyses (ROI). Initial setup and maintenance costs can be high. As more data is added, scalability becomes a concern.
- End user awareness: if (for lack of skills) the end user does not understand what exactly BCT provides, and how it can be useful for own activity, adoption is compromised.
- Technical Expertise: Technical expertise may not be readily available in the agri-food industry.
- Smallholders are currently excluded.
- Regulatory Uncertainty: The regulatory environment for blockchain in the agri-food sector is still evolving (e.g. lack of standards).
- IoT not enough implemented as associated technology for generating trustworthiness data in its source
- Interest in maintaining some data *off-chain*

Opportunities

- Improved Food Safety and Reduced Frauds: Blockchain can make it easier to identify the source of contaminated products, and can reduce frauds in labeling, certification, and origin claims, in particular for high positioning food products
- Business reputation and consumer trust: Demonstrating a commitment to societal, environmental and public health issues, plus transparency and food safety through blockchain can build consumer's trust and loyalty.
- Market Access: Blockchain can provide evidence of compliance with food safety and sustainability standards.
- Supply Chain Innovation: Blockchain can enable innovative business models (peer-to-peer sales, fractional ownership of agricultural assets, and crowd-funded farming projects).

Threats

- Data Privacy Concerns: Storing sensitive supply chain data on a blockchain raises concerns about data privacy and European new GDPR.
- Security Risks: Vulnerabilities and cyberattacks could compromise the integrity of the supply chain data.
- Resistance to Change: The agri-food industry has longstanding practices and traditions that may resist technological change.
- High Entry Barriers: The initial investment and technical knowledge required can create barriers for smaller players in the agri-food sector.
- Connectivity in rural areas and low digital maturity of agri-food sector can create structural barriers.
- Most of data are still originated in an analogic way, reported by hand by an operator, reducing the trustworthiness of data in its source on the ledger
- Trustworthiness between data and physical assets.
- Low interest to enable trust for information exchange between cooperating organizations

Figure 2 – SWOT analysis

By a quick look at the picture, the list of weaknesses and threats is currently longer than benefits and opportunities. It is on such *weak points* which is necessary to investigate more.

1.7. Identification of patterns and anti-patterns

- **Patterns (best practices)**

Global reach. Most BCT-powered agri-food initiatives have a scope that reaches beyond Europe [Annex 2].

Targeting consumers. BCT as an enabler of the trust of the customer is a prized asset. Producer is interested in providing consumer access to information, to trace the origin of food and verify its authenticity. The consumer can thus check variety, time of hand-picking, localization, weather, and many other information from the stored data. In the agri-food industry, we found many examples of blockchain technology being used to benefit the consumers. In the area of consumer-centric blockchain applications, many of our UCs involve scanning a QR code with a smartphone. These cases have exploited the potential of QR codes, blockchain and other technologies. The common factor is the valorisation of a product, telling the consumer its story, enhancing its qualities in terms of sustainability and provenance. The path taken by many companies is to ensure that certain product characteristics are demonstrated through a transparent and traceable system “endorsed” by blockchain. The link between blockchain and consumer seems to have become the QR code, which is easily integrated on product labels and can be a vehicle for information that cannot be conveyed in a few centimetres of labelling. Still to be understood is if the same scope can be reached using other kind of technological solutions.

- **Anti-patterns (bad practices)**

Not building awareness of BCT in end users. “End user awareness” is, by far, the top hindering factor in solution delivery [Annex 2]. It means that understanding what exactly BCT provides, and what its shortcomings are, is a key factor for adoption from users. Currently, technology providers failed in this process.

Designing systems that are overly complex to maintain. It is not a mystery that BCT is difficult to master, from the point of view of both developers and users. However, end users are not supposed to be exposed to the intricacies of Blockchain transactions: solution providers are tasked to make their applications user-friendly, hiding complexity behind a straightforward interface. This part of the delivery process has a margin for improvement.

Use of BCT for ‘business reputation’, not considering the BCT as enabler of trust between cooperating organizations (e.g., partners of a supply chain). The possibility to use blockchain for a better supply chain management is underestimated so far.

Apply BCT in absence of:

- ✓ ***Trustworthiness of data on the ledger.*** Although, up to the recent past, the prevalent narrative was that Blockchain-secured information is trustworthy by definition, users are now increasingly aware that the level of trust in data mainly depends on the trust in its source: it doesn’t matter that the storage is secure if the information is unreliable.
- ✓ ***Trustworthiness of binding between data and physical assets.*** This problem arises when BCT is used for tracing agri-food supply chains: Blockchain records are supposed to be related with specific physical items – e.g., an individual consumer product, a crate of supplies, or anything of relevance – but there are no strong guarantees that this is always the case: the same ID code (either printed or embedded in a tag) may be applied to

multiple items, without the possibility for users or auditors to spot such violation of rules.

1.8. Topics for further discussion with stakeholders

The process of data mapping, collection have represented the main baseline for the identification of stakeholders.

Without overstepping our role (WP3 is responsible for recruiting the members of our stakeholders' board), we suggest engaging with the following groups, each focused on some specific topics:

- regulators and lawmakers;
- PA officials;
- consumers that had some usage experience of BCT-based solutions;
- the providers of such solutions;
- social scientists

In terms of Topics for future discussions, the following (not exhaustive) issues are suggested:

- What are the technical and governance shortcomings of BCT that are perceived as a hindering factor, in particular when it comes to operating a solution?
- When a BCT-based solution is not the only possible path to the business objectives, is the BCT choice worthwhile, considering its development and operational costs?
- Can consumer be guaranteed on traceability and transparency along the supply chain without the use of blockchain?
- Are public fundings a basic-element for a wider BCT application in agri-food sector?
- How to solve the lack of trustiness along the supply chain?
- What are the factors which could contribute to enhance "End user awareness"?
- What is behind the term "complexity of the systems"? Are interoperability and technical skills the only main issues to be solved? What about standardization?
- What are the BCT features which can contribute to climate change mitigation & adaptation?
- What are the technical characteristics of a blockchain system that could make records legally binding?
- How to leverage the European Blockchain Services Infrastructure (EBSI)
- Impact of the coming eIDAS v2 standard and European Digital Identities
- Role of private capital vs public investment in BCT-powered social good
- How much true decentralization (i.e., enabling zero-trust business ecosystem) plays a role in the adoption of BCT-based solution? Are partially- or even non-decentralized Blockchain networks still useful, when compared to their non-BCT equivalents?
- What are the most compelling technical features of BCT, besides decentralization?
- What about ROI?

A1.1. Definition of Pilot/Use Case (UC)

What is a “pilot project” in research? A pilot (experiment, study, test or project) is a small-scale preliminary study conducted to evaluate feasibility, duration, cost, adverse events, and improve upon the study design prior to performance of a full-scale project.

Use case means an operational scenario in a particular environment in which a user performs actions by the use of a system to achieve a goal.

In our study, **Pilots/use cases** are intended as applicative cases of blockchain technology in an operational scenario (integrating it in on-going activities/procedures/processes) to test its performances and decide if to move towards a full-scale application.

Such kind of Pilots/use cases can be carried out through funded projects (at national/EU level) or through private (and self-funded) initiatives.

A1.2. Secondary and primary research

The significance of blockchain for supply chains has been extensively debated in academic literature in recent years. A considerable portion of the identified literature concentrates on Bitcoin and investigates potential use cases. However, it fails to depict the current market state and its advancement.

Our analysis begins from a different perspective by exploring the state of blockchain adoption by companies (intended as “users”), based on publicly available data. Through our study, we mapped/collected and analyzed **320 pertinent blockchain initiatives**. **For more details, refer to D2.2.**

A1.3. Methodology

The use of blockchain technology in agri-food applications in **Europe, Africa and Middle East** was examined until the end of winter 2022, mostly based on publicly available data from companies’ websites and articles. The research followed a methodical process, started with the collection of raw data from various sources and followed by the data cleaning stage.

As clarified in D2.2, a taxonomy has been set up in order to classify and compare results, validated and shared with other members of the consortium (**Table 1**).

Table 1 - Taxonomy

Field	Description	Value	Value Description
Name	The name of the project/initiative/system	-	-
Description	Textual description of the project found on source documents/websites	-	-
Short Description	Brief description of the project	-	-
Main goals	The stated main goals/benefits of deploying a blockchain	Efficiency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Process efficiency – contribute for supply chain efficiency by streamlining the process of product confirmation, authorizations for processing products, etc... • Cost reduction – contribute to decreasing costs of production / money transfers for specific objectives • Less intermediaries
		Traceability (WHERE)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Item traceability – any physical product • Processes – tracing processes performed in a supply chain (e.g., production process) • Digital asset traceability – tracing digital currencies, NFTs or any other asset in order to know, for example, where it is used/spent
		Transparency (HOW)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Item transparency – any physical product proof of origin and authenticity • Processes Transparency – Know what was done during the processes (e.g., production process) • Digital Asset Transparency – How was the asset used • How food was gathered/stored/processed/etc
		Env. & Societal Concerns	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improvement in tracking societal and environmental issues, fairer income distribution, crisis funding distribution, carbon tracking
		Safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Item Safety – physical objects were subject to safety concerns (e.g., temperature/humidity constrains, non-contamination, product test results, product recall processes) • Process Safety – process control enabling safer processes
		Authenticity of Documents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Make documents (e.g., certifications, invoices, docking authorizations, product dispatch authorization, etc., student qualifications) easily authenticated • Use NFTs/Cryptocurrencies and authorization mechanisms as mechanism to access services
		Insurance Settlement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Streamline the insurance claims and confirmation process more effective • Make insurance services available to areas where there is no such services
		General purpose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solution designed to tackle a multitude of objectives, with no mention of cryptocurrencies/NFTs

		Money/Cryptocurrency/Asset exchange	• Solution to ease the exchange of money/cryptocurrency or any digital asset for general purposes
		Records management	• Solution design specifically to tackle records management (e.g., patient's data)
		Finance	• Solutions specifically designed for the Financial sector
		Digital Identity	• Solution that employs non trivial Digital Identity mechanisms (more than simple user name and password), like Self-Sovereign Identity
Consortium Type	Status of the involved parties (Public/Private/NGO/Hybrid)	Public	-
		Private	-
		Hybrid	-
Funding	Project funding sources Public (EU, National)/Private/Hybrid	Yes/No	-
Permission model	Permissioned/Permissionless/Hybrid	Permissioned/Permissionless/Hybrid	-
Cryptocurrency/Tokens	Whether the system supports any form of cryptocurrency or token	Yes/No	-
Countries	Countries involved in the project	List of countries	-
Inside EU	Whether the project has members inside/outside the EU	Yes/No	-
Website	The website of the project	-	-
Contacts	Contacts of key person, could be used to clarify certain aspects of the project	-	-
Technology	Blockchain technology used (e.g.: Fabric, R3 Corda, Etherem, etc)	-	-
Single/Multi organization	Whether the project involves a single or multiple organizations/partners/companies/public entities	Single/Multiple	-
Information sources	Pointers to the sources used (website, technical reports, news articles, etc)	-	-
Deployment	Where the nodes are deployed: on prem/cloud/hybrid	on-prem / cloud / hybrid	-
Industry / Sector	The industry of the project (Agrifood/Financial/IoT/L	Finance	-
		Healthcare	-
		Agrifood	-

Logistics/NGO/Humanitarian Aid/Others)	Humanitarian Aid	-
	Real estate	-
	Insurance	-
	General	-
	Banking	-
	Retail	-
	Post	-
	Logistics	-
	Art	-
	Forestry	-
	Entertainment	-
	Development and Construction	-
	Transportation	-
	Tourism	-
	Public Administration	-
	Artisan	-
	Jewelry	-
	Smart City	-
Infrastructure	-	
Social Economy	-	
Education	-	

Furthermore, other more technical classification parameters have been added ([Table 2](#)).

Table 2 – Other technical classification parameters

Field	Description
RFID	Indicate (with an "x") if the description of the solution has any hints on to the usage of this technology
Manual Insertion of data	Indicate (with an "x") if the description of the solution has any hints on to the usage of this technology
Paper document	Indicate (with an "x") if the description of the solution has any hints on to the usage of this technology
IoT devices	Indicate (with an "x") if the description of the solution has any hints on to the usage of this technology
QR Code	Indicate (with an "x") if the description of the solution has any hints on to the usage of this technology
Barcode	Indicate (with an "x") if the description of the solution has any hints on to the usage of this technology
smart phones	Indicate (with an "x") if the description of the solution has any hints on to the usage of this technology
Cryptocurrencies	Indicate (with an "x") if the description of the solution has any hints on to the usage of this technology
Digital Documents (excel, word, etc...)	Indicate (with an "x") if the description of the solution has any hints on to the usage of this technology
Electronic Data Interchange (invoices, etc)	Indicate (with an "x") if the description of the solution has any hints on to the usage of this technology
Official Websites information	Indicate (with an "x") if the description of the solution has any hints on to the usage of this technology
APIs	Indicate (with an "x") if the description of the solution has any hints on to the usage of this technology

A1.4. Limits of the Database

As already clarified in D2.2.,

- It is to be expected that the consortium was able to map and collect some (not all) use cases.
- Our research scope returned heterogeneous data that were not easy to classify for conducting the study. For example, some of these data sources do not make a distinction between use cases/ projects, consulting services, initiatives, blockchain associations, and so on. Furthermore, restricting ourselves to publicly available data, the public information was often inconclusive for defining certain categories of the taxonomy challenging the proper classification of projects concerning these categories. In some cases no technical details about the type of technology adopted, permission model, or deployment were provided. In these cases, this information was left blank.
- Finally, as a limitation, it should be noted that in most of the public available reports and databases agri-food cases resulted very few compared to applications in other sectors. This increased the difficulty for the analysis.

According to this preamble, the consortium intends to consider the presented results not as “irrefutable” evidences, but rather preliminary insights capable of providing some ‘trends’ which need to be further explored in the months to come through project activities (studies, dialogue with stakeholders).

A1.5. Analysis

Out of the 320 UCs, 191 are related to the EU, 100 are related to non-EU countries, and 23 are related to UCs involving mixed partners, both from EU and non-EU countries. The proportional representation of this evidence can be seen in **Figure 3**.

Figure 3 – Use cases per country

Interestingly, in the case of collaboration between European Union / non-EU countries, the non-EU countries involved are represented by Switzerland, China, USA, Canada, Australia, Kenya, Senegal, Vietnam, Singapore, Russia, Israel, Ghana, Rwanda, Egypt, Colombia, Brazil, Mexico, New Zealand, and Australia.

As the data on the situation in Europe are more numerous and complete (191 UCs), they will be analysed in more detail. However, considerations will also be given to the situation outside Europe where data of interest is available.

The main goal of blockchain implementation.

The main strategic purpose for approaching blockchain technology (and consequently investing on it) has been investigated. Different choices were possible:

- Efficiency: contribute for supply chain efficiency by streamlining and automatizing the process, contributing to cost reduction
- Traceability (WHERE): where information on the product could be traced through the supply chain, relating to track and trace and product provenance
- Transparency (HOW): How the product was produced (production process) and what happened along the supply chain (gathered/stored/processed/etc)
- Env. & Societal Concerns: Improvement in tracking societal and environmental issues, fairer income distribution, crisis funding distribution, carbon tracking
- Safety: physical objects were subject to safety concerns (e.g., temperature/humidity constrains, non-contamination, product test results, product recall processes)
- Authenticity of Documents: Make documents (e.g., certifications, invoices, docking authorizations, product dispatch authorization, etc., student qualifications) easily authenticated and use NFTs/Cryptocurrencies and authorization mechanisms as mechanism to access services
- Insurance Settlement: streamline the insurance claims and confirmation process more effective
- General purpose
- Money/Cryptocurrency/Asset exchange: Solution to ease the exchange of money/cryptocurrency or any digital asset for general purposes
- Records management: Solution design specifically to tackle records management (e.g., patient's data)
- Finance: Solutions specifically designed for the financial sector
- Digital Identity: Solution that employs non trivial Digital Identity mechanisms (more than simple user name and password), like Self-Sovereign Identity

This particular taxonomy of 'application areas' has been adapted from UCL Center for Blockchain Technologies (2019).

Figure 4 – EU use cases main goal

Figure 5 – EU use cases main goal (focus on Agri-food)

Figure 4 reports an overall picture on collected EU use cases, while **Figure 5** restricts the vision to agri-food sector's applications. Both figures reveal a significant emphasis on goals linked to the **traceability and transparency of food supply chains**. Several of these instances entail provenance certifications, including the Italian PGI (Protected Geographical Indication) and PDO (Protected Designation of Origin), or the traceability of high-value products such as olive oil, coffee, wine, cheese, honey, etc.

This is in line with current sector's trends. Indeed, the application of blockchain in the food sector is an emerging area and holds great promise for food safety control, with food traceability as a key application. The main areas of application in food sector that have driven its diffusion are:

- ✓ *Supply Chain Transparency*: It allows the tracking of food products from farm to fork, enabling consumers to trace the origin of food and verify its authenticity. This is especially important for addressing food safety concerns, such as foodborne outbreaks and food frauds.
- ✓ *Traceability*: Consumers are becoming more interested in knowing where their food come from. Blockchain helps providing a complete picture of the journey from the farm to the fork.
- ✓ *Food Safety*: Blockchain improves food safety by enabling real-time monitoring of food conditions during transportation and storage. Temperature, humidity, and other data points could be recorded and stored on the blockchain to ensure that food products were kept under appropriate conditions.

The complexity of the current food supply chain system, involving multiple stakeholders across different countries, results in a lack of transparency and traceability, and poses challenges related to data privacy and security. Blockchain has emerged as a highly encouraging technology in improving transparency and traceability in food supply chains.

Furthermore, *efficiency* is crucial in food production systems that involve multiple intermediaries. Therefore, implementing a blockchain system is a viable option to optimize processes, as demonstrated in [Figure 5](#).

Additionally, it is worth noting the target objective of "*Environment and Societal Concerns*". This section covers relevant case studies pertaining to topics including Carbon Footprint, decarbonisation, and carbon credits tokenisation.

This analysis aligns perfectly also with Vadgama and Tasca's (2021) findings, which suggest that blockchain is extensively employed in supply chains, logistics, product tracing, and the circular economy.

The main objectives identified in the non-European UCs are to some extent comparable with those in Europe, but there is less interest in environmental and transparency objectives, while the efficiency objective becomes even more important (2nd position), as shown in [Figure 6](#) and [Figure 7](#).

Figure 6 - Non-EU use cases main goal

Figure 7 - Non-EU use cases main goal (focus on Agri-food)

Main sectors and involved food products

Keyword research has been done within our UCs descriptions to identify the food sectors mainly involved and interlinking them with main goals. Seventeen keywords have been identified in the titles and scenarios description, and their quantitative presence is showed below in [Figure 8](#).

Figure 8 – Food sectors of use cases

Significant focus is evidently directed towards a set of products characterized by high positioning (also in consideration of their prices on the market), such as PGI, PDO, organic products and sectors with greater margin. This is an expected trend, since most of the new technologies are mainly adopted by those sectors who have higher-cost products and that can afford and absorb the related initial investments. The main representativeness is related to:

- Grapes and wine,
- Milk-dairy
- Oil

- Coffee
- Pasta
- Etc.

Wine sector is at the first position. Moving on different e-commerce websites, the average price of a wine bottle ranges from 15,66 - 32,48 \$ up to 500-1200 EUR for a gold old vintage one. It is a sector with margins that can justify investments in innovation. Vineyards, distributors, and retailers do not have the means to certify the origin or supply chain information related to their products; blockchain has the potential to improve the traceability and authenticity of the provenance data of wine products, increase consumer trust, reduce frauds and protect the brand's image. The wine industry is therefore embracing such new technology with many cases linked to consumer's use of IoT, such as NFT and QR codes, to check product's quality, accessible via blockchain. These *smart labels* enable access to information about traceability of the value chain, quality certifications, and winery origin. As an example, we can mention the Casa Girelli use case; through a collaboration with technology providers, the winery implemented blockchain to certify the organic wine production process of an organic red wine.

At the second position in the ranking we find **oil products**. A bottle of EVOO (mainly from Spain, 62.5%; Greece, 14,2%; Italy, 17,1% and Portugal, 5,5%¹) has a price of around 9-10 €/bottle (Eurostat 2022-2023). Also seed-oil increased its prices (+68,6%²). The substantial occurrence of it (palm and extra virgin olive oil) can be attributed to several factors. These factors, when considered together, could lead to the implementation of blockchain technology for certifying oil quality attributes:

- Olive oil is susceptible to fraud and adulteration, making a blockchain-based control system advisable,
- Olive oil can be marketed as a food with a Protected Denomination of Origin (PDO), necessitating rigorous supply chain management,
- Palm oil is associated with environmental issues, specifically deforestation. Therefore, documented sustainable production of palm oil is favourable.

An ambitious project of Extra Virgin Olive Oil use case is DNA Blockchain, developed through a collaboration between BioCos and InTTrust. A combination of DNA analysis, data collection, analysis with AI and Machine Learning, and blockchain offers benefits in the olive oil industry through:

- Increase of EVOO's value through transparency and consumer trust
- Beneficial impact on local producers and environment
- Food fraud reduction

For the same reasons behind oil blockchain traceability, we can see a high presence of use cases applied in **coffee's** production. This product's average price of about 12,1 €/kg (we can move from 7,9 € of the bags to 31,3 € of the capsules). In our UCs, the key motivations for adopting blockchain technology are sustainability and traceability. Moyee Coffe, for instance [Annex 1], built a pilot project to promote supply chain transparency, while making real time payments to Ethiopian farmers. Lavazza produced a specialty blend coffee, named Noble Volcano, whose production data are notarized on blockchain, with consumer access. The consumer can check coffee variety, time of hand-picking, localization, weather, and many other information from the stored data of this project.

¹ https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/news/producing-69-worlds-production-eu-largest-producer-olive-oil-2020-02-04_en

² https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/product/-/asset_publisher/VWJkHuaYvLIN/content/id/15115887/pop_up

Referring to **milk**, we mainly refer to infant formula (whose price can overcome 30 €/kg) or cheese, mostly high-quality cured cheese (e.g., Parmigiano Reggiano, whose price on the supermarkets can vary from 18-28 €/kg, or other PDO products). Milk, as stated in the JRC Technical Report “Fighting fraudulent and deceptive practices in the agri-food chain”, carries a substantial risk of fraud, such as substitution, dilution, mislabelling. Furthermore, aside from the aforementioned issues, there is also the need to maintain temperatures and storage conditions throughout the supply chain to prevent contamination, to guarantee animal welfare, and to comply with even stricter standards in the case of organic and GMO-free supply chains. Milk can be processed into various products, including butter and cheese, protected by designations of origin. The use of IoT and blockchain could be the right combination to guarantee the required standards. For instance, in the dairy industry, Arla Food has implemented a blockchain initiative named Arla Milkchain. This project aims to enhance the value of its products, including the first tested Single Estate Organic Milk. The CheeseChain project instead aims to transform the Tête-de-Moine PDO (Protected Designation of Origin) value chain by developing and implementing a built-in product authentication system, propelled by DNA technology and supported by automated fraud detection. This approach enhances proof of origin, immutability, and transparency by fusing biological data with blockchain technology, integrated with partner-specific databases.

Origin of investment (funding)

Analysing our collected data, we can argue that the type of funding behind the testing and implementation of BC is important in understanding how this technology is perceived by stakeholders. Our analysis is limited to the data available on the Database, meaning that not all the use cases were able to specify this detail. The analysis is based on these few cases, considering them in any case “significant” for capturing a trend.

Figure 9 – Fundings of EU use cases

Figure 10 – Fundings of non-EU use cases

In **Figure 9** and **Figure 10**, we can see that the funding of use cases which detailed such aspect is predominantly private. This can be due to lack of public support (e.g., funds) or as private tests done by companies supported by technology providers, who mainly propose the technology and its deployment. This is in line with the Nature of the initiative (external proposal), as shown at page 56 of this document.

Blockchain Technology used

The list of blockchains is becoming longer every day. Different authors have analysed the changing landscape of BC, and changes observed from year to year. For example, Vagdana and Tasca (2021), analysing the period 2014-2020, found that projects developed with Ethereum were dominant compared to Hyperledger until 2017, and then the trend reversed. In the meantime, new BCs have emerged, further eroding the percentages of the two giants Ethereum and Hyperledger.

The main differences between the most important blockchain platforms, Bitcoin, Ethereum, and Hyperledger Fabric, can be listed as follow in more detail (**Table 3**).

Table 3 – Blockchain Platforms Characteristics Comparison

Blockchain Characteristics Comparison			
Characteristics	Ethereum	Hyperledger	Bitcoin
Permission	Permissionless	Permissioned	Permissionless
Restricted public access to data	Public or Private	Private	Public
Consensus	Proof-of-Work	PBFT	Proof-of-Work
Scalability	High node scalability, Low performance scalability	Low node scalability, high performance scalability	High node scalability, Low performance scalability
Centralized regulation	Medium, core developer group, but EIP process	Low, open-governance model based on Linux model	Low, decentralized decision making by community/miners
Anonymity	Pseudonymity, no encryption of transaction data	Pseudonymity, encryption of transaction data	Pseudonymity, no encryption of transaction data
Native currency	Yes, Ether	No	Yes, Bitcoin

Figure 11 – Type of BC used in the use case

In line with bibliographic data (Table 3), the use cases which specified such aspect also demonstrate that the field of blockchain technology is in a state of rapid evolution (**Figure 11**). Various new technologies are emerging, providing a choice of alternatives to the current market dominators,

Ethereum and Hyperledger. The 'Other' category includes Connecting Food, FoodChain, VeChain and Polkadot. The first two have a more specific role in traceability and food supply chain management. VeChain is used for traceability and authenticity of luxury products. Finally, Polkadot is associated with the creation of interoperable blockchain ecosystems.

Understanding which technologies the market is moving towards allows us to understand what stakeholders ask for. Indeed, the technologies mentioned above have different, and in some ways opposite, characteristics, and the fact that an industry chooses one of these technologies over another means that it has sought certain characteristics. The most essential distinction between Hyperledger and Ethereum is the intent they are designed for. Ethereum runs the Smart Contracts on the EVM for Applications that are attributed to being decentralized and are for mass consumption. On the other hand, Hyperledger leverages blockchain technology for business. It is designed to support pluggable implementations of components delivering high degrees of confidentiality, resilience and scalability. Hyperledger has a modular architecture and provides a lot of flexibility in how it can be used. To stay with Ethereum and Hyperledger, for example, they differ in terms of the type of permissions, confidentiality, speed of transactions, etc.

Figure 12 – Cross-match between BCT and main goal for application

By cross-referencing the data on the BC used and the main application goals, as shown in Figure 12, we can see in the use cases which declared such detail a lower usage of Ethereum in the fields of traceability and transparency, compared to other objectives. The following reasons outline why companies might favour permissioned blockchain for managing concerns around traceability and transparency:

1. Control, as it allows the supply chain to control and validate transactions and who can participate in the network;
2. Privacy, as permissioned blockchains provide better management of data privacy by creating rules for accessing and viewing specific information on the chain;
3. Scalability, as permissioned blockchains offer superior scalability and speed compared to permissionless blockchains, enabling them to better manage high transaction volumes;
4. Regulatory compliance, as permissioned blockchains support regulatory compliance by allowing for the application of restrictions and controls, helping to ensure adherence to policies and regulations.

Associated Technologies

One of the key characteristics of BCT is the possibility of achieving decentralization. However, blockchain use cases are not necessarily decentralized. A truly decentralized blockchain can be defined as a “zero-trust” system, because users are not required to have trust in anyone in order to trust the information managed by the system. This is indeed true for cryptocurrency blockchains, like Bitcoin and Ethereum, because:

- All the information that feeds the business processes is generated internally by algorithms (e.g., the creation and transaction of digital tokens), the correctness of which is validated collectively – through some distributed consensus mechanism – by the nodes of the network.
- The validating nodes do not need to belong to trusted entities, because their correct behaviour is guaranteed by a system of economic incentives that is also entirely based on algorithms.

On the other hand, blockchain applications that deal with data that is sourced externally are not zero-trust systems, because users have to trust the external sources in the first place: the output of any IT system can only be as accurate as the information entered into it. The trustworthiness of a system of record does not come from its records being stored on a blockchain, but from their contents being subject to rules that are impossible to circumvent. Therefore, keeping track of real-world things and events cannot be done by BCT alone, as it is important that the data entered into the blockchain is also reliable from the outset.

Some of the most interesting technologies to be used in combination with blockchain are:

- Smart Contracts: self-executing digital contract or agreement, encoded in computer code and stored on a blockchain or distributed ledger, which automate and enforce the terms of an agreement without the need for intermediaries. Smart contracts typically operate on the basis of pre-defined rules and conditions, and when these conditions are met, the contract is automatically executed.
- IoT devices: RFID, NFC, QR codes, and barcodes serve as tools for monitoring and following physical goods, supporting key objectives such as enhancing efficiency and traceability. Some of these technologies even allow for the inclusion of additional information, such as website URLs or details related to physical or digital assets, empowering end users to access more products’ information and history. IoT sensors play a pivotal role in capturing diverse types of data, including footage, temperature, pressure, humidity, light intensity, wind intensity.

Internet of Things (IoT) is a system that works over a network with uniquely identified machines, devices, animals, objects, and people, which are interrelated, and they have the potential to transmit the data among themselves without any interaction between them. The IoT integrated blockchain system provides enough benefits such as connecting the flows in the supply chain to improve the efficiency of the supply chain network. It makes the system transparent, reducing the code of conduct violation throughout the supply chain networks, while the immutable properties help the stakeholders to trace the products throughout the networks.

Even though blockchain based system provides enough benefits across industries, so far the implementation rate is very low, because of the lack of knowledge about its benefits, as well as lack of understanding about how and why it is needed in their fields.

As previously mentioned presenting the wine sector, a concrete IoT and blockchain application example could be the use of a QR code on a product that contains an RFID chip. Buyers can scan the QR code with their smartphone to get detailed information about the origin of the product, while at the same time the RFID chip can be read and the information checked on the blockchain to ensure traceability, providing security and transparency for both consumers and producers. Furthermore, in

the case of fresh products, tools like data loggers can be used to record the maintenance of the refrigerated temperature at all stages of production and transport. These data can be notarised on a blockchain, making the product's characteristics trustworthy and tamper-proof.

The BC framework could be represented with a multilevel system, whose architecture is represented below (Figure 13). The system has three layers as follows.

- **Physical layer:** This layer consists of different food products from different farmers and producers within the supply chain.
- **Digital data layer:** This layer includes digital data associated with the produce belonging to the physical layer, which will be used for traceability and accessibility. One example of the data of the produce could be the expiry date of the food product.
- **Cloud layer:** In this layer, the digital data are processed in the cloud using BC, which is used for traceability and accessibility.

Figure 13 – Blockchain framework

An example of framework to digitise the food production data in the four different phases (production, processing, distribution, and retailing) of the supply chain and make the data available and accessible to consumers (consumption) for verification purposes using the QR code is shown in the Figure 14. For this exemplar supply chain, we considered the production and processing phases to happen at the farm, whereas the warehouse represents the distribution phase and the shops the retail phase. The food item is produced and processed at farm level, where the relevant information is digitised and stored in a block, and then, the item is transported to a warehouse/distribution centre, from which the item is finally transported to a shop for consumers to buy. In each step/phase of this supply chain, new transactions are created that allow to track and trace.

Figure 14 – Digitalisation of production: exemplar supply chain

In the agri-food industry, we found many examples of blockchain technology being used to benefit the production process and customers. In the area of consumer-centric blockchain applications, many of our UCs involve scanning a QR code with a smartphone. For example:

- FoodInsights is an IT provider focused on the food supply chain, from farm to fork. FoodInsights provides transparency solutions, such as blockchain, together with database-driven storytelling to consumers. By scanning a QR code, additional product information, not mentioned in label, is presented to the consumer, creating further trust.
- Ponti is the leading Italian vinegar producer, which stores product details on the blockchain. Customers can access this information through a QR code or the company's website. Customers can access information such as the harvest date, variety and origin of the apples used in each batch of vinegar. This additional information complements the content of the label by giving customers a more complete overview of the product's production process. This openness towards the consumer leads to greater trust in the company, thanks to increased traceability and transparency.

We found other QR code associated UCs (VeChain, Gruppo Felsineo, FoodChain, Colli del Garda, Supreme Green Cotton, Devoleum, Cantina Volpone, etc.). These cases have exploited the potential of QR codes, blockchain and other technologies, whether these companies are IT providers or producers in the food supply chain. The common factor is the valorisation of a product, telling the consumer its story, enhancing its qualities in terms of sustainability and provenance. As analysed above, many of these cases relate to valuable products (cured meats, coffee, wine), but also to products that may be at risk in terms of sustainability (cotton, palm oil). The path taken by many companies is to ensure that certain product characteristics are demonstrated through a transparent and traceable system **“endorsed” by the blockchain**. The link between blockchain and consumer seems to have become the QR code, which is easily integrated on product labels and can be a vehicle for information that cannot be conveyed in a few centimetres of labelling. To be still understood if the same scope can be reached using other kind of technological solutions.

BCT applications for climate change mitigation and adaptation – preliminary findings

Preliminary remark

The following explanations present the preliminary results of Task 4.1 activities on climate change impact & agriculture. The analysis builds upon the collected use cases of our Database, result of WP2 activities carried out in the first year of the project. Due to the amount of analyzed use cases not statistically representative, the goal is not to exactly describe “certain” facts, but rather to **capture a trend** on blockchain’s use in the agri-food and agriculture domain for sustainability reasons. By doing so, the aim is to **understand how the potential of this technology can be utilized to address ‘climate change mitigation & adaptation’ and the related impact on the agriculture and agri-food domain**.

Methodology

In this section, a new methodology will be outlined to identify and categorize climate change related use cases among the overall collected use cases of 317 provided by the TRUSTyFOOD consortium in WP2 at the date of the analysis.

The methodology is divided into 2 phases:

Phase 1 – Identification

Phase 2 – Categorization

The phases are described below.

Phase 1 – Identification

In accordance with the objectives outlined in Task 4.1, the focus was set on determining blockchain-based use cases related to Green House Gas Emission (GHG) Tracking, especially in the field of agriculture and their technological maturity.

Phase 1 runs in two steps:

- Step 1 – Broad search: Each of the 317 use cases provided by the TRUSTyFOOD consortium, which was also the foundation to create the [Dashboard](#), contained a short description that was used to screen for keywords that are closely related to sustainability and climate change. Even though the primary objective was to focus on climate-change related use cases, the inclusion of sustainability-related use cases was made due to the intersecting goals of both areas as sustainability addresses economic, societal, and environmental challenges. The keywords therefore included words such as reduction of food waste, plastic recovery, sustainable supply chain, sustainability-driven, etc. This search resulted in 47 cases overall.
- Step 2 – Focused search: Subsequently, among the 47 use cases, the focus was narrowed down to those related to GHG emission tracking and offset. Similar to the approach of step 1, a key word analysis was used and included among other words emission trading, carbon, product carbon footprint, reduce greenhouse gas, decarbonization, climate resilient or low carbon. This search resulted in 22 use cases.

Phase 2 – Categorization

After identifying relevant use cases for GHG emission, the next step involved the development of a categorization model for the identified use cases. To do so Gausemeier & Plass³ propose various tools and strategies which support companies to adapt to new innovations and changing market conditions. One of them includes the integrated market-technology-portfolio analysis by McKinsey, which was adapted for our purpose to analyze climate-change related use cases as seen in [Figure 15](#). The categorization consists of three dimensions and will be further detailed:

- 2.1 Market clusters
- 2.2 Industries
- 2.3 Technology Readiness Level

It should be noted that the current approach to categorizing is still a work in progress, as it mainly relied on manual work and might therefore be influenced by subjectivity. In the future, improvements such as using text mining tools could be applied to improve the accuracy and reliability of our analysis. Nevertheless, despite its limitations, the current state of the work provides a foundation to further improve upon during the remaining work related to Task 4.1.

³ Gausemeier, J.; Plass, C. (2013). Unternehmensgestaltung 2.A: Strategien, Geschäftsprozesse und IT-Systeme für die Produktion von morgen. Carl Hanser Verlag. <https://doi.org/10.3139/9783446438422>

Figure 15 – Technological maturity of use cases for GHG emission

2.1 Market Clusters

The vertical axis marks the market clusters, through an analysis of the use cases related to GHG emissions, three market trends emerged and clusters were formed:

- A. Circular Economy
- B. Carbon Farming
- C. Carbon Trading

The clusters are described in the following sections:

A. Circular Economy

The Circular Economy is a production and consumption model that emphasizes sharing, reusing, repairing, and recycling existing materials and products as long as possible. Its core objective is to extend the lifespan of products while minimizing waste generation. ⁴

Traceability and transparency are regarded as enabling factors of the circular economy. Among different technological options to implement traceability and transparency in global supply chains, blockchain technology has gained particular interest. ⁵ Another discussed enabler for the Circular

⁴ https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/headlines/economy/20151201STO05603/circular-economy-definition-importance-and-benefits?at_campaign=20234-Economy&at_medium=Google Ads&at_platform=Search&at_creation=RSA&at_goal=TR_G&at_audience=circular%20economy&at_topic=Circular Economy&at_location=DE&gclid=EAlaIqobChMIInrCD-qTXgQMVUvhRCh14qw3kEAAAYASAAEgJG3PD_BwE

⁵ <https://circulareconomy.earth/publications/supply-chain-traceability-and-transparency-for-a-global-circular-economy>

Economy is the Digital Product Passport, which represents “[...] a set of data summarizing a product’s components, materials, chemical substances and/or information on reparability, replacement parts and proper disposal. The data originates from all phases of the product life cycle and can be used for various purposes in all these phases (design, manufacture, use, and disposal)⁶”. The use of blockchain-based Digital Product Passports is actively being researched and developed.⁷

The compound annual growth rate (CAGR) for the global circular economy market is estimated to be 9% for the period of 2021-2026. Due to the exponential growth of the population, the increase of food consumption and food waste is a major concern for governments around the world, which drives them towards sustainable approaches such as the circular economy to minimize food waste.⁸

B. Carbon Farming

Carbon Farming describes the sequestration (removal) and storage of carbon and/or reduction of greenhouse gas emissions at farm level. Even though the mitigation potential for climate change is still uncertain, the EU nevertheless considers it as a significant contribution towards reaching the objectives as laid out in the European Union Green Deal and climate mitigation in the EU.⁹

Blockchain-based carbon removal or offset projects include for instance the evaluation of CO2 absorption potential of forests via satellite images and documenting these results on a blockchain to create CO2-certificates.¹⁰ In other words, with the introduction of Blockchain-Technology, it is possible to tokenize, i.e., represent intangible assets such as CO2-emissions, as a tamper-proof and digital version, which can be owned and transferred.¹¹

C. Carbon Trading

The adoption of sustainable farming practices requires concrete incentives. For farmers to implement sustainable practices in the short term, economic benefits in form of increased productivity or profitability are essential. In the long term, farmers are motivated by the perceived positive outcomes for their farm or the environment.¹² However, farmers are not adequately compensated to adopt and maintain sustainable practices, e.g., the value of carbon credits is either too low or fees for intermediaries significantly lower the profit margins for farmers.¹³

Blockchain-Technology attempts to solve this problem by not only providing the ability to tokenize intangible assets but to provide a market infrastructure for such assets to be traded. One example would be the application of Blockchain-Technology in Voluntary Carbon Markets (VCM). Current barriers in VCMs are lack of transparency and standardized verification processes to ensure high-quality carbon-credits. Blockchain-based carbon market platforms such as Toucan offer the possibility to automatically track and manage carbon credits and reduce the risk of double-counting (i.e., when

⁶ <https://epub.wupperinst.org/frontdoor/deliver/index/docId/8042/file/WP198.pdf>

⁷ <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf/10.1002/cite.202100121>

⁸ <https://www.marknteladvisors.com/research-library/global-circular-economy-market.html>

⁹ [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2021/695482/IPOL_STU\(2021\)695482_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2021/695482/IPOL_STU(2021)695482_EN.pdf)

¹⁰ <https://carbonstack.de/#/de/>

¹¹ <https://www.mckinsey.com/featured-insights/mckinsey-explainers/what-is-tokenization>

¹² <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41893-020-00617-y>

¹³ <https://thecounter.org/carbon-farming-blockchain-climate-change-regenerative-agriculture/>

two different parties claim the same carbon credit).¹⁴¹⁵

The CAGR of the global carbon credit market is estimated to be 24.4% for the period of 2023-2030.¹⁶

2.2 Industries

The industries have already been predefined from Task 2.1. In **Figure 15** the industries are shown through different bubble sizes.

The bigger ones refer to **use cases relevant to the agri-food and agriculture** domain and the **smaller bubbles refer to other industries**, such as real estate (brown), transportation (yellow), general (blue) or forestry (grey).

2.3 Technology Readiness Level

The horizontal axis represents the maturity assessment of the blockchain-technology itself. The methodology was based on the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) framework that has been used in EU funded projects since 2014 as part of the Horizon 2020 research and innovation funding program.¹⁷ The TRL framework has already previously been used to assess blockchain use cases for carbon markets.¹⁸

The TRL framework consists of 9 stages:

- TRL 1 — Basic principles observed
- TRL 2 — Technology concept formulated
- TRL 3 — Experimental proof of concept
- TRL 4 — Technology validated in a lab
- TRL 5 — Technology validated in a relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)
- TRL 6 — Technology demonstrated in a relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)
- TRL 7 — System prototype demonstration in an operational environment
- TRL 8 — System complete and qualified
- TRL 9 — Actual system proven in an operational environment

TRL Model adaptation and evaluation criteria

Adaptations to the TRL were done for our work as such a fine-grained differentiation was not possible to achieve without substantial effort into each use case (e.g., requesting further information, writing email, etc.). As previously stated, the purpose of this work was to capture a direction of the current development, therefore the TRLs were grouped together under following categories:

1. TRL 1-2 = Concept (theoretical and experimental)
2. TRL 3-4 = Prototype (implementation in isolated environment)
3. TRL 5-7 = Pilot (implementation in real environment)
4. TRL 8-9 = Production (fully working product in operational environment)

For the categorization of each use case, criteria based on the TRL framework¹⁵ and blockchain-specific evaluation criteria were taken into consideration.¹⁶

¹⁴ <https://toucan.earth/>

¹⁵ <https://www.coindesk.com/consensus-magazine/2023/04/21/unleashing-the-green-economy-how-blockchain-can-transform-climate-friendly-investment-opportunities/>

¹⁶ <https://www.coherentmarketinsights.com/market-insight/global-carbon-credit-market-4382>

¹⁷ <https://horizoneuropencpportal.eu/sites/default/files/2022-12/trl-assessment-tool-guide-final.pdf>

¹⁸ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2590332222003256>

Phase	Concept	Prototype	Pilot	Production
Characteristica	Theoretical & Experimental	Implementation in isolated environment („laboratory“)	Prototype implementation in industry-relevant or operational environment	System complete, implementation in operational environment and full integration with existing systems
TRL equivalence	1 & 2	3 & 4	5, 6 & 7	8 & 9
Examples	<p>-Oleificio Zucchi did an announcement but further research on their progress did not result in any findings/updates</p> <p>-Grove Mango Trust, no updates since 2020 and only research paper published to present concept</p>	<p>Fjord Maritime built PoC in 2020, tested their hypothesis and did built their solution on a second layer blockchain nahmii. However, no further updates regarding expansion to other partners/customers</p>	<p>Tradelens, had a big network of partners and customers in real environment, however were closing down due to the lack of viable business income and therefore not used</p>	<p>Toucan, code publicly available, over 50 climate projects were involved and more than 4 billion USD of carbon trading volume, were used to bridge Verra Carbon Credits (integration with existing systems), however due to quality concerns of carbon credits currently on pause</p>
Evaluation Criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Mainly based on theory, concept clearly explained, scientific research just started ▪ Tests are designed and have to be conducted based on the initial findings ▪ Technical details listed, including blockchain platform and consensus mechanism, however technology still very speculative 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Tests/experiments were conducted which support initial findings ▪ (private) Proof-of-concept model constructed ▪ Technology is feasible from scientific point of view ▪ Basic technology implemented together in isolated environment/laboratory to show they work together ▪ data published on the technology, either through open source code platforms, transaction data, or through published data (on website) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Solution now tested in environment, which is closer to real one (although still under controlled conditions) → Technological feasibility proven ▪ 2+ partnerships with external companies announced. The pre-condition is, that the organization has already proven their use case internally before collaborating with others. ▪ Solution now tested in real environment → Engineering feasibility proven ▪ media reports or public data released of partner PoC or pilot successfully using the technology ▪ proof of use in an operational supply chain as opposed to using a test environment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Implementation and integration of new technology in its final form with existing technology ▪ Stable version of software available ▪ New technology after integration can operate under full commercial deployment ▪ If produced, the planned product roadmap is completed. ▪ Security and quality have been verified by third parties. ▪ If possible, all code is publicly available in open-source projects and functional. ▪ blockchain technology is fully integrated into the system and operating competitively to other projects
Value range in Excel Table	[0-1]	[1,1 - 2]	[2,1 – 3]	[3,1 – 4]

Table 4 – Adapted Technology Readiness Level Mode

The level of maturity of BCT applications

The above-mentioned developed methodology to estimate the technological maturity for blockchain climate change use cases was in a next step applied to collected use cases that focus on agriculture and agri-food. In order to identify the relevant use cases, the list of 317 was filtered according to the industry that included agri-food, agriculture and sustainable agriculture. This resulted in overall 174 use cases of which the **technological maturity** should be assessed.

For the evaluation, one main researcher and two research assistants from FHG were involved to prevent bias of the results by only one reviewer. After the first round of independent evaluation was completed, the main researcher followed with a quality check and made corrections or added additional information that supported the given score.

As shown in **Figure 16** out of the 174 use cases, 11 were excluded as the assessment showed that they were not relevant to the agri-food domain. One reason was that the use case had started in the agriculture domain but then switched over time to a different service offering, e.g., Ambrosus who combined IoT and blockchain for supply chain management in agriculture in 2017, changed their focus in 2022 to provide a blockchain ecosystem in general.¹⁹ Other reasons for exclusion were that the use case was active in a different industry, did not build their solution on blockchain at all or only offered the possibility to integrate their non-blockchain solution with other blockchains. Furthermore, 35 use cases seemed to have ceased their activity as their website was inaccessible or the latest update on their website or social media was made several months or even years ago. Despite the inactivity of some use cases, evaluations were still conducted whenever possible, as the current stage of the case before its discontinuation was considered useful in assessing the technology's maturity – overall 19 use cases belonged to that category. Last but not least, 128 use cases were still actively used or developed.

Figure 16 - Overview status of blockchain use cases in agrifood and agriculture domain

After the relevant use cases were identified, **Figure 17** shows the final evaluation result on the blockchain technology maturity in agri-food and agriculture for 147 cases. As can be seen, the technology is still being actively explored with 36% showing characteristics of a prototype followed by 31% in the pilot phase, which test the solution under conditions that are similar to the real world. 18%

¹⁹ <https://ambrosus.io/>

fall into the 'concept' phase and it shall be noted that research projects, despite their complexity and involvement of other partners tend to fall into that category as the project goal does usually not require the development of a working product. To conclude, around 15% seem to have reached production stage.

Figure 17 - Technology maturity according to their phase (n = 147)

Figure 18 looks at each phase and their activity status. Out of 28 concept cases, 6 or 21% are inactive, for the 56 prototype cases this holds true for 10 or 18% and the pilot cases have around 3 or 7% inactive out of the 43. Regarding the production cases, all are still active. In conclusion, the analysis validates the trend that increased maturity correlates with a reduced likelihood of failure.

Figure 18 Phase & activity status of use cases

Another point worth mentioning is that several of the identified use cases do not build their own blockchain solutions but rely on Blockchain-as-a-Service (BaaS) instead to implement their case. What is more, many cases only mention the use of blockchain on a very high level. Figure 19 therefore gives an overview of some of the underlying blockchain solutions. It is important to differentiate between

native blockchains such as Algorand, Quorum, VeChain, Polygon or Quadrans and service providers, who build their offerings on top of blockchains. To the latter group belongs IBM Food Trust, which is based on the Hyperledger Fabric framework that allows companies to create their own blockchain. This was the most used one, followed by Connecting Food Solution, Genuine Way or EZ Lab. Established companies such as SAP, Microsoft or Ernst & Young (EY) also offer a blockchain-based platform so use cases can build on top of the pre-established blockchain infrastructure and reach at least the maturity of a prototype with reduced effort. As an example, IBM Food Trust provided the technology for known food & retail corporates such as Nestlé, Carrefour, Barilla or even assembled several Norwegian seafood companies and institutes create to create traceability in the fishery industry.

Figure 19 Applied Blockchain or Blockchain-as-a-Service

For the evaluation of the blockchain maturity cases, the use of BaaS however poses the question whether the maturity of the BaaS provider should be assessed or the use case as a whole? When a BaaS provider has other companies use their blockchain technology, they have reached production level as the product is used by final customers, e.g., IBM Food Trust. On the other side, when looking at the use cases, they can differ from how advanced they are in being implemented even though they share the same underlying technology. Another aspect exemplified by the IBM Food Trust and Norwegian Fishery case is that the pilot stage for the involved cases is reached when a central platform provider unites different use cases to participate on their platform. What needs to be considered then is, how use cases compare, who do not rely on such a central provider to reach the pilot stage.

Furthermore, another challenge was that use cases mentioned the use of blockchain among other technologies such as AI or IoT. For such cases, on first sight the maturity appears to be high as they have a fully working product. Even so, when trying to understand the role of blockchain technology, the maturity could be substantially lower as they only explain the use of blockchain on a generic level among all their other technologies involved.

Third, the differentiation between prototype and pilot was at times challenging. As a common application area of blockchain is food traceability, e.g., for coffee, this naturally requires the involvement of several external partners, beginning from the farmers, to the processors, the retailers and customers, which moves the maturity closer to the pilot stage. However, from the perspective of a food retailer company, that wants to track their offered product, this can in cases be seen as an advanced prototype to test the basic functionalities of the blockchain for their case, which could not be done without involving other parties.

A1.6. Conclusions

A growing number of blockchain initiatives in food supply chain are emerging, challenging traditional business models. Despite the complexity of UC classification revealed by our research, the amount of UCs collected and analysed has given preliminary useful information regarding to BC strategy and application, even if the wide application nuances revealed the difficulty of comparing them. Our findings are shown below.

Blockchain technology has mainly been focused on cryptocurrencies and financial transactions. Nevertheless, it is widely recognized the limitless potential for blockchain's application in various domains, in particular in agri-food. Key areas for exploration encompass:

- **Transparent Supply Chains:** The need for traceability and accountability within the food industry is more crucial than ever, particularly in light of the growing global trade. Manufacturing processes span the globe, often in a lack of transparency among suppliers. Blockchain technology emerges as a promising solution to address these supply chain challenges, facilitating traceability.
- **Automation:** Blockchain-based process automation offers numerous benefits, including cost reduction, human error elimination, increased transparency and security, and the ability to create more efficient and reliable processes. The use of blockchain in supply chain management is a powerful tool to immediate costs- savings, but also contribute to long-term operational efficiency and competitiveness within the industry.
- **Digital Product Identity/Passport:** Blockchains record all critical information about a particular item, such as its production route, provenance, quality certifications and other relevant data also related to sustainability. Thanks to blockchain, this digital product identity can be reliably verified by all parties involved, including manufacturers, distributors, retailers and consumers. Blockchain can help combat counterfeiting and ensure the authenticity of products throughout their lifecycle, supporting Circular Economy.
- **Synergizing Blockchain with the Internet of Things (IoT):** Blockchain's potential is intriguing when integrated with Internet of Things (IoT) solutions. IoT inherently comprises a network of dispersed devices, aligning seamlessly with blockchain's distributed ledger capabilities. The key advantage of applying blockchain technology to IoT lies in the trust it instils, enhancing data integrity and reliability.
- **Sustainability:** Blockchain is adopted also for Circular Economy, Carbon Farming and Carbon Trading purposes.

Figure 20 – Summary of insights derived from Database analysis

In the ANNEX 4 there is the list of use cases mapped, collected and analysed through our work.

In order to achieve greater granularity than desktop research, it was essential to use a survey-based analysis, which is discussed in ANNEX 2.

A1.7. References:

- ✓ Vadgama and Tasca (2021), An analysis of Blockchain Adoption in Supply Chains Between 2010 and 2020, Frontier in Blockchain, 10.3389/fbloc.2021.610476
- ✓ JRC Joint Research Centre (2023), Fighting fraudulent and deceptive practices in the agri-food chain, European Commission 1831-9424
- ✓ UCL Centre for Blockchain Technologies (2019), <http://blockchain.cs.ucl.ac.uk/>

ANNEX 2

Assessment through digital resources, Surveys and Interviews

A2.1. Assessment through literature review

We started from collecting a comprehensive library of papers, articles, and other qualified digital resources that were related to the use of BCT in the agri-food context. The complete list is provided in ANNEX 5 – List of digital resources. We got through a first, high-level review of these resources to identify those that had the most value for our research. The selection criteria were: relevance, currency (should not contain or be based on outdated information) and novelty (should include at least some original elements or present some new perspectives). Most of the items that were not included in our shortlist failed the relevance check, as they were focused on the theoretical analysis of *potential* BCT use cases, while our main interest was in its actual usage in real-world processes.

From the shortlist, we extracted what we consider are the key takeaways, which are presented below, together with a link to their source.

A2.1.1. State of play

These aspects are the most important characteristics of the current BCT solution space.

- **The use of BCT in the agri-food domain mainly concerns the integrity of agricultural production records, the monitoring of production steps, and the monitoring of products** [2]. One very visible symptom of this is the appearance of QR-Code tags on some products (not only food, but also textile), that allow consumers to retrieve “certified” provenance information from some blockchain source.
- **The prevalent rationale for BCT adoption is the immutability of data stored on the ledger** [2] – see also the previous point, where we talk about product provenance. While immutable data enable *accountability*, the big, still mostly unfulfilled BCT promise is *decentralization of control*, which may enable the disintermediation of agri-food value chains and thus a more efficient and accessible market.

A2.1.2. Main road blockers

Here we list, in no particular order, the most important critical aspects of BCT when applied to agrifood solutions.

- Issues identified in *United Nations’ 2021 report on Blockchain for Agri-food Traceability* [3]:
 - **Trustworthiness of data on the ledger.** Although, up to the recent past, the prevalent narrative was that Blockchain-secured information is trustworthy by definition, users are now increasingly aware that the level of trust in data mainly depends on the trust in its source: it doesn’t matter that the storage is secure if the information is fake²⁰. This obviously puts the most common use of BCT in agri-food under a different light.
 - **Trustworthiness of binding between data and physical assets.** This problem arises when BCT is used for tracing agri-food supply chains: Blockchain records are supposed to be related with specific physical items – e.g., an individual consumer product, a crate of supplies, or anything of relevance – but there are no strong guarantees that this is always the case: the same ID code (either printed or embedded in a tag) may be

²⁰ This elementary consideration is also known, within ICT circles, as the Garbage-In-Garbage-Out (GIGO) effect.

applied to multiple items, without the possibility for users or auditors to spot such violation of rules.

- **Scalability in IoT scenarios.** IoT is the key for *precision agriculture* and many other important processes, but it typically produces huge volumes of raw data. On the other hand, BCT is ill-suited to Big Data scenarios. The bottom line is that Blockchain-based solutions are not yet ready to address IoT problems – except for secondary aspects like identity management. This state of things may change in the future, when next-generation BCT will become available for commercial-grade application.
- **Limitation of smart contracts with respect to complex logic and integration of off-chain data sources.** This is a very technical issue that we cannot delve into here. Enough to say that smart contracts are not like your everyday computer program: they suffer from constraints that come from the need of executing the same logic on multiple nodes of a Blockchain network, and still produce identical results. This means that many use cases that would potentially benefit from BCT are simply not viable.
- **Lack of standards for cross-chain interoperability.** This is a problem that only very advanced users of BCT have: how to interconnect different Blockchain networks to create a single data space. It is not a very significant hindering factor for BCT adoption, at this stage, but may become a roadblock later.
- **Inclusion of smallholder farmers.** It is a matter of fact that BCT is complex and expensive to implement, so it's not a surprise that small enterprises are often unable to do so. Third-party solutions exist that significantly lower this barrier, to the point that no specific technical knowledge is required to participate. However, there is a more baseline obstacle along that path: the digital maturity of agri-food SMEs.
- Issues identified in *A Systematic Review of Blockchain Technology Adoption Barriers and Enablers for Smart and Sustainable Agriculture* [4]:
 - **Lack of government regulations.** Actually, this is more a perceived problem than a real one, because the legal framework for legally binding electronic transactions does exist - basically, it's eIDAS²¹: although not BCT-related, its scope is wide enough to encompass Blockchain-based solutions. However, it is true that this is a very difficult and tricky path to thread, so it makes total sense that many users are waiting for more specific regulation.
 - **Privacy and confidentiality concerns.** Blockchains are, by definition, containers of shared data. There is a reluctance to share proprietary information in all economic sectors, and agri-food is no exception. Additionally, Blockchains are not suitable for storing personally identifiable information (e.g., data related to consumers), because their immutability puts them at odds with GDPR regulation.
 - **Lack of awareness of users.** The key BCT concepts are neither well-known nor easy to grasp. This often creates a situation where an existing solution (Blockchain) is deployed to address existing problems (with questionable effectiveness), instead of modelling the solution on the problem. Moreover, it is unlikely that BCT-unaware organizations may be able to design radically new processes and/or business models that take advantage of the unique characteristics of the technology.
 - **Difficulty in usage.** It is not a mystery that BCT is difficult to master, from the point of view of both developers and users. However, end users are not supposed to be exposed to the intricacies of Blockchain transactions: solution providers are tasked to make their applications user-friendly, hiding complexity behind a straightforward interface. This part of the delivery process has currently a margin for improvement.

²¹ See <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/eidas-regulation>

- Issues identified in *Blocking blockchain: Examining the social, cultural, and institutional factors causing innovation resistance to digital technology in seafood supply chains* [5]:
 - **Entrenched players resisting innovation.** Innovation from Blockchain threatens the competitive advantage of wholesalers, since it would reverse existing asymmetries around trade, price, and provenance information.

A2.1.3. Emerging trends

- **There is a progressive shift from public (e.g., Ethereum) to permissioned/private chains (e.g., Hyperledger Fabric)** [1]. This, *if confirmed*²², would imply that users are less interested in the decentralization opportunities offered by BCT, and more on its use as a secure distributed database. However, it may simply mean that the mandatory use of a cryptocurrency to *fuel* operations on the network²³ is, in most cases, too inconvenient for end users.
- **There is increasing interest in BCT – in particular from regulators and lawmakers – as a tool to support MRV (Measuring, Reporting and Verification) for climate action** [6]. Current MRV systems provide static feedback regarding the performance of the underlying productive activity and are often considered less than trustworthy in terms of verifying the veracity of the due diligence process and therefore an unreliable source for participation in carbon credit markets. Blockchain-enabled MRV systems can track every credit certificate from the day it is created to the day it is retired and provide a record of ownership during its life and ensure that data travelling through the value chains can be verified in real time between network participants and jurisdictional authorities.

A2.2. Assessment through surveys and interviews

A2.2.1. Shortcomings of digital resources and database

Most of available literature is about theoretical research, not about the observable results of applying the technology to real business scenarios. Moreover, we wanted to ask some very specific questions to the practitioners to verify if the above-mentioned aspects (see §2.1) are confirmed.

A2.2.2. Preparation of the survey

A2.2.2.1. Modelling the topic to be investigated

The very first step in the preparation of our survey was the definition of the questions to be asked. As **our purpose was a thorough statistical analysis of the responses**, we needed to make all statistically relevant questions close-ended, which in turn meant that we had to design a *discreet model* of the topic to be investigated, providing the blueprint for the questions. Actually, we broke down this modelling task into three smaller ones:

- Design the **model of the problem**: definition of the domains characterizing the business problem addressed in the context of the BCT use case.
- Design the **model of the solution**: same as above but relative to the technical solution addressing the business problem.
- Design the **model of the outcome**: same as above but relative to the final assessment of the solution, in terms of results vs. expectations.

²² As privileged observers of the ICT market (from the perspective of a leading software solution provider company), what we see is that public and private/permissioned networks are serving different needs, and that there is a growing awareness among solution developers of what is the best BCT approach for their use cases.

²³ Transactions on a public Blockchain network are subject to a pay-per-use business model: each user submitting a transaction is charged a fee, which is paid with the platform's native cryptocurrency. This means that users must manage their crypto wallet, procuring themselves cryptocurrency funds in advance. For businesses, this may also imply a lot of accounting overhead, or even legal compliance problems.

Additionally, we also designed a **taxonomy for the classification of the use cases' context** (e.g., geographical area, business sector, etc.). This was something that was already done in the scope of task T2.2, to a great extent and depth, for the purpose of building a comprehensive use case database. However, we found that we needed a *simpler* taxonomy for grouping the answers to our survey into broad categories of use cases.

After a first iteration of design, **these four dimensions were tested by executing an *internal simulation of the survey***: some TRUSTyFOOD members having a similar profile as the survey's intended audience²⁴ tried to answer the questions and then gave their feedback on the survey itself. From this experiment, we learned that this initial version had a couple of severe shortcomings. First and foremost, some of the people did not have any practical knowledge of the underlying technologies, to the point that most of the questions were left unanswered. Secondly, some very straightforward but "difficult" questions, could not always be properly understood even by people having a technological background.

Consequently, **we revised our first design with a second iteration**. The new version of the survey contained several adjustments: the model was modified to reflect a less direct approach to our key areas of investigation, resulting into a more *user-friendly* set of questions that could still, with some interpretation on our part, do the intended job.

Here we include an overview of the discreet model that backs the survey – see Figure , Figure , Figure 2, and Figure below, which are all screenshots from the original Excel working document. There is no need for a detailed description of the individual domains, as their meaning and scope will be made clear in the section dedicated to the analysis of survey results (see §2.2.4).

Taxonomy

Profile of the initiative: classification of the use case according to some statistically relevant aspects.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N
1	Country	Area		Scope		Sector		Consumers		Funding		Organization		Maturity
2	Albania	ETA		Regional		Agrifood		Yes		Private		Private partnership		Experimental
3	Algeria	MED		National		Finance		No		Public		Public partnership		Production
4	Austria	EU		European		Insurance				Mixed		Public-private partnership		
5	Belgium	EU		European+		Logistics						Single private company		
6	Bosnia & H.	ETA		Global		Green Economy						Single public agency		
7	Bulgaria	EU				Public Administration								
8	Croatia	EU				other								
9	Republic of Cyprus	EU												
10	Czech Republic	EU												
11	Denmark	EU												
12	Egypt	MED												
13	Estonia	EU												
14	Finland	EU												
15	France	EU												
16	Germany	EU												
17	Greece	EU												
18	Hungary	EU												

Figure 21 – Survey: taxonomy (AKA profile of the initiative)

Model of the Problem

Problems and needs addressed by the solution: broad classification of business and functional requirements.

²⁴ More specifically: people who were personally involved is some agri-food BCT use case, either as a technology provider or as an end user.

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	Business Goal		Business Sensitivity		BC Functionality	
2	Business revenue		Existential		Data sharing	
3	Business efficiency		High		Notarization of documents	
4	Business reputation		Medium		Workflow management	
5	Business transparency		Low		Identity management	
6	Public health issues		Negligible		Reputation management	
7	Environmental issues				Accounting	
8	Societal issues				Token trading	
9					Payments	
10					Asset provenance / tracing	
11						
12						

Figure 22 - Survey: model of the problem

Model of the Solution

Characteristics of the blockchain-based system: some key elements that can help spotting technical trends.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	BC Platform		Ledger Access		Data Visibility		Data Storage	
2	Hyperledger Fabric		Direct		Confidential		On-chain	
3	Hyperledger Besu		Indirectly (middleware)		Registered users		Off-chain	
4	Hyperledger Sawtooth				Public			
5	Ethereum (public network)							
6	Ethereum (ad-hoc network)							
7	IBM Blockchain							
8	MS Azure Blockchain							
9	Oracle Blockchain Cloud Service							
10	Ripple							
11	Stellar							
12	ConsenSys Quorum							
13	R3 Corda							
14	Polygon							
15	Tezos							
16	MultiChain							
17	other							
18								

Figure 23 - Survey: model of the solution

Model of the Outcome

Assessment of results: measuring the initiative’s success – or lack thereof – and identification of the most typical / significant drawbacks.

	A	B	C	D	E
1	(B) Achievement of Planned Objectives		(B) Return on Investment		(T) Evaluation of Performance
2	Unacceptable		Unacceptable		Unacceptable
3	Below expectations		Below expectations		Below expectations
4	Meets expectations		Meets expectations		Meets expectations
5	Exceeds expectations		Exceeds expectations		Exceeds expectations
6	Too early to judge		Too early to judge		Too early to judge
7					
8	(T) Evaluation of Security / Robustness		Hindering Factors		Operational Issues
9	Unacceptable		Maturity of technology		Data management
10	Below expectations		Technical skills		Cybersecurity
11	Meets expectations		End user awareness		Immutability of ledger
12	Exceeds expectations		Innovation risk		Inefficiency of ledger
13	Too early to judge		Data security / confidentiality		Complexity of systems
14			Data interoperability		Unpredictable costs
15			Cross-chain interoperability		No major issues
16			Regulatory compliance		
17			No hindering factors		
18					

Figure 24 - Questionnaire: model of the outcome

A2.2.2.2. Configuring the online survey tool

For conducting the survey, we configured an online data collection tool on the Google Forms platform (https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSf0j6IYnIc0LLQP3b4kEij1DAewhxZS2cDWZHUwM_8xOfRfQ/viewform). A screenshot of the splash page is shown in **Figure** below.

The screenshot shows a Google Forms splash page with the following content:

Blockchain applications to agrifood systems: survey

Dear Sir/Madam,

TRUSTyFOOD is a research project funded by the European Commission to investigate the role that blockchain technology (BCT) can play in changing the agriculture and food system in the forthcoming years.

We noticed that you have been involved in an initiative where this technology was applied/tested, and we would like to know more about your experience both from the technical and non-technical points of view.

Your contribution is important. By putting together different cases and experiences, we hope to identify gaps, barriers, best practices, success stories, and opportunities which can help with depicting the usefulness of this solution, case by case. Thanks to our recommendations, policymakers will support investments in this field, putting more money at the disposal of farmers and other agrifood chain players for adopting it.

We hope that you are willing to take a few minutes to complete this survey and contribute to our research. It will not take much time, as most of the questions are in a closed-ended format.

The survey is split into **two** components - the first concerning the technical details of the blockchain solution you experimented with or collaborated to apply in a real-world case, and the second concerning your experiences implementing the solution.

It is not necessary to fill out both parts, but we invite you to do so if you believe your experience is relevant, or to ask a colleague/partner involved in the experimentation if they can provide support.

Please note that all personal information provided, including contact details, will be kept strictly confidential and will not be used for any purpose other than the research we are carrying out. Contact information will be stored for internal use only if you indicate your interest in participation in future TRUSTyFOOD research activities.

Thank you for your participation,

TRUSTyFOOD team

Not shared

Next Clear form

Figure 25 – Survey: splash page

After the welcome message, the survey is structured into two sections: the introductory part and the actual questionnaire. In the first part, the respondents can - optionally - introduce themselves, state their affiliation and provide some basic information about their organization.

Blockchain applications to agrifood systems: survey

Not shared 🔒

Basic Information

All information provided will be kept confidential

What organization do you belong to (company name)?

Your answer _____

What is your role within your organization?

Your answer _____

Can you provide a brief description of your organization?

What is the type of organization?
Please select all that apply

- Small/medium farm
- Large farm
- Organic farm
- Food processor
- Exporter
- Wholesale Trader
- Technology developer
- Other: _____

How many people do you employ?

- <10
- 10-100
- >100

Back
Next
Clear form

Figure 26 - Survey: introductory section

The questionnaire that follows is just a linear sequence of questions. All the questions are optional. A sample is given in [Figure 27](#) below. In order to help users in understanding all the subtleties, many close-ended questions have been laid out with plenty of context information that was not included in the original model.

Technical Questions: Problems and needs addressed by the blockchain-based solution

1. What are the goals that suggested the adoption of blockchain technology for your solution?

Please select all that apply.

- Business revenue (increase the revenue of an existing business, or create revenue from a new business)
- Business efficiency (cut the costs associated with running an existing process, or make such a process faster, more agile, or any combination of the above)
- Business reputation (improve the reputation of your organization or group of organizations, either objectively - because of specific features of the solution that make your business more trustworthy - or subjectively as a blockchain adopter)
- Business transparency (make information on your business more reliable and available to a larger audience)
- Public health issues (make your products safer for the end consumer. Note: this option means that your solution is set to concretely help in the achievement of these objectives; simply providing the means for monitoring the progress goes under the "Business reputation" goal (see #3).
- Environmental issues (make your business more sustainable from an ecological perspective, such as reducing its environmental footprint. Note: this option means that your solution is set to concretely help in the achievement of these objectives; simply providing the means for monitoring the progress goes under the "Business reputation" goal (see #3))
- Societal issues (make your business more sustainable from a social perspective, e.g., by improving inclusiveness or creating opportunities for the disadvantaged. Note: this option means that your solution is set to concretely help in the achievement of these objectives; simply providing the means for monitoring the progress goes under the "Business reputation" goal (see #3))
- Other: _____

Figure 27 – Survey: example of question, with lots of additional context information

The survey terminates with a final pair of questions that provide TRUSTyFOOD with an opportunity for a follow-up (see [Figure 28](#)), useful for WP3 activities.

Future Participation in TRUSTyFOOD

Are you interested in remaining in contact with us? *

TRUSTyFOOD will be engaging stakeholders in the coming months as part of our ongoing research on blockchain and food systems. We kindly invite all respondents to this survey to participate in future research activities (e.g., focus groups, interviews, etc) that TRUSTyFOOD will conduct to further investigate this exciting topic.

No

Yes, to receive newsletters, event invitations, or other communication

Yes, to actively participate in ongoing discussions about blockchain technology

Email address of contact person
If "yes" selected above

Your answer _____

[Back](#) [Submit](#) [Clear form](#)

Figure 28 - Survey: closing questions

A2.2.2.3. Selecting the participants to the survey

While the online survey tool was in the making, we faced the issue of how to get the *right* people on board. Our starting point was the database of BCT use cases populated by task T2.2 and released at M8 as deliverable D2.2 “Database of pilots/ use cases of projects”. At that time, the database contained 320 entries, representing 22 countries. The approach of the consortium has been that to **search a referent for the Pilot/use case**, through the public information available on the web, for asking about their experience in using the blockchain product.

Quoting from the D2.2 report: “The search was focused mostly on agriculture and agri-food projects and use cases *that use blockchain technologies, but also on projects/use cases with a foreseen relation or implications with the agri-food sector in areas such as finance, logistics, IoT and others. All the collected information was gathered from public sources [...], but in some minor cases some contacts have been taken with Organisations for obtaining support. It is the case of EIP AGRI, CINEA, Osservatorio Blockchain & Distributed Ledger of Politecnico di Milano, EU Blockchain Observatory & Forum. [...] Another important source [was the] knowledge of project’s partners on existing use cases.*” In other words, most records in the D2.2 database were fetched from public sources, but some were contributed directly by TRUSTyFOOD partners thanks to their direct knowledge of the case. However, many of these records (in particular, those from public source) lacked the contact details of a representative that could be invited, or in most of the cases a generic contact point, along the lines of “info@company.com”, was provided reducing the number of contactable respondents.

Another issue was that, as we realized during our *internal simulation* (see §2.2.2.1), some technical questions were too difficult to be understood by our average respondent. This problem was likely to be exacerbated by the language barrier in countries where English is not commonly spoken. To mitigate this risk and maximize the quality of results, we decided that every respondent should receive, while taking the survey, real-time assistance from a technically qualified member of the TRUSTyFOOD

consortium that could speak their native language. In other words, the *survey experience* was going to look quite similar to an interview. As a cautionary step, we ran an internal training session for TRUSTyFOOD members who were going to provide assistance, to ensure consistency in the explanations given to the respondents.

The original dataset of 320 records had to be revised, excluding those cases that had some obvious mismatch with the TRUSTyFOOD scope and followed with those with no clear path for a contact. The remaining subset was then invited by means of an email message, sent by the TRUSTyFOOD member connected to the invitee.

A2.2.3. Execution of the survey

The execution of the survey was a very straightforward process, thanks to the simplicity of the Google Forms platform. As explained in §2.2.2.3, online assistance in the native language of the respondent was given by a qualified TRUSTyFOOD member to anyone who asked for it. In those cases, it was necessary to schedule an online session with a conferencing tool (usually, MS Teams).

Overall, the execution phase lasted approximately two months: from 30/03/2023 to 01/06/2023. We collected the input from 37 use cases. Results were exported from the Google Forms platform into a Google Sheet file. From there, data was copied into a new spreadsheet, where raw user input was curated to make it more suitable for statistical analysis. For instance, close-ended questions that included the possibility of specifying a customized answer (see example in [Figure 29](#)) were *normalized*, putting all non-standard answers into one single “others” group.

2. Who are the active participants / stakeholders?
Please select one.

- Private partnership
- Public partnership
- Public-private partnership
- Single private company
- Single public agency
- Other: _____

Figure 29 - Survey: example of close-ended question with additional “customizable” answer

A2.2.4. Analysis of results

We start our analysis by looking at the *demographics* of the participants, as we are interested in the role of the respondents in the Blockchain initiative, and the type of organization.

Figure 30 shows the composition of the participants by role. This information is extremely important, as it hints at how the “assessment of the outcome” should be interpreted.

Figure 30 – Survey: role of participants

Key takeaways:

- 20% of respondents are “users”, so they are in the best position to assess the results of the initiative but lack the knowledge to answer technical questions.
- 70% of respondents are the “providers” of the solution: they are in the best position to answer all the technical questions, but it is safe to assume that their assessment can be biased.
- 10% of respondents, while being “users”, have answered all the technical questions. We can assume that these have provided the most comprehensive and trustworthy information.

The organization type is a close-ended question that allows multiple answers, as companies can often run more than one business unit. For example, a large enterprise - like a wholesale trader or a finance firm - may also have the “technology provider” profile if they develop their technologies internally.

Figure 31 - Survey: type of participating organizations

Key takeaways:

- More than 40% of respondents are technology providers, those who supported the development of the BCT solution at the food company. This is a significant data. This suggests the prevalence of the “technology push” approach as opposed to the more traditional “technology selection based on technical requirements” one.
- In few cases the consortium found itself faced with a company representative, usually represented by a person from the ICT department.
- With the above exception, there is no prevalence of specific business profiles.

Q – What is the type of organisation?

- *I'm the product owner, system analysis for Decapolis food guard development for the last years*
- *I was heavily involved in a marketplace for Colombia coffee farmers, where we aimed to find better alternatives for the current system that would provide better income and payment security for farmers. Our goal was to create a platform where farmers didn't have to rely on federations or government sectors for micro loans or funding.*
- *Internally, we are developing the technology in such a way that we can track the almonds produced, having information on the productivity of each sector, treatments used, and activities carried out with the aim of transmitting this information to the end consumer.*
- *Supported an agritech blockchain startup*
- *developer, system architect, solution architect, product development*
- *I have developed 100 projects using blockchain using public & private blockchains*
- *We developed our own blockchain.*
- *I'm cofounder of a blockchain protocol and I'm familiar with communicating new features to end users.*

- I do academic research on blockchain and smart contracts, I apply these concepts in the agrifood sector and in the energy sector
- We have integrated calls within the web application into two use cases
- Foodchains, solution designer
- This solution for the wine industry leverages a combination of blockchain technologies and IoT to enable product anti-counterfeiting, consumer loyalty programs, and data analytics for winemakers and their end consumers
- This solution is designed around the needs of certification companies operating in the wine sector (labs, etc.), with the aim to ensure the validity of certifications related to the quality and origin of products
- This solution enables winemaker to manage the full lifecycle of their product digital labels and provide advanced levels of transparency to consumers. It offers out-of-the-box compliance with the EU Regulation 2021/2117 related to wine product disclosures of ingredients, nutrition declaration, and allergens
- I am currently working in a startup that uses blockchain to provide services. I am part of the commercial team
- I worked on own sustainable blockchain solutions, on policy advisory for blockchain for financial inclusion in developing countries, on innovation projects in traditional finance using blockchain, and finally on this project using blockchain to build a on-chain marketplace to efficiently funnel liquidity from end users to projects and project developers, implementing climate projects (through carbon credits)
- I developed a deep passion for utilizing BCT potential in the incentivization of regenerating ecosystems and since half a year I found a way to express this in my company.
- We are the owner of KalaOos Platform and a technological provider
- as project manager I deal with the meeting between the agri-food chain and the managers of the design and development of the digital solution created
- I am in charge of the design of blockchain integrations, acting as support to both the CTO and the PM of reference for the organization of milestones. In addition, I am involved in on-chain research and analysis so as to individuate the most suitable solutions for our clients.

A2.2.4.1. Profile of the initiative

This section of the survey is for the classification of the use case according to our taxonomy.

Q1.1 In which country is the initiative based?

The question has the following explanatory note: *“If multiple organizations from different countries are involved, select the country where the lead organization has its headquarters. If no unique leader exists, select the country where the initiative has the largest footprint.”*

Figure 32 – Survey question: Q1.1 In which country is the initiative based?

Key takeaways:

- BCT is tested/applied in most of EU countries & outside
- By design (see §2.2.2.3), every survey session was conducted with the assistance of a *local* TRUSTyFOOD partner, who was able to communicate with the surveyed subject in their native language. This implies that, generally speaking, countries / geographical areas that are not represented in the TRUSTyFOOD consortium are also not represented in the survey results²⁵.
- Italy hosts more than one quarter of the use cases reported in our survey. This uneven distribution does not match the statistics that have been made publicly available by other information collectors. For instance: according to the EU Blockchain Observatory and Forum (BOF), Italy's "Blockchain weight", as measured by the number of Blockchain initiatives hosted, is less than half of Germany's; in our study Italy outweighs Germany by a factor of three. However, it is also true that BOF database is not limited to the agri-food sector and the non-agri-food cases cannot be filtered out. Spain is under-represented with respect to its agri-food turnover, as well as Portugal over-represented. Overall, it seems much more likely that the geographical distribution of our sample is the product of one key factor: the degree of capability of TRUSTyFOOD consortium members of engaging with national initiatives' stakeholders and convince them to participate to the survey.
- The bottom line is that the answers to this particular question are *not* indicative of the level of adoption of Blockchain technology in individual countries, not even within the limited scope of the agri-food sector. We believe, however, that this does not undermine the validity of the survey when it comes to the analysis of Blockchain solutions from the business and technical perspectives, as our sample contains enough *diversity* to account for the different levels of digitalization and access to finance across the geographical spectrum.

Q1.2 What is the geographical area that the initiative targets?

The question has the following explanatory note: *"Consider not only the de-facto situation but also the potential reach. Europe+ means that some extra-European countries are targeted, but the initiative is still primarily Europe-centric."*

Figure 33 - Survey question: Q1.2 What is the geographical area that the initiative targets?

²⁵ Ireland and Slovenia, both with one surveyed initiative, are the only two exceptions to this rule.

Key takeaways:

- Less than one quarter of the sampled initiatives have a national – or narrower – scope. Apparently, this confirms that BCT is perceived by most as an enabler of cross-border business and interoperability.
- The reason why the surveyed subjects make a distinction between within-Europe and beyond-Europe scopes (37% vs. 63%, respectively) may be rooted in the European regulatory framework.

Q1.3 What business sector does the initiative address?

Figure 34 - Survey question: Q1.3 What business sector does the initiative address?

Key takeaways:

- The “Public administration” option received zero votes.
- The scarce diversity of the results, together with the prevalence of the “Agrifood” sector, is *not* indicative of any trend in BCT adoption: rather, it reflects our criteria for the selection of use cases to be surveyed (see §0).
- That said, it does stand out that the “Logistics” and “Industry 4.0” (basically, the transformation, at industrial scale, of agriculture raw materials into food products) sectors are hardly interested in BCT.
- The presence of “Green economy” with nearly 17% of votes, as opposed to the 10% scored by “Finance and insurance”, is also a strong signal: it means that the *orthodoxy* of BCT as a tool for financial transactions is questioned – at least for agriculture-related applications – by a new generation of adopters who see it as a more generic *enabler of trust for information exchange*.

Q1.4 What is the governance model of the initiative?

Figure 35 - Survey question: Q1.4 What is the governance model of the initiative?

Key takeaways:

- As expected, the vast majority of initiatives originate from consortia.
- Less obviously, all initiatives have at least one private organization as their owner, co-owner, or co-sponsor: the “Public partnership” and “Single public agency” options received zero votes.

Q1.5 What kind of funding has the initiative received, or will receive?

Figure 36 - Survey question: Q1.5 What kind of funding has the initiative received, or will receive?

Key takeaways:

- Funding type statistics are consistent with the answers given to question Q1.4: initiatives that are entirely publicly funded are just one tenth of the total (by the way, all such cases being “Public-private partnerships”), while the majority is split right in the middle between 100% privately funded projects and those where private and public capital are both present (we presume in this case to be in a funded/co-funded project’s context).

Q1.5.1 Nature of the initiative

Figure 37 - Survey question: Q1.5.1 Nature of the initiative

From the graphic, the application of BCT turns out like a personal initiative (dictated by curiosity) or pushed by a technology provider for testing. In some cases the initiative was included in a funded project able to cover the financial exposure (e.g. EU, national).

Q1.6 Are citizens / consumers directly involved in the initiative (do they have access to data)?

Figure 38 - Survey question: Q1.6 Are citizens / consumers directly involved in the initiative (do they have access to data)?

Key takeaways:

- Business-to-Business (B2B) use cases are just 10% of the total: **Business-to-Consumer (B2C) ones are preponderant**. This is probably a symptom that BCT as an enabler of trust between cooperating organizations (e.g., partners of a supply chain) is not currently seen as a major factor, while the trust of the customer is a much more prized asset.

Q1.7 What is the level of maturity and scope of the initiative?

Figure 39 - Survey question: Q1.7 What is the level of maturity and scope of the initiative?

Key takeaways:

- Our sample is well-balanced between technically mature use cases and more experimental ones.

A2.2.4.2. Problems and needs addressed by the solution

In this section of the survey, we identify the business objectives and the high-level functional requirements of the BCT-based solution.

Q2.1 What are the needs that suggested the adoption of blockchain technology for your solution? (multiple answers allowed)

Figure 40 - Survey question: Q2.1 What are the needs that suggested the adoption of blockchain technology for your solution?

Key takeaways:

- Our sample is also well-balanced when it comes to the seven general needs that we have identified as the drivers for BCT adoption. Transparency is at the 1st position as adoptions' reason. "Business reputation" is the second most voted option, meaning that the *BCT label* attached to a business is still considered a factor for adoption. It is also worth noting, however, that the question allows multiple answers, and that all the respondents who selected the "Business reputation" option also mentioned one or more additional needs.

Q2.1.1 Aims of the blockchain project

Figure 41 - Survey question: Q2.1.1 Aims of the blockchain project

Key takeaways:

Not considering those applications which are not enough statistically representative, it is clear that – in order – the use cases had the following **main goals**:

- 1 – **transparency** - It is clear as the message towards the consumer assumes an important role for BCT's application at the eye of the end user;
- 2 – **traceability** (and its notarization);
- 3 – **control delivery procedures** (optimisation of processes).

Q2.1.2 What did you track with blockchain?

Figure 42 - Survey question: Q2.1.2. What did you track with blockchain?

Key takeaways:

Entering in more detail, **the blockchain intervenes on the food product flows**, but also in managing contracts (e.g.: certification, with external customers).

Q2.2 What is the expected impact of your solution on your business as a whole?

Figure 43 - Survey question: Q2.2 What is the expected impact of your solution on your business as a whole?

Key takeaways:

- Most of the respondents (80%) consider their BCT initiative as an important, or even very important contribution to their existing business. Also, a lower, but still significant number of respondents (17%), are creating an entirely new business based on their BCT solution. This answer, however, could have been interpreted by technology providers in relation to own business rather than to that of the company supported.
- A very small minority of respondents (actually, one single case in our sample) do not rely much on their BCT initiative, which is clearly considered a *nice to have* rather than a need.
- The option representing *cosmetic* or *testing the waters* initiatives (“Very low / negligible” impact on business) was not voted by any respondent. It may be argued that nobody would openly admit such scarce commitment, but there is no evidence that we can extract from our data.

Q2.3 What specific solution features are delivered through blockchain technology? (multiple answers allowed)

Figure 44 - Survey question: Q2.3 What specific solution features are delivered through blockchain technology?

Key takeaways:

- Use of *typical* features of BCT is quite evenly distributed: “Data sharing”, “Asset provenance and/or tracing”, “Notarization of documents” and “Workflow management” are – in this order – the most useful features of BCT according to our respondents. All of these happen to be data-driven processes that occur frequently in corporate organizations. Together with “Accounting”, which also belongs to this category, this group of data-oriented BCT features scores a whopping 68% of votes.
- “Token trading” and “Payments”, which are the most well-known and exploited uses of BCT, got a cumulative 17% of votes.
- “Identity management” and “Reputation management” have less scores, although they are both, from a purely technical perspective, a perfect use case for BCT.

A2.2.4.3. Characteristics of the blockchain-based system

This section of the survey is aimed at investigating the technical architecture of the BCT-based solutions that were deployed, taking into consideration just the few aspects that we see as the key characterising elements.

Q3.1 Which is the blockchain platform that your system is based on? (multiple answers allowed)

Figure 45 - Survey question: Q3.1 Which is the blockchain platform that your system is based on?

Key takeaways:

- The two leaders are, by far, the *public* Ethereum network and *private* Hyperledger Fabric systems. The former represents the classic *permissionless* approach to Blockchain, the latter is the flag bearer of the *permissioned* paradigm. The most obvious difference is that private networks are created and operated to serve ad-hoc purposes, while public ones are community platforms that are open to any user willing to pay on the go – with a cryptocurrency – for the computing and storage resources that they consume.
- If we group together public and private systems, the numbers are easier to read:
 - Public *permissionless* systems (Ethereum, Bitcoin, Polygon, Tezos): 54%. That said, our knowledge of the BCT scenario makes us believe that the “others” item is unlikely to include anything that is not, in some form or another, a public system; so, the total share of this category is 64%.
 - Private *permissioned* systems (Hyperledger Fabric, MultiChain, *ad-hoc* Ethereum): 29%. Note that Hyperledger Besu (7%) can be deployed either as a client of the public Ethereum network or as a node of a private network, so it doesn’t fit precisely in any

of the two categories. However, we know as a matter of fact that the main point of Besu is that it sports “enterprise” features – like permissioning and data confidentiality – in an environment that is friendly for Ethereum developers, so it makes total sense to enrol Besu in this category, bringing its share to 36%.

- Bitcoin does not support smart contracts. In other words, it is not capable of executing any business logic that is not related to its core mission: the trading of the Bitcoin token. With this in mind, it is quite interesting that Bitcoin still gets a 7% share in our survey. A possible explanation is that, as Bitcoin transactions can carry a tiny data payload, such payload is used to *seal* data that is maintained elsewhere. Note that this is pure speculation, as no hard evidence can be found in the survey’s results. Given Bitcoin’s minor share of the total, however, we are not overly concerned at finding out the true meaning of its score.

Q3.2 How can client software access the blockchain ledger?

Figure 46 - Survey question: Q3.2 How can client software access the blockchain ledger?

Key takeaways:

- Only one quarter of the surveyed solutions are designed so that client software communicates directly with the nodes of the Blockchain network of choice. The vast majority of solutions, on the contrary, are based on some sort of mediation – either an API server or a web site. **This is a key finding:** it should be clearly pointed out that the latter approach **requires the user to fully trust the provider of the mediation service**, regardless of such service being presented as just a “neutral” Blockchain gateway. In other words, there is no substantial difference between a web-mediated, BCT-based application and a more traditional cloud-based one. The reasons why many BCT-based solutions are designed with middleware in their way are three, not mutually exclusive:
 - direct access to the Blockchain ledger (through a Blockchain network node) is difficult to implement and even more difficult to manage;
 - data is not entirely stored on the Blockchain ledger – see also question Q3.4;
 - the business logic does not run entirely on the Blockchain (Smart Contracts) and/or on the user’s side (e.g., as mobile app).

Q3.3 Where does your system store data provided by its users?

Figure 47 - Survey question: Q3.4 Where does your system store data provided by its users?

Key takeaways:

- Only one quarter of the solutions use the Blockchain ledger as their only persistence layer.
- The rest adopt a hybrid approach, with massive data storage offloaded on some cheaper and more efficient system – like a Cloud-based facility.

Q3.4 How visible are data on the blockchain ledger?

Figure 48 - Survey question: Q3.3 How visible are data on the blockchain ledger?

Key takeaways:

- The majority of the respondents tell us that data stored on the Blockchain ledger by their solution is publicly readable, without requiring any form of user registration. Basically, this means that data that is stored *on-chain* (see Q3.3) is accessible to anonymous users. Note however that this does not imply that anonymous users can *write* any data on the ledger.

- One fifth of them, on the other hand, require their users to be registered in order to gain read access to the ledger. This also implies that some sort of access control is implemented on top of the Blockchain infrastructure – probably by means of some middleware (see Q3.2).
- Only 7% of cases use the Blockchain ledger to store confidential information. This means that the ledger itself is configured as a private Blockchain network.

A2.2.4.4. Assessment of the outcome

Here we ask the respondent about their own assessment of the results, from both the business and the technical perspectives. We also ask about the main problems encountered.

Q4.1 How do you judge the achievement your business objectives?

Figure 49 - Survey question: Q4.1 How do you judge the achievement your business objectives?

Key takeaways:

- Apparently, 83% of the respondents are happy with the outcome of their Blockchain initiative, with a significant portion (24%) declaring that it even surpassed what they expected.
- Only one tenth of the assessments were negative, with the results not being in line with the plan.
- Around 7% are undecided, as results are still preliminary.
- On the one side, this picture is consistent with the assessment of ROI (see Q4.2) and technical performance (see Q4.3); on the other, **we must consider the effect of positive bias**, as 75% of the survey respondents are those who provided the solution under assessment. If we do some very simple correlation analysis, we discover the following:
 - The negative assessment rate in the “technology providers” group is around 7%.
 - In the “customers” group, it raises to 25%.

In order to correct positive bias, **we then *scale down* the success rate of Blockchain initiatives by only considering the average assessment of the “customers” group: from 83% to 75%.**

Q4.2 How do you judge the return on investment (ROI)?

Figure 50 - Survey question: Q4.2 How do you judge the return on investment (ROI)?

Key takeaways:

- The main difference between the ROI and the achievement of business objectives (see Q4.1) assessments is that the former has a much larger portion of “too early to judge” answers (32%). This reflects the evolving status of many initiatives: while checking that requirements have been met can be done quickly, measuring ROI takes time.
- If we compare this pie chart with the one from Q4.1, what strikes the eye is that the “below expectations” slice is basically the same size in both. We might be tempted to conclude that whoever was unhappy with their business objectives was also disappointed by the ROI. But then we do our correlation exercise, and we discover something surprising: **two thirds of “below expectations” votes came from people who made a positive assessment of the achievement of business objectives.** This clearly means that **meeting requirements isn’t enough for a Blockchain-based solution, as its cost may easily outweigh its benefits.**

Q4.3 Were the costs involved acceptable?

Figure 51 - Survey question: Q4.3 Were the costs involved acceptable?

Key takeaways:

- In 8% of the cases, the respondents were not in the position to properly answer to this question. A minor part considered them unacceptable (too expensive), while most of them report costs as more or less acceptable (in line with plans).

Q4.4 What is the actual level of performance of your solution, as observed in real-world operations?

Figure 52 - Survey question: Q4.4 What is the actual level of performance of your solution, as observed in real-world operations?

Key takeaways:

- More than 85% of solutions have good operational performance.
- In around 11% of cases, the performance of the solution was deemed sub-par.
- Less than 4% of cases do not yet have a performance assessment. Comparing this value with the equivalents from Q4.1 and Q4.2 suggests that technical performance is much easier to assess than business-related indicators.
- Overall, these results are very similar to those of Q4.1, suggesting that business and technical performance have a strong correlation. As usual, we are not going to take this at face value and will do our own correlation analysis instead. It comes out that, at least if we limit ourselves to the (most interesting) “below expectations” group, there is no business-technical correlation at all: technically disappointing cases are *equally distributed* between “exceeds expectations”, “below expectations” and “too early to judge” on the business objectives achievement side. This tells us that **even a successful Blockchain initiative may be hindered by BCT’s structural limitations.**

Q4.5 What is the level of reliability of your solution, as observed in real-world operations?

Figure 53 - Survey question: Q4.5 What is the level of reliability of your solution, as observed in real-world operations?

Key takeaways:

- Long story short (if you did read the analysis of Q4.4): the assessment of operational reliability looks nearly identical to that of operational performance. And, after some correlation analysis, we can confirm that it actually is: the “below expectations” answers given here come from people who gave the same answer to Q4.4, while the difference in the total is because of systems that are deemed reliable in spite of their sub-par performance. As a conclusion, we may say that **Blockchain is confirmed as a robust and trustworthy technology.**

Q4.6 What were/are the main hindering factors in delivering your solution? (multiple answers allowed)

Figure 54 - Survey question: Q4.6 What were/are the main hindering factors in delivering your solution?

Key takeaways:

- “End user awareness” is, by far (24%), the top hindering factor in solution delivery. It means that **understanding what exactly BCT provides, and what its shortcomings are, is a key factor for adoption.**
- “Regulatory compliance” comes in the second place. This result is interesting, so we have to look behind the gross number (15%) in order to understand what type of regulation is perceived as a burden. Correlation is our friend, and we find that 91% of these respondents have to deal with cryptocurrencies and/or tokens – for some of them because it’s part of their core business, for others because the use of a cryptocurrency is required to operate their Blockchain platform of choice, which in these cases is always a public network. So, **regulation as a hindering factor is a thing because of the difficulty for some organizations to deal with crypto assets within the current legal framework.**
- “Data interoperability”, “Innovation risk” and “Technical skills” (of developers) are *ex-aequo* in the third place. This raises the suspect that there might be correlation between them, but after digging into raw data we found no evidence of this.
- “Data security / confidentiality” and “maturity of technologies” are the least voted issues.
- As a side note, the “No hindering factors” option was not selected by anyone, suggesting that no path to delivery was flawless.

Q4.7 What are the major issues for the regular operation of your solution? (multiple answers allowed)

Figure 55 - Survey question: Q4.7 What are the major issues for the regular operation of your solution?

Key takeaways:

- A significant share of respondents (39%) doesn't have anything to complain about their solution, once in operation.
- The two issues that emerge from the survey as the most likely to occur are "data management" and "complexity of systems", with a 18% and 15% share, respectively.
- All the other options (with the exception of "downtime" – see next point) collected a minor share of votes (below 10%). **The "immutability of ledger" and "inefficiency of ledger" issues – two well-known structural limitations of BCT – do not appear to raise big concerns.**
- The "downtime" option was not voted by anyone. We can thus conclude that **the robustness and resiliency of BCT is confirmed in day-to-day operations.**

A2.2.4.5. Assessment of non-technical questions

A series of questions were posed to understand more the dynamics behind the experience with blockchain.

Q5.1 Was the organization technologically prepared (e.g., sufficient connection, broadband)

Key takeaways:

In 65% of the cases the agri-food companies resulted sufficiently digitally prepared, but in about 35% of the cases some limits (not specified in their nature) occurred.

Figure 56 - Survey question: Q5.1 Was the organization technologically prepared?

Q5.2 Did the technology provider offer you adequate support?

Figure 57 - Survey question: Q5.2 Did the technology provider offer you adequate support?

Key takeaways:

- From an end user's perspective, the technical provided support received was according to the expectations, but in 20% of the cases it didn't turn out to be up to par.

Q5.3 What challenges did you face during the blockchain project?

Figure 58 - Survey question: Q5.3 What challenges did you face during blockchain project?

Key takeaways:

Prioritizing, respondents report as **main challenges**:

- Missing end users' technical skills and knowledge (from technology provider's perspective)
- Missing harmonized regulations
- Need of external support (from end users' perspective)
- Higher cost than expected.

Q5.4 What would you need in order to be able to effectively use a blockchain product?

Figure 59 - Survey question: Q5.4 What would you need to effectively use a blockchain product?

Key takeaways:

In line with the previous graph which underlined the 'challenges', as solutions to overcome such gaps the respondents ask for:

- Increased technical skills and knowledge
- External support (from the technical point of view)
- Financial support for the investment
- Clear regulations

Some respondents underline the need to have a legal obligation for applying BCT.

Q5.5 Is the project still ongoing?

Figure 60 - Survey question: Q5.5 Is the project still ongoing?

A series of questions followed:

QUESTION	YES	UNSURE
BCT helps to optimize company's internal processes	69,2%	30,8%
BCT helps to optimize the supply chain's functioning	72%	28%
BCT helps to address counterfeiting and other fraudulent activity	76,9%	23,1%
BCT ensures data integrity	80,8%	19,2%
BCT helps to improve collaboration amongst supply chain players	68%	32%

In general, respondents consider BCT a technology able to optimize internal processes, the supply chain's functioning and collaboration among players. However, it is significative that more than 32% have some **uncertainties** on the collaboration along the supply chain as well as in optimizing the internal processes.

A2.3. Final considerations on results

Here we highlight the most significant findings that emerge from the analysis of the survey results. In our analysis, we also look beyond the answers given to individual questions, by considering some interesting correlations between them.

1. **Even in the cases of BCT adoption, users appear far from a complete understanding and awareness on BCT.** Indeed, the prevalence of technology providers as main referents makes perceive a use of blockchain as an additional "given out" service.
2. While this survey was not able to reliably assess the per-country level of adoption of BCT (Q1.1), we are positive that most BCT-powered agri-food initiatives have a scope that reaches beyond Europe (Q1.2). We believe that **European lawmakers should pay attention to this matter of fact when designing future regulation.**

3. The European Public Administration (PA) footprint in the area under investigation is very light – except for the fact that the majority of BCT initiatives received public funds (Q1.5). Initiatives that directly target the PA sector are absent from our survey (Q1.3), but the partnership with some private company appears to be a precondition for the participation of PA agencies in BCT initiatives (Q1.4). **The opinion of PA stakeholders may shed some light on this matter.**
4. Where blockchains are deployed, citizens / consumers are nearly always involved. Purely B2B use cases are quite rare (Q1.6). **It would be interesting to know the opinion of consumers as the final users of these solution.**
5. It is not surprising that reputation – i.e., the public perception of a given company or organization – is still a factor that drives the adoption of BCT (Q2.1). What is more interesting is that business efficiency and revenue, together, represent less than 30% of the motivation, while “common good” reasons (i.e., societal, environmental and public health issues, plus business transparency) reach the 50% mark. We have to conclude that BCT adoption is, more often than not, driven by ambitions that are not directly related to profit. This, together with the finding reported at #2, raises the question if, within the scope of ICT, private companies are currently more instrumental than PA to the achievement of social objectives. **Social sciences may surely help in finding an answer to this question.**
6. On a more technical level, we found that decentralization of control in BCT-based solutions is probably not the top priority for users. On the one side, public / permissionless Blockchain networks seem to be more appealing than private / permissioned ones (Q3.1). This speaks in favour of decentralization, but on the other hand we can see that access to the Blockchain is mediated by some kind of centralized service in nearly 75% of cases (Q3.2). To make this point clear even to the less tech-wise readers: mediated access to the Blockchain defeats decentralization because the mediator retains full control over the information that flows through the mediating service. Most probably, this conflict is motivated by the need to maintain some of the information *off-chain* (i.e., not stored on the Blockchain): something that is done by the same percentage of use cases (Q3.3), most probably not by coincidence. Apparently, BCT is commonly used for its data immutability features rather than for anything else. The point is: is this feature, when evaluated together with the weak points, enough to justify the adoption of a radically new technology? **We would like to know more from technology providers that chose the “centralized access to a decentralized system” about their motivations.**
7. When it comes to the assessment of the deployed solutions, there is a clear prevalence of happy users (Q4.1 and Q4.3). On the topic of the return on investment (Q4.2), however, the picture is more blurred: a large portion of the respondents (32%) were not in the position to make an assessment, due to their initiative being still in an early phase. This is a shortcoming, because ROI is a critical issue for the adoption of new, challenging technologies. **It would be useful to have a follow up with people who didn't provide a definitive answer to the ROI question, so to have a more complete and up to date picture.**
8. There is a significant difference in the results from the polls on delivery (Q4.6) and operation (Q4.7), suggesting that the **BCT is indeed mature enough for production use, but is still difficult to master for software developers and system integrators.** That said, as this aspect is key for understanding the challenges faced by early adopters, we can try to dig a bit deeper.

If we can look at the answers given to questions Q4.6 (hindering factors for delivery) and Q4.7 (operational issues) only by those people who expressed some disappointment with respect to their initial expectations (Q4.1 to Q4.5), the *filtered* charts are shown here below (Figure and Figure). As we can see, there is no significant difference in the views on delivery, but there is indeed an obvious one for operation: **“complexity of systems” is by far the most challenging trait of BCT.**

Figure 61 - Disappointed users' perspective on Q4.6 What were/are the main hindering factors in delivering your solution?

Figure 62 - Disappointed users' perspective on Q4.7 What are the major issues for the regular operation of your solution?

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ANNEX 3

Digital maturity of the agri-food sector – preliminary findings

A3.1. Definition of ‘digital maturity’

In the recent academic literature, the term “**digital**” has been declined by the authors towards different types of more or less narrow concepts.

The concept of *digitization* refers to the conversion of information into digital formats by computers, in a bid to enhance efficiency [1] [2] [3]; it is an innovation that turns an analogical process/product into a digital one [4].

While digitisation is a purely technical process, *digitalisation* is a term that qualifies the change that digitisation generates in a broader social (or, better, sociotechnical) system [4]. Digitalization entails a deeper transformation that changes value creation activities or existing business processes, such as enhancing customer experiences, communication and distribution [5] [6].

Finally, *digital transformation* is the most pervasive phase that involves the emergence of entirely new business models considered new to the focal firm or industry [7] [8]. When digitalisation goes beyond the boundaries of local production processes and affects the way the economy and society are organized – the rules, distribution of power, knowledge and resource base – it is possible to talk about digital transformation [9].

When looking at the existing literature and what is written about digitalization it is clear that it is a broad topic and having different definitions, but it is still managed and funnelled down towards the same meaning, of how to restructure or change something analog into something digital [10].

Sometimes *digital transformation* and *digital maturity* are used interchangeably without considering differences [11].

Digital maturity can be seen as a systematic way for an organization to transform digitally [12]. Hence the term “digital maturity” specifically reflects the status of a company’s digital transformation [13].

The term “**maturity**” refers to a state of being complete, perfect or ready [14] and is the result of progress in the development of a system.

In some more extended interpretations, the term “digital maturity” goes beyond a merely technological interpretation simply reflecting the extent to which a company performs tasks and handles information flows by IT, but also reflects a managerial interpretation describing what a company has already achieved in terms of performing digital transformation efforts including changes in products, services, processes, skills, culture and abilities regarding the mastery of change processes [14]. In such case, digital maturity comprises a technological and a managerial aspect and therefore can be seen as a holistic concept.

Moreover, digital maturity is not a static concept because the digital landscape is continuously changing. As such, maturity should be assessed over time [15].

As in most of the research, such topic can be addressed from a qualitative or **quantitative** perspective. In the latter case, it is thought as the “measurement” (in a quantitative way) of the level of *digitization*, using modern indicators (Indexes, scores) and methodologies. There are different digital maturity models. Digital maturity models consist of dimensions and criteria which describe areas of action and measures in various levels which indicate the evolution path towards maturity [16]; some examples are provided below.

Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI) [17] is a composite index that summarizes indicators of European digital efficiency and competitiveness. It includes 30 relevant digital performance indicators measured from five areas (dimensions): connectivity, human capital, use of Internet services, integration of digital technologies and digital public services.

The *Rural Digital Index (RDI)* is part of the European Union Action Plan for a rural digital future, to measure the progress of the rural area geared towards closing the digital gap between rural and urban areas and to identify focus area for policy and investment. RDI is developed from the re-arrangement of the existing indicators in the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI). It is measured across 3 dimensions which include: connectivity, human capital, and use of internet and some indicators as described in Figure 59 that also share the key 5 dimensions measured with DESI (connectivity, human capital, use of internet, integration of digital technology and digital public services).

Figure 63: An illustration of the Rural digital index (RDI) 2022 dimensions and the indicators.
Source: European Commission

The *digital intensity score* is based on counting how many out of 12 technologies are used by each enterprise. The 2015 list of technologies includes: usage of internet by a majority of the workers; access to ICT specialist skills; fixed broadband speed >30 Mbps; mobile devices used by more than 20% of employed persons; has a website; has some sophisticated functions on the website; presence on social media; does e-sales for at least 1% of turnover; exploit the B2C opportunities of web sales; use an ERP software; use a CRM software; share electronically supply chain management information. Then they are divided into four clusters of digital intensity: Very Low (scores 0–3), Low (score 4–6), High (score 7–9) and Very High (score 10–12). [18]

Very interesting also the - *6Ps Digital Transformation Tool*, developed by Politecnico di Milano, which – even if has been developed thinking about manufacturing domain – can be translated to agri-food as well [79].

However, digital maturity studies can be also approached more from a **qualitative** point of view, providing the *status-quo* of the digital level of a specific sector.

In the recent academic literature, the term “**digital maturity**” has been/is mainly declined by the authors with focus ranging from the most basic technologies of internet access and use, e-commerce and business management systems, to advanced disruptive approaches aimed at efficiency (cloud computing), connectivity (IoT), disintermediation of trust (blockchain) and automation (big data and artificial intelligence) [7].

Summarising, from consulted bibliography three main distinctions emerge:

- 1) ‘Digital maturity’ intended as the presence of connectivity and broadband connection,
- 2) ‘Digital maturity as “use of Internet” and presence of a company’s website [19],
- 3) ‘Digital maturity’ intended as uptake of new digital technologies by actors across the agri-food systems (robotics, AI, sensors/remote Sensing, augmented and virtual reality, drones, BCT, IoT); DT developments have been referred to using different names, such as Agriculture 4.0, Smart Agriculture 4.0, Smart Farming 4.0, Smart Farming and Digital Agriculture, among others. If it includes the whole agri-food production chain from agricultural production to food consumption, the term used is agrifood 4.0 [20].

We included all of these declensions in our analysis.

A3.2. TRUSTyFOOD approach to the concept of digital maturity

Agri-food is a sector closely connected to the analog world, and this can represent a factor slowing down the process towards *digitization* and the related application of BCT.

The possibility to directly measure (in a quantitative way) the digital maturity level of the supply chain players in EU comes out the scope of a CSA, as it would require longer time and a different approach able to involve a large population.

Starting from the project’s goal, which is related to understanding the state-of-the-art of the BCT application in the agri-food sector as well as if the premises and the benefits for a wide future application exist, the scope of this first analysis of the “*digital maturity*” is the following:

The concept of Blockchain application is strongly related to the level of digitization of the agri-food supply chain players. A new technology can be disruptive and useful at specific scopes, but there are some basic pre-requisites to be guaranteed, in the absence of which a real development and digital transition would be slowed down (if not ineffective). For this reason, while findings on the current BCT-related use cases in the food system are identified, an investigation on the digital transition of the European food system is carried out.

We don’t need at this stage to approach the concept of ‘digital maturity’ from a social and managerial perspective; considering this and the fact that it is clearly demonstrated that research about digital transformation maturity as a holistic concept is scarce and needs more attention by research in the future [1], **we are mainly interested in applying the merely technological interpretation of the term simply reflecting the extent to which – to date – agrifood companies perform tasks and handle information flows by IT.**

The ‘digital maturity’ concept is thus approached from a **qualitative** point of view.

A3.3. The methodology

The performed study foresaw three main steps, as summarised in the picture below:

Figure 64 – Digital maturity assessment methodology

A3.3.1. Secondary research: literature review

Secondary research is a very common method for mapping and collecting data, often used as a way to start the deepening/research process and as a low-stakes way to determine if further primary research is needed, according to the gaps encountered in secondary research.

In the period March-May 2023, all the project's partners have been involved in the search of public documents (published peer-reviewed papers, meta-analyses, or government or private sector databases and datasets, deliverables, reports) in the field of "digital maturity" of the food system. Partners carried out mainly desk research, using terms such as "digital + maturity + food"; "digital + maturity + agriculture"; "digital + maturity + rural areas" and other key-words. A total of **52 papers/reports** have been collected, referred to the food sector in general, but also to rural areas and aquaculture/fisheries. Some documents were at country level, others at regional level, still others at EU level; Africa and Middle East were covered by NSCE partner.

A3.3.2. Primary Research

Primary research is "pinpointed", i.e. it is carried out around only a specific issue or problem and all the focus is directed to obtaining evidences. It was carried out to confirm (or not) evidences coming from desk research in relation to digital maturity concept.

Through the Survey for farmers and food supply chain players launched in spring 2023 in the context of WP3 activities (and mentioned also in D3.1), specific questions able to depict the respondents' digital maturity level have been added.

The number of collected feedbacks doesn't justify the possibility to use such Survey as a statistically-relevant source "per sé" / alone, however, the consortium used the **82 answers** to compare them with the evidences coming from the literature (thus reinforcing or refuting them).

A3.4. Limits and boundaries of the study

Independently from the effort posed in the search, the collection of existing papers may not be exhaustive, meaning that some documents that consider digital agriculture may be missing from our analysis. However, our review on this specific aspect does not intend to be exhaustive, but rather – as said – to preliminarily capture a European trend in the digital transition of the agri-food sector to date.

Another issue incurred in our search, evidenced both through literature and empirical data collection, is the fact that the terms “digitalisation” and “Digital maturity” can have different meanings for people. As an example, on papers which included the term “digital maturity” into the title we were expecting to find measurements of the digitization level of the sector, while on most of the cases such papers were focused on the challenges and opportunities which new digital technologies potentially can offer [21] [8], or to the internal and external drivers of digitalisation in agri-food companies [20]. So, definitions in literature can act as guidelines towards the right direction and give fundamental knowledge about the topic but in the end it comes to a subjective interpretation of the different individuals (and authors). This has clearly highlighted a lack of documents ‘really targeted’ on our specific purpose. For this reason, it was decided to proceed also with primary research, in support.

Finally, digital maturity is not a static concept because the digital landscape is continuously changing. As such, findings and percentages can not be considered definitive but constantly evolving.

A3.5. RESULTS

A3.5.1. From desk research

In line with [22], [23], [24], [25], we can confirm that there is a lack of papers related to the digital maturity of agriculture and digital transformation processes in this sector, or are focused on foreign countries. Indeed, most of the literature depicts the situation in US, New Zealand, Australia, China or UK [26 → 37], more than in EU. This is a shortcoming for our purposes and also a symptom that Europe and European companies are clearly lagging behind their US competitors in the race for a leading position in many digital markets. In fact, US digital ecosystems seem to have such a large lead that European companies simply cannot keep up yet.

However, from the assessment of the information collected through available sources, it emerges that the **digital maturity of farmers and agri-food companies in agriculture and rural areas in the EU is, on average, low.**

A3.5.1.1. Connectivity and broadband connection

Connectivity deserves a paragraph of its own. Indeed, some of the main barriers to increase digital maturity include the lack of access to telecommunications and internet infrastructure [38] [39], as well as slow internet connectivity [40]. According to literature review, the basic infrastructure, such as broadband or access to other high-speed internet connections, is partly missing. In particular, the European urban-rural **digital divide**²⁶ is real and significant.

Despite the efforts to narrow down differences in broadband coverage between urban and rural regions, progress is relatively slow [41]. As reported by SHERPA project [40], the connectivity gap is a case of market failure: in sparsely populated areas, the demand is insufficient to recoup the cost of the infrastructure investment. Mobile network operators (MNOs) focus on cities, in which required investment in infrastructure is usually lower and purchasing power of consumers is higher, thus creating a spontaneous gap and leaving a technological vacuum between urban and rural livelihoods. Digital divide might emerge from a chicken-egg problem: lack of infrastructure implies no demand for internet-based services, and lack of demand does not encourage internet providers to invest in infrastructure. Moreover, the problem is dynamic, as connectivity is subject to technological innovation, and to catch up an upgrade of infrastructure is needed.

²⁶ At a high level, the *digital divide* is the gap between those with Internet access and those without it (Internetsociety.org)

Europe's countryside is at the heart of our agricultural production, our deep-rooted traditions and rich natural resources. Yet rural areas all across Europe continue to lag behind when it comes to fast and quality broadband coverage. Currently, only 60% of EU rural households have high-speed internet access, compared to the EU's total average of 86%. Only 48% of rural residents have at least basic digital skills, compared to 62% of the urban population.

Rural broadband deployment varies significantly across the EU. At the end of 2017, only 47% of rural areas had fast broadband connectivity, which means that some rural communities are not able to reap the full benefits of the social and economic integration that digitalisation brings [42]. There are still many European rural households which have only limited or unreliable internet connectivity. Indeed, in June 2021 the Commission published the results of the Eurobarometer on rural areas. In the survey, 26% of Europeans said that digital infrastructure, such as broadband and internet access, is a key need that should be addressed in rural areas. The same has been confirmed by another survey, where over 50% of respondents stated that infrastructure is the most pressing need for rural areas.

If we consider that farming is seen as the sector contributing the most to rural areas, and that the farming and food sectors remain crucial for the rural economy (together providing nearly 40 million jobs in the EU) [43] we understand how much important such aspect is.

Network quality has improved overall, but there is substantial variation across countries. Average download speeds for leading performers are approaching 40 Mbps, but the vast majority (75 percent) of countries has not achieved speeds of even a quarter of this [44]. Europe is at the top of the table for Internet access, with 76 percent of its population able to go online, whereas only 21.8 percent of people in Africa have access to the Internet [45]. Compared with all other regions, Africa has worst Internet connection, both in terms of price and quality. 20 out of the 25 least connected countries are in Africa, and only 22 percent of households in this region have Internet access with only 24 percent of the individuals within these households actually using it [80]. Africa is the most difficult place to obtain Internet access and the disparities are huge. In relation to costs, in Egypt the average monthly broadband connection in 2018 was approximately US\$14, but in other African countries such as Burkina Faso, Namibia and Mauritania, monthly average costs were US\$202, US\$384 and US\$768, respectively, confirming that disparities are high in the continent.

According to FAO 2019 [46], smallholder farms and local agripreneurs without reliable access to highquality IT infrastructure are disadvantaged. Indeed, data-driven interventions are widely suggested to be a disruptive force in global food systems. However, mobile network coverage, handset ownership and affordable mobile service subscriptions are necessary prerequisites to achieve these solutions. Although the footprints of mobile networks and mobile phone ownership have increased in recent years, and the costs of mobile data have declined, substantial gaps in access remain.

Mehrabi, Z., et al., 2021 [47] reported a global baseline assessment of the state of mobile coverage and access to data services in farming. They used the coverage of mobile services as a measure of availability, which is the basic infrastructural backbone needed for scaling data-driven solutions.

Globally, only 37% and 24% of farms of <1 ha receive 3G and 4G services, respectively, whereas 80% and 74% of farms of >200 ha receive 3G and 4G services, respectively. Spatial heterogeneity in coverage is important. High-speed (that is, 3G and 4G) services are predominant in North America and Europe, whereas large coverage gaps exist in sub-Saharan Africa. It is well known that Internet access across countries in Asia, Latin America and Africa still lags behind that in other regions of the world such as North America and Europe, but Internet access also varies at the subnational level, and importantly, between farming and non-farming populations.

Rural areas remain at a disadvantaged position due to poor connectivity, a problem that needs to be addressed by governments to correct imbalances [48].

Broadband is a key technology that not only ensures connectivity, but also has a decisive impact on companies' ability to innovate and grow [49]. The absence of broadband leads small agri-food companies to take a passive approach to growth opportunities, particularly posing a serious barrier to diversification and internationalization. In their study on micro and small rural enterprises (Rural Public Access Wi-Fi Service (PAWS) project), Philip and Williams [50] analyze micro and small enterprises in the agriculture, concluding that, in order to ensure the future of micro and small rural enterprises, the quality of connectivity and digital skills are fundamental, and so the former is necessary to enable the latter.

While the deployment of fiber and high speed does not appear to be sufficient on its own to drive rural economic development, it may be a lever for development when certain conditions, related to the territorial economic context and design of digital policy, are met [51].

The digital divide between connected and disconnected farms and economically small and large farms must be addressed quickly to unleash the potential of new innovative solutions in the agricultural sector (<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/digitalisation-agriculture>).

A3.5.1.2. Use of Internet, ePlatform (including e-commerce) and management systems

Some studies declined the term “digital maturity” to the web presence (e.g. new domini) and level of maturity in e-commerce's use of farmers and food companies [54]. Most of these papers analyse situations at country level, rather than at EU/global level.

One of the most significant paper is referred to Spanish agri-food domain which represents 10.1% of the total EU agri-food sector, behind only France and Italy [55]. The sample is composed of companies in both agriculture and the agri-food industry. In such study, the mentioned digital solutions are used by between 70 and 100% of companies, due to their ease of access and use.

Moving to the use of digital platforms (such as those for e-commerce), from the latest data published by Istai (which refer to 2018) it emerges as only 7% of Italian companies with three or more active employees in the food industry use these tools [56].

ePlatforms diffusion has been studied also by Open DEI project [57]. Here the role of B2B Digital Platforms in the Digital Transformation of Agri-food has been investigated, as well as the role of Digital platforms in European Research and Innovation Landscape for Digital Transformation of industry. As reported, the adoption and use of the technology is still in its early stages.

A3.5.1.3. More disruptive DT: cloud computing, big data, IoT, blockchain, AI and robotics

The **agriculture 4.0** sector, i.e. the one that combines physical work in the field with digital innovations and connected machines, is increasingly entering the management of farms along the entire supply chain through various methods including the Internet of Things (IoT), the optimization of Big Data, Artificial Intelligence and robotics, in an attempt to make the various activities that start from production up to marketing more efficient.

The fields of applicability are many, ranging from the primary sector (agriculture) up to industrial applications (production processes), logistics and infomobility.

The most recent data processed by the **Internet of Things** Observatory of the Politecnico di Milano shows that IoT-based Smart Agriculture is constantly growing and has not shown signs of stopping even in coincidence with the recent global crisis of 2020.

Positive examples in the use of these techniques are the management of fields and farms, where through IoT sensors it is possible to constantly and continuously connect the various processes both for the management of the livestock and for the management of the fields.

On farms, these systems allow precise monitoring of the distribution of animal feed and milk production, in order to identify with precision and accuracy possible changes in terms of health, performance and reproductive status.

At the field level, many arable farms use IoT to manage fertilizers and irrigation systems through sensors, which provide a series of useful data on crops, allowing precise and immediate analysis of the situation, saving time and money in the long run. A very important chapter is safety in the storage phase, because grain silos and elevators can sometimes be dangerous places with conveyor belts that could get blocked, as well as risk catching fire, in these cases the use of IoT sensors to keep track of potential dangers, will be key in prevention through various ways of alerting.

Considering the growing interest of public opinion in safeguarding the quality of the agro-ecosystem, to maintain and strengthen a link between the peculiarities of a food and the place where it is produced, it is possible through innovative sensors present on the land under cultivation, to detect physical parameters of air, water and soil, in order to evaluate the quality of the production ecosystem and that of the products derived from it, for example in terms of lower content of contaminating agents. Through the use of these protocols, it will be possible to certify environmental quality on different scales: company or parcel, by following microclimate analysis procedures capable of identifying potential critical environmental conditions, so as to allow the geographical traceability of raw materials and products, monitoring and managing possible emergencies at the same time.

According to the results, for now investments in IoT always show a medium-term return; in cases where they prove counterproductive, this is mostly due to the cost of the sensors, poor interoperability of the company's internal systems, infrastructural problems of networks that are not yet so advanced as to allow a quick and functional connection between the parts (e.g. problems with connectivity, wireless connection speed and the like), if not a lack of skills on the part of the operators or a technological culture of farmers that is not yet widespread due to the more to a distrust in changing habits.

In order for the Internet of Things to become a value-added tool for farms, as it already is for other sectors, it will be necessary to lower the costs of sensors while trying at the same time to provide support to farmers in this technological leap.

For [58], a technological revolution is underway in agriculture which has continued in recent years despite the pandemic driven above all by the promised improvements in terms of efficiency and sustainability. Indeed, as an example, investments in Agriculture 4.0 technologies in Italy in the last two years have exploded, going from a turnover of 540 million euros in 2019 to 1.3 billion in 2020 and then reaching 1.6 billion euros at the end of 2021 with a further jump of 23% in 12 months. A global agritech turnover is estimated at around 15 billion dollars. Among the progress recorded by research is the increase of the areas cultivated with Agriculture 4.0 tools which in 2021 reached 6% of the total, doubling the previous year. 60% of Italian farmers use at least one Agriculture 4.0 solution, +4% compared to 2020, and over four out of ten use at least two, in particular management software and machine monitoring and control systems. There is a growing attention to data analysis and decision support systems (DSSs), confirmed by 26% of farms that plan to invest in this area for the near future.

If we move the attention towards Industry 4.0 [59], also the agrifood industry is implementing the I4.0 paradigm (defining it **Agrifood 4.0**). In such research, a systematic literature review was performed to provide a comprehensive picture of the current state-of-the-art about the adoption of I4.0 in the agrifood supply chain, considering 42 papers published between 2018 and 2022. In such study, it was confirmed that the agrofood industry lags behind other industries in the adoption of digital technologies.

Deepening the theme of the diffusion of innovation and digital technologies within the food industry, and therefore of the progress of the concept of Industry 4.0 in the sector, considering enabling digital transformation processes, i.e. the **cloud computing**, within the food industry it is employed by 15% of companies [55].

What emerges from consulted papers (but also from use cases analysis) is that the most used digital solutions in agri-food are innovations related to food traceability, then follow the use of QR codes, the development of mobile apps and the implementation of devices related to the **Internet of Things**.

Moving to **AI adoption**, the above-mentioned empirical analysis focused on the Spanish agri-food sector showed that the more complex digital tools, such as artificial intelligence, are only used by just over 55% of companies.

According to [60], which refers to the I-DESI to understand the relative maturity of different economies with respect to AI and blockchain technologies, several European countries perform strongly in the I-DESI, but there is large variance within Europe.

While the European Union overall exhibits readiness for deployment of AI and blockchain technologies, there are significant differences between the EU countries. The DESI 2022 results show that while most of the Member States are making progress in their digital transformation, the adoption by businesses of key digital technologies such as **artificial intelligence and big data** remains low.

Blockchain technology is currently implemented by only 22 % of companies and does not make a difference in the digitalisation of the sector.

A3.5.2. From Surveys

Figure 65

The 'digital maturity assessment of the agri-food sector' was completed through a survey targeting agriculture, aquaculture, and food industries (in a Farm-to-Fork vision) carried out in the period March-May 2023. The survey involved key project partners in this endeavor, i.e. AgriFood Croatia (DIH), Confagricoltura, Tecnoalimenti and NSCE. The primary objective was to gain insights into the adoption and potential of digital technologies within the agri-food system.

The survey yielded valuable feedback from various countries, with the majority of responses coming from Italy (51%), followed by Croatia (32%) and Egypt (8%). Additionally, we received feedback from farmers in France, Spain, the Netherlands, Hungary, and Turkey, even if in smaller numbers. While this distribution can be attributed to the partners' geography and personal networks, it is reasonable to assume a similar trend across Europe.

The survey has reached a diverse range of organizations within the agri-food sector. The respondents represent farms (i.e. growing of crops, breeding of livestock), food producers (e.g. from the field up to production of transformed products such as preserves, wine, olive oil, sweets, cheeses and cold cuts) and industrial processors. Farmers account for 29% of the organizations reached, while agricultural cooperatives comprise 10% of the total respondents. Then follow food producers and processors.

Figure 66

Respondents were well distributed ranging from young adults under 30 to older individuals over 60 years old.

Figure 67

Analyzing in detail the Farms, we noticed that 32% of farmers are +60, while 20 % are younger than 30 years old.

Figure 68

Comparing such data with Eurostat archived data, we can notice that the socio-demographic characteristics of our group is perfectly aligned with them. As an example, as reported in the 2016 Labour Force Survey (LFS), in the EU-28, 59.2 % of people working in agriculture were 40-64 years old, 11 % under 40 and 30.0 % were older than 64. Having a look at the graphic, 64 % is represented by respondents 40-64 years old. As confirmed also by other sources (Copa-cogeca), only a small percentage of all European farms are managed by farmers under the age of 30, while the majority of all farmers are over the **age**.

When considering the **gender**, there is a higher proportion of male respondents (70.2%) compared to female respondents. Analyzing in more detail the allocation of females, we noticed that in 20% of cases they belong to Associations (of agricultural cooperatives, producers or food industries), in 70% were owners or employees in farms and 4% in food industries.

However, moving the analysis to farms only, we noticed more or less an equal number of females/males (50%) among respondents. This is a little bit in contrast with **[61]**, which statistically report as women represent only 30 % of EU farm managers.

A significant proportion of respondents possess a high **level of education**, with 49% holding a graduate degree and an additional 31% having pursued post-education studies. Concentrating only on farms, food producers and cooperatives, only a 4% of respondents has primary education, while 16% finished the secondary school and 80% has a degree/PhD. This social-demographic picture emerging from our survey is very interesting and requires some more considerations. Comparing such data with archived data of 7-8 years ago, we can notice that something is evolving in this regard. Even if our target is not fully representative of the overall EU situation, the raising the level of education is significant, in particular where a correlation between propensity to investments/innovation and age/education level of farmers is stressed. In 2016, among people working in agriculture more than 50% had a low level of education in most of the Members States (Eurostat), while our survey depicts a situation where the level of education is much higher. Much more interesting to discover that 32% of them are +60. Other 32% is <30 or 30-39, showing as younger generations are studying agronomy as a profession to be re-discovered.

DEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION ON RESPONDENTS: FARMERS

Figure 69

When analyzing the agricultural sector, as expected, consulted farmers primarily reside in areas one-two hours far from urban areas (rural areas).

Figure 70

In terms of farming land size, a significant proportion can be categorized into different brackets. One-quarter of farmers possesses farming areas exceeding 100 hectares, while an equal quarter operates on a smaller scale, with land ranging between 10 and 50 hectares. 40% of farmers manage micro areas that are smaller than 10 hectares.

Official data report that the average size for livestock farms in Europe is below 50 hectares and that most of the EU's farms are small in nature, with two-thirds being less than 5 hectares (ha) in size. Accordingly, we can affirm that also in this case we have well represented in our survey the structure of the reality.

Figures 71-72

Considering the scale of operations, most farmers employ fewer than 10 individuals and generate a turnover below 100k EUR for 41% of the target and below 499k EUR for 36,4% of them. In fact, this applies to a majority of farmers when examining their business size and revenue.

Figure 73

When it comes to land ownership, a striking 81% of farmers outright own the land they cultivate, implying a significant degree of ownership and control over their farming operations. However, for 9% of farmers land ownership is partial, indicating shared ownership or leasing arrangements and the other 9% do not own the land they cultivate.

Figure 74

Arable farming is the primary occupation for the majority of farmers who participated to the survey, encompassing both annual crops (11) and permanent crops (6), alongside livestock (4).

Figure 75

A significant portion (45%) is engaged in organic production, while 20% follow traditional farming methods.

DEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION ON RESPONDENTS: AGRI-FOOD CHAIN ACTORS

Figure 76

Referring to the agri-food industry actors, the survey primarily targeted micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs), with 43% of the respondents having less than 10 employees. These companies typically represent the majority of businesses in the agri-food sector [according to Commission data, in 2017 there were 22 000 agri-cooperatives and 289 000 food and drink companies in Europe, 90 % of which SMEs and many of which were operating in rural areas **[61]**].

Figure 77

Additionally, a significant proportion (85%) of the surveyed enterprises reported a turnover lower than 10 million €, which is a common characteristic of small and medium-sized businesses in this industry. Some larger firms provide valuable insights due to their substantial turnover and significant number of employees, reflecting the diversity within the agri-food sector.

DIGITIZATION

Figure 78

Analysis of the emergence of digital technology reveals that connectivity tools such as internet, intranet, remote connections, and VPN are nearly ubiquitous, with approximately 75% of companies, both small and large, adopting them. A similar trend is observed for marketing tools such as websites, online advertisements, social networks, and e-commerce, which are utilized by approximately 57% of businesses. However, more advanced tools like Information Management Systems (e.g., ERP, CRM, SCM) are not that widely adopted, as only 32% of respondents report to utilize them.

Similarly, ICT security tools are not well spread, with a usage rate of 20%. These lower adoption rates may be influenced by the size of the companies. Interestingly, around 10% of respondents stated that they do not possess any of the listed digital tools, indicating that they have limited access to connectivity and digital technology; such respondents are all farmers, not located in an urban area (in line with literature above-mentioned barriers).

Figure 79

42,3 % (mixing farms, food producers and processors) have an ICT department or a dedicated digital support service. In order to harness the full potential of the digital landscape, individuals often turn to online tutorials and other self-learning options as their primary resources. Only 2% reported no actions in this regard.

Figure 80

When examining the inclination to invest in digital skills, it is evident that only a mere 15% of individuals expect substantial investments in the near future, and they are mainly represented by the food industry (more likely to such kind of investments). Meanwhile, a significant portion (39% are farmers/agriculture cooperatives which use papers and few digital documents, and 44% food producers) foresee null or small investments in this regard.

DATA

Figure 81

Figure 82

When it comes to managing internal and external data, there is still a significant portion of data being managed in paper form, accounting for approximately 10-15% of the total. They are mainly farms, family farms, and agricultural cooperatives (only in very few cases food processors). This reliance on physical documents can pose challenges in terms of accessibility, storage, and efficient data retrieval, but also - in terms of BCT application - on the reliability of data (which can be untrustable in origin). Approximately 33.7% of individuals primarily manage data in a digital format. However, a considerable portion of data management, around 50-57%, remains in a mixed format, combining both paper and digital methods.

Figure 83

The frequencies of data protection through backups range from monthly to weekly, with some organizations even implementing daily backups. More than one-quarter doesn't know, probably because such task is delegated to others within the company or it is even a procedure not applied at all (9,3%).

Figure 84

In the analysis of corporate digitization, it is revealed that a significant proportion of companies recognize the fundamental role of digitization in their business models, with 40% explicitly stating its inclusion. However, it is noteworthy that 21% of companies do not consider digitization as an integral part of their business model. Moreover, the study highlights that 34% of companies believe their existing workforce possesses the necessary digital skills to support their digitization efforts. This indicates a positive outlook on the current state of skillsets within these organizations. However, 44% still acknowledges future investment in enhancing the level of digitization. This emphasizes the recognition of the evolving digital landscape and the importance of continuous upskilling and development to remain competitive on the market.

Figure 85

Strengthening the significance of technology within the food sector, an overwhelming majority of individuals (97.8%) hold a favorable outlook on the utilization of new technologies.

Figure 86

Investments in digitization primarily target process enhancement and the transformation of the business model. Subsequently, they lead to improvements in company organization and service delivery. All of them are motivated to enhance the overall quality of the products and services provided by the company. In addition, it seeks to optimize production costs by streamlining processes and improve company's value.

Figure 87

Figure 88

The primary obstacles concerning investments in new technologies are the associated costs, time requirements, internal skill gaps, and concerns over potential impacts on productivity.

Figure 89

Collaboration and transparency are widely recognized as essential elements within the supply chain, with nearly 92% of stakeholders aware of their importance. However, it is interesting to note that only 58% express a specific interest in leveraging technological advancements that can render data immutable, ensuring authentication and combating counterfeiting. On the contrary, 36% of individuals show a lack of interest. An additional 5% of respondents are not even aware of their existence and remain disinterested.

Figure 90

By delving further into the subject and exploring the understanding of blockchain technology, a mere 23% of individuals assert familiarity with it (in line with literature data, mentioned in par. 5.1). Another 26% have encountered the term before but appear to possess only partial awareness. A significant 50% remain unaware of blockchain and exhibit no interest in it. Among those who have acquired knowledge or direct experience (32), the 46% possess only a rudimentary understanding obtained through independent research or limited exposure, whereas 53% have gained a better understanding through participation in specialized seminars or meetings. Only a single company asserts having practical experience in applying this technology.

Figure 91

The major challenge in business running is the cost of investment in equipment/tools (62%), followed by the cost of investment in technology (42%) and in services (approx. 37%).

A deficiency in highly skilled personnel (33.7%) ranks as the fourth most challenging factor, underscoring the pressing need for skilled individuals within the food sector. The complexity and technological advancements in modern agriculture require individuals with a diverse skill set, including knowledge in areas such as agronomy, crop science, animal husbandry, agricultural engineering, and food processing.

Adverse weather conditions resulting from climate change are the 5th emerged critical factor with consequences across the entire food supply chain. Rising temperatures, droughts, intense storms, and other extreme weather events are becoming more frequent and severe, disrupting agricultural production and impacting food availability and quality. These adverse conditions affect crop yields, leading to reduced harvests and lower overall productivity. Additionally, unpredictable weather patterns make it challenging for farmers to plan and manage their operations effectively.

At the 6th place, there are regulatory measures and barriers (30%). Food sector is indeed subject to various regulatory based on market and research evolvement.

Focus on STATUS-QUO ON TRACEABILITY, TRANSPARENCY AND DATA SHARING IN THE AGRI-FOOD DOMAIN

For better understanding the track-and-trace phase along the supply chain, the same food supply chain players not familiar with BCT (including farmers, cooperatives and food processors) have been interviewed by the consortium, posing them additional Questions related to data sharing and traceability procedures.

Figure 92

According to the interviewed players, 53% of them engage in tracking and tracing their value chain. This is not a high percentage, probably due to the fact that a significant portion of the respondents consists of micro and small enterprises, often representative of short chains. For such kind of businesses, implementing traceability measures which go beyond the law requirements may present financial challenges that need to be addressed.

Figure 93

Through the value chain, data is primarily tracked and traced to fulfill regulatory requirements, manage client information, and enhance supply chain transparency. In 39% of the cases, it is used for guaranteeing products' recalls capacity.

In terms of data flow:

Please provide a brief description of what data or information you have to receive and transmit in your day-to-day work

Figure 94

This question was posed to **understand more in detail the flow of data along the supply chain**. As we can see, the flow is bi-directional: a player receives data from the supplier and communicates data to the actor downstream (which can be a transporter, another supply chain actor, the retailer).

Figure 95

Agri-food players receive data from suppliers mainly linked to product origin, transportation and regulatory records, ingredients list and times of production.

Figure 96

This question was posed to understand the “TRUST” of the businesses on data sharing along the supply chain. As we can see, it is significative to note that **66,6% of respondents have some doubts or don't have trust at all on data they receive.**

Are there particular stages within the value chain where you perceive a risk of fraudulent data manipulation?

In 37,5% of the answers, no risks were perceived (in particular along the short supply chains). 9% were uncertainty but possibilists. The remaining majority acknowledge the existence of sensitive stages where such manipulation could occur. These critical stages include data related to purchased raw materials, treatments in the field (e.g., fertilizers, pesticides), and logistics. Also, paper documentation is considered suitable for theft or manipulation. Another point highlighted was the data security (handle personal data, or legal data). Some others interpreted differently the question, and posed attention to the possibility to lose data (no proper data storing or saving).

In terms of **data sharing**:

Figure 97

Only 16% declares that other players along the supply chain have visibility into this data, for the rest data remain reserved.

Figure 98

As a concept, collaboration along the supply chain seems to be an important asset for most of the farmers/supply chain players.

Figure 99

Effective communication with consumers is overwhelmingly crucial and plays a significant role for nearly 90% of individuals.

A3.6. CONCLUSIONS

For analyzing the Digital Maturity of the agri-food sector, first the consortium clarified the related terms. Then, the consortium carried out secondary and primary research. For the latter, the survey involved a group of players along the supply chain who, even if reduced in number, well represent the agri-food system in all its facets and dynamics.

While thinking about BCT application in the agri-food chain, there is a plethora of potential ‘dark sides’ / risks that should be adequately addressed. They include the creation or persistence of digital divides and inequality of opportunities.

The internet is crucial for conducting transactions on the blockchain. But, dependence on the internet can be a critical concern, in particular if infrastructural deficit does not allow Internet for all. Numerous studies have been carried out in the last six-seven years and in most of them, the concept of “digital divide” emerges strongly, mainly related to rural areas. If we consider that farming is seen as the sector contributing the most to rural areas, this is a big issue to be faced.

A digital divide exists that reflects various digital differences among and within countries. This divide is defined by three primary factors: the availability of telecommunications infrastructure (connectivity); education and skills; and financial resources –in order to close the digital divide.

The survey carried out shows that connectivity is a problem but in less cases than expected. In terms of education and ICT skills, it emerges that more than 40% of companies have an ICT department but a consideration which has to be done is that not always an individual with awareness and knowledge on ICT knows and understand about BCT.

Other emerging evidences coming from our preliminary analysis, is that agri-food companies in general within the EU (28) have a very low level of digital intensity. Overall, we detected a quite slow uptake of new digital technologies by actors across the agri-food systems and the lack of a global implementation of such digital solutions in the entire agri-food sector. As confirmed by our survey, there is interest for new technologies (97,8% has a positive perception of them) but the level of

concrete adoption is low. 21,2% of respondents claim not to consider digitization as an integral part of their business model. The primary obstacles concerning investments in new technologies are the associated costs, time requirements, internal skill gaps, and concerns over potential impacts on productivity.

This is in line with literature. Indeed, some authors correlate this delay with the typical profile of companies in the sector: predominantly small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs) with limited budgets and little access to financial resources [77] [78] [79]. Moreover, they show low levels of generational renewal and underdeveloped information and communications technology skills [80]; also in our survey, we noticed that 32% of respondents are +60. Another major threat relates to the traditional nature of the agri-food domain and thus reluctant to move towards open innovation and share data with other players in the value chain (Open DEI, Position Paper) [57].

The lack of digital skills and the limited availability of reliable cost/benefit analyses of the new technologies are challenges to increased investments in such digital applications. Indeed, it is not a case that - as confirmed by our analysis in WP2 activities - in many cases, R&I are still required to approach digitization and disruptive digital technologies (many solutions are experimented/piloted along EU funded projects, e.g., BLOCKFIL, A2C, IoF2020, DEMETER, ATLAS, GRACED, HARTU, TITAN). The reasons reside in the nature of funded projects, which (i) allow end-users to be accompanied, along the process of innovation and digital transition, by technical-scientific people, (ii) represent a testbed for such solutions (reducing the risk and increasing the trust on them) and (iii) help sustain the financial effort.

Agriculture 4.0 is still limited to a few innovative firms [76], indicating that the sector could still be in a starting phase inside the digital transformation process. Currently, apart from some growing investments in IoT, there is a lack of awareness about which are the most frequently adopted technologies, their limitations, and the conception of the agents involved, as well as those of society, all of which could strongly influence this process. More investigations are needed.

Additionally, much of the potential value of the data that is already collected remains untapped because it exists in silos unavailable to those who might use it [75].

The low digital maturity of agri-food market, in particular SMEs operating in agri-food, hinders their shift towards digital platforms since they still lack some of the basic capabilities in terms of digital transformation. All of these weaknesses need to be bridged, to build a plan for new technologies (blockchain included) wide adoption in line with real conditions of rural farms & food producers, both in EU and in less developed countries (e.g. Egypt and other Middle East countries).

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ANNEX 4

List of use cases mapped and collected

Table 5 EU based Use Cases

Industry/Project	Description	Country
AB InBev	(The parent company of Heineken) trialing an internal supply chain tracking solution deployed by SettleMint.	Netherlands
Acorn	a Rabobank carbon credit scheme oriented towards smallholder farmers. Carbon removal units (CRUs) are traceable and tradeable through blockchain.	Netherlands
AgriTrack	Our values revolve around simplicity of use, transparency of information and efficiency, to enable a widely available Agri ecosystem.	Greece
Agro2Circular	Agro2Circular is focused on the implementation of the first territorial systemic solution for the upcycling of the most relevant residues in the agrifood sector (fruits & vegetables and plastic multilayers) into high added-value products, powered by a digital tool and constructed upon a systemic approach with high replicable and scalable potential.	Italy; Spain; Austria; NL; Germany; Lithuania;
Albert Heijn	Albert Heijn together with supplier Refresco has used blockchain technology to provide insight into the production chain of its own brand of non-perishable orange juice. Via a QR code on the packaging, consumers can see which route the bottle of orange juice takes until it is on the shelf. The primary goal for Albert Heijn was more transparency, "Blockchain turned out to be the best tool for this because this technology makes it possible for each partner in the international chain to add pieces of information to the product flow in a transparent and reliable manner." According to the supermarket chain, the challenge was not so much the blockchain technology itself, but providing insight into which data is available, its relevance to the customer and to what extent the partners are willing to share it. "The complexity of the chain and its international character also made the realization of the blockchain a challenge. Consumers use a mobile app to scan a QR code on the juice bottle to discover the journey from farm to supermarket. In this example, the LDC juice originates from Brazilian orange groves.	Netherlands
Alce Nero	Blockchain experiment on the Organic Extra Virgin Olive Oil DOP Terra di Bari Bitonto. Collaboration with the Hi-Tech company EX Lab BlockChain Solutions. QR-code framing. Blockchain application to geolocate all fields of the producers and collect, in a certified way, all data concerning manufacturing from the field to the package. Collaboration with Finoliva and Biodistretto delle Lame	Italy
Almaviva SpA	Blockchain solution that enables the following use cases: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Traceability: Non-replicable smart tags, blockchain and distributed documentation to make the distribution chain of goods reliable and certified. - Legal Automation: The ability to extend a legal contract with an electronic component that adds dynamisms and automation by reacting to pre-arranged events and agreements in an automatic and non-repudiable way. - Property Certification: Decentralized management of the ownership of an asset, without intermediaries and with the guarantee of the certified history of the various changes of ownership. - Notarization - the decentralized solution for notarizing digital assets or digital twins of real assets. - Privacy and GDPR - Manage consent and user data processing on blockchain in a decentralized way and compliant with the European GDPR regulation. - Smart Insurance - Create decentralized insurance solutions with direct and automatic compensation when pre-established and certified conditions occur thanks to smart contracts. - Ticketing - secure, non-replicable tickets and coupons verifiable by purchasers and IoT systems to guarantee controlled access based on capacity, automated and certified calculation of copyright fees or interoperability on cash back platforms. - Telemedicine: services: Generating value for the future of Healthcare means the ability to prevent and respond to the health needs of an aging population. Blockchain application for public and private companies. Some Use cases of Almaviva BCT development regards: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ROUGE: the hi-tech mark for Sicily Red Oranges IGP - enology; for wine defence - Public Privacy 	Italy
Amadori	SAP Ariba to centralize the core of suppliers selection and to improve the procure to pay (management and compliance processes from goods and services supply to	Italy

	invoices receipt and suppliers payment). A new generation of back-office purchase born.	
AMPnet	From asset management, emissions trading or real-estate investments to brand loyalty and decentralized finance – digital assets are transforming industries around the world. Get a head start on competition by rapidly deploying your digital asset solution with ampnet.	Croatia
Ängöl brewery	BCT on beer to verify and track each production process. The production is by Ängöl brewery and the project Helt Spårat has been possible through the traceability integrator Foodchain by Blockchain and the trading platform Skira. The purpose is to be able to completely document a consumer product using blockchain technology through all processes, from the time the first malt grain is sown until the beer is bottled.	Sweden
Ania	Sandbox project (in collaboration with IBM and Reply). Experiment the resolving disputes between the insurance and the policyholder in the blockchain environment. GOAL: faster dispute resolution	Italy
AquaLedger	AquaLedger aims to harness earth observation (EO) and advanced analytical techniques in order to collect valuable information about the marine environment and activities in relation to fisheries and aquaculture management while enabling its integration with a Blockchain/Distributed Ledger Technology based platform towards improved and sustainable supply chain management in the fisheries and aquaculture sector.	Greece
Arla Foods	European dairy business Arla Foods claims to be the first in its field to use blockchain technology to provide information on its supply chain. Arla has launched a pilot project – Arla Milkchain – which allows customers to track the origin and production of the company's products from farm to dairy. The first item to launch on the platform is Single Estate Organic Milk. Single Estate Organic Milk is produced using raw materials from the Tikka organic farm in Kurikka, and is processed in the Hämeenlinna Cooperative Dairy.	Finland
ARXUM	ARXUM® provides an advanced, industrial blockchain infrastructure and a versatile middleware which reduces complexity to interconnect existing IT Systems with blockchain based business logic. Transparency and food waste play an important role in the food & beverage industry. To meet these challenges, the ERP system as the central nervous system needs a cross-company connection with suppliers, manufacturers and the retail trade.	Germany
Atecluster The food Initiative	CERTH: To become the growth catalyst and reference point of the Agri-food sector in Greece and abroad, utilizing the unique Greek agricultural products and the know-how, innovation and productive capacity of its members, to promote prosperity, healthy Mediterranean diet and sustainable development INOV: The aim of the blockchain research project would be the development of a fully digitized traceability and quality assurance system for new or existing products of the companies involved, based on the Blockchain technology. The system will collect all information that accompanies the product, in order to better inform consumers and at the same time protect and enhance the reputation of the company's products in the National and/ or international markets.	Greece
Authentico	Authentico applies BCT on food supply chain to protect the Made in Italy, especially during export and to certify the safety procedures from processing to delivery.	Italy
Axéreal	Purchaser of grains from 13.000 farmers across Europe	France
Axfoundation	BCT in the food industry. Axfoundation is convinced that broad collaboration and increased transparency are key to solving the complex issues and challenges we face in the food industry. During 2017 to 2019 did Axfoundation, along with a dozen actors from the food industry, explore blockchain's potential in the food chain. Our goal was to learn together and to slowly develop practical ways to test the potential of blockchain.	Sweden
Banca Mediolanum	Certifying the immutability of the non-financial declaration (document that collects information about i.e. environmental and social policies) with hash publication (the encrypted key) on the institutional bank website.	Italy
Barilla	In collaboration with IBM, it has developed a pilot project that uses blockchain to guarantee products and raw materials origin and quality. From the field to the table. The first application is for fresh basil.	Italy
BASF	BCT pilot platform to trace durable palm oil supply	France

BBTWINS	Bio-Based Digital Twins (BBTWINS) aims to overcome the challenges faced by the EU agri-food sector's transition to become more sustainable by developing a digital platform for the optimisation of agri-food value chain processes and the supply of quality biomass for processing. BBTWINS' novelty is, on the one hand, that for the first time different technologies -sensors, computer simulations of food processes, artificial intelligence and blockchain- are put together into one digital twin. And on the other hand, the breakthrough is to develop these digital twins for the pork and peach industry, covering all inputs such as materials, energy, water, etc., all processes and transformations, and all outputs including products, waste, and side streams.	Portugal; Spain; Greece
betterEco	betterECO is a B2B service company that strategically sources organic agricultural commodities around the world to meet the quality requirements of companies in all sectors, especially the food, cosmetics and pharmaceutical industries.	Germany
Big Eye Smart Fishing	Fish tracking from sea to plate	Portugal
BIMChain (Building Information Modeling)	Created by Italferr (FS Italian Group) and co-design with Own Your Business in the Open Italy Program. The blockchain is used to enhance information management processes in terms of reliability, security and transparency of the information exchanged among the various stakeholders	Italy
Bjärefågel	BCT to trace chicken production	Sweden
Block.IS	Catalyzing Blockchain Innovation. Block.IS is an acceleration programme that aims to build an open and collaborative cross-border innovation ecosystem that fosters the use of blockchain technology in three vital sectors for the EU coeconomy: Agrifood, Logistics and Finance. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 824509.	Spain; Ireland; Serbia; Luxemburg; Germany; Belgium; Estonia; Portugal; NL; Greece
BlockFIL	Italian and EU funded project, closed in 2022, which developed a sperimental and innovative integrated technologies framework (IoT sensors, distributed ledger, AI) based on blockchain approach to be applied in agrifood supply chain	Italy
BuondiOli	Thanks to the collaboration with the startup xFarm, the company tracks the Extra Virgin Olive Oil via the Blockchain technology. The company has already produced the first lot of 1.000 bottles tracked and got relevant advantages both in process optimization and in process costs and time reduction. Collaboration with XFarm (sensors and software provider) and DNV-GL (for data certification)	Italy
Campus Peroni	The projects partners are: Birra Peroni, Saplo, Crea, UniTeramo, UniPerugia, UniFi, UniPd, UniSa, UniTuscia. Collaborating with the startup pOsti, the project aims to get value and to protect regional italian food products by traceability of the supply chain by Blockchain technology and the e-certification of "Nastro Azzurro Mais Nostrano-Qualità Certificata". Collaboration with pOsti start up and EY (technology provider)	Italy
Cantina la Pergola	Winery and Distillery society, use cases of the Blockchain implemented is the one from AgrichalNitalia (an italian IoT startup specialized in the Agrifood and Chemical fields). The blockchain trace the product from the grapes to the GDO	Italy
Cantina Volpone	Case Hystory of the WINE BlockChain thanks to the partnership with Ernst&Young (EY) EZ Lab on the Falanghina production line. Through a smart label on the bottle (QR-code framing) is possible to acces to information about value chain traceability, quality certifications and origins of the chain.	Italy
CarbonStack	We accelerate the transformation to CO2 neutrality by offsetting emissions that are difficult to avoid with local offset projects. We evaluate the CO2 absorption of forests with satellite images and document the projects on a public blockchain.	Germany
Cargoledger	logistics and supply chain management via blockchain, digitizing many documents needed for managing cross-border supply chains.	Netherlands
Carrefour	Project born in 2018 with the goal to apply by 2022 the Blockchain technology on all products branded "Carrefour BIO" with the goal of more transparency on products origins and process procedures.	France
Carrefour Italia	The first italian GDO to use blockchain technology for treacibility purposes. Info are available also thourgh app on the smartphones.	Italy
Casa Girelli	Collaborating with EzLab and EY, the winery implemented the AgriOpenData Blockchain to certify the organic wine process of the "Nero D'Avola LaMura BIO".	Italy
Caseificio Montano	Use cases of the Blockchain implemented is the one from AgrichalNitalia (an italian IoT startup specialized in the Agrifood and Chemical fields)	Italy

Certified Origins Italia	The export-company of Extra Virgin Olive Oil applies the Oracle Blockchain Platform to monitor and trace the EVOO Bellucci from the Italian bottling establishment up to USA	Italy
Chain4Travel	Chain4Travel is the facilitator of the Camino consortium blockchain, a new disruptive approach to trade touristic products B2B and B2C with over 120 supporters from the travel industry.	Germany
ChainFlip	Chainflip Labs GmbH is a Berlin based Software Engineering Firm with a local and global presence. We primarily develop distributed networking technology using Rust and other frameworks. Our clients, products and partners are far reaching in scope and our multidisciplinary team of software engineers and product managers engineer cutting edge solutions to new problems.	Germany; Ireland
CIED BV	We are an agri-tech company headquartered in the Netherlands. RightOrigins, our ESG-specialized traceability, and supply chain management suite help organizations ensure transparency, trust & fair ownership in agri-food supply chains & showcase product stories from farm to fork. There are no definitions on technologies used found. Only that is on traceability	Netherlands
CircularTree	Synchronizing supply chain compliance management through Blockchain technology. Making it simpler and safer for organizations to tackle their responsibilities along the supply chain. With their product CarbonBlock you can easily exchange Product Carbon Footprints with your suppliers and customers. Identify the product-based greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from your own manufacturing and request upstream data from your supply chain, increasing the primary data share of your Product Carbon Footprint.	Germany
cirplus	cirplus is the global marketplace for recycled plastics and plastic waste feedstock. Our team and technical partners have extensive experience in the manufacturing & recycling of thermoplastics. We know from first-hand what it takes to build digital platforms and bring them to scale. We are 100% independent and guard strict neutrality in our work. We are based in Germany, but our ambitions are truly global. We are on a mission to make buying and selling recycled plastics easier and more efficient than ever before. We accomplish this goal with our next generation B2B-marketplace, connecting the plastic & recycling industries. Transparency, global reach, and standard-setting are just a few of the features that cirplus provides. Our vision is to make plastics 100% circular. We are only satisfied the moment no more plastics enter the environment, keeping this valuable material in the loop. To this end, we serve as the digital catalyst of the circular economy. With our work, we will lower the transaction costs for recycled plastics and thus massively reduce the environmental footprint of plastics overall. Let's make plastic waste history!	Germany
Clàrù	BCT start-up to demonstrate the provenance of Irish food products "from farm to fork" and make it easily accessible to consumers.	Ireland
Climate Farmers	carbon credit+ program operates in partnership with US-based Regen Network's Regen Ledger, a web3 native carbon credit. Climate farmers provides additional training and agroecological support services to farmers, and are working to include biodiversity, water retention, and other ecosystem services into their credit.	Germany
Colli del Garda	Pilot experiment of the Blockchain application thanks to the support of IBM Group on the cured meat production chain. The QR-code on products' label let the consumer know information from the animal genetic up the fork.	Italy
ComeTogether	ComeTogether's NFT ticketing solution launched in October 2019 and has provided ticketing to more than 80 live events despite the pandemic and lockdowns. During 2021 ComeTogether repositioned its offering as a broader provider of NFTs with utility, of which NFT ticketing is one category, but there are other use cases as well, such as NFT fan club memberships and any other collectible that has utility.	Greece
Compellio	The Compellio platform is an enterprise software service powered by blockchain technology that manages the lifecycle of digital representations associated with enterprise assets.	Luxembourg; Greece; Italy; Belgium
Comune di Bari	In collaboration with Sia, it has launched a project based on blockchain technology that aims to digitize the process management of surty policies, dematerializing the process of issuing guarantees by banks, financial intermediaries, insurance companies, certifying them unambiguously and irrevocably.	Italy
Conad Centro Nord	A project that connects blockchain and customer experience to let be known Conad Chain. Thanks to the collaboration with the University of Florence, it has created an avatar that talks to customers Conad-branded products history.	Italy

Connecting Food	Connecting Food is a technology company based in Paris serving agribusiness clients and consumers worldwide.	France; Italy
Consorzio Arance Rosse di Sicilia	History record of each production lot of red oranges-IGP (production field, harvest day, storage rules and distributions). GOAL: prevent food fraud and let the consumer be aware of the origine an genuinity of agrumes.	Italy
Consorzio del Parmigiano Reggiano	Blockchain technology to trace Parmigiano Reggiano with the collaboration of the Dutch Kaasmerk Matec and the US p-Chip Corporation. An additional p-Chip will play as smart label; additional to the Casein Plaque. The goal is to grant a safer and more protected product.	Italy
Consorzio Grana Padano	Blockchain application into Grana Padano Consortium, especially in Desenzano Del Garda (BS) district, to protect the PDO cheese from fraud and counterfeiting but also to guarantee transparency and reliability of the production process. Project began in 2019, and in 2022 the Caseificio Torre Pallvicina (BS) is the first one to grant the supply chain traceability among its 21 milk producers compnaies through the Blockchain	Italy
Coop Italia	CoopChain: treacibility of organic eggs "Coop-branded" using the Blockchain platform "Connecting Food" that uses IBM Blockchain Permissioned platform (Hyperledger Fabric) GOAL: in-real treacibility and digital quality control on lot freshness and organic quality (via digital audit)	Italy
Coorest	web3 native carbon standard leveraging remote sensing data via Floodlight which is oracled on-chain via chainlink. Primary focus is agriculture and (agro)forestry projects.	Netherlands
Crea	Microsoft blockchain solution to develop a treacibility app for wood: from the tree to the consumer	Italy
Croatia Post	Croatian Post in cooperation with the Croatian blockchain community gathered around the Association for Blockchain and Cryptocurrencies presents the Croatian Kriptomarka. An incredible combination of philately and modern technology comes to us on the eve of the twelfth year since the appearance of blockchain technology through its first emanation - the cryptocurrency Bitcoin. The Croatian crypto stamp is envisioned as the perfect combination of the analogue and the digital. After purchase of the crypto stamp, the part used for paying the postage may be detached, while the digital part remains to be used in the blockchain. Stamps are represented in the blockchain as the so-called unique or non-fungible tokens (NFT) under standard ERC721. Such non-fungible tokens have collectible value, just like classic stamps, which means that philately is faithfully transposed into the digital world. Since such tokens are located on the Ethereum platform, they have the potential to live forever, which adds another dimension to philately – protection from deterioration caused by passage of time. Whether digital albums will replace philately albums remains to be seen, but it is already clear that the passion that people have for collecting rare items did not disappear with the emergence of digital technologies.	Croatia
Danone	Blockchain technology application on infant formula milk. The main goal are trasparency on production of infant milk and ingredients traceability. The project will regard the Aptamil brand sell in France, Germany, Austria and New Zeland	France
Daruma Sushi	Collaborating with Genuino (startup that developed a decentralized certification protocol based on blockchain tehcnology, IoT and AI), the japanese catering company Daruma, developped a decentralized certification protocol via Blockchain to certify the quality and autenticity of the production chain on the japan cuisine. By doing this, the control during the cold-chain have been mazimized granting the temperature respect of the raw products up to the GDO	Italy
DataFund	Datafund protocol guards personal data, provides safe storage and enables ethical data exchange. Individuals create their own datafund to reclaim, own and manage their data.	Slovenia
Datarella	A web3 company builder which provides a technology stack of Blockchains, Self-Sovereign Identities, Decentralised Data Marketplaces, Autonomous Economic Agents, Machine Learning & AI. Datarella built a blockchain-based payment system for the world food programm for syrian regugees.	Germany
Decentralized smart system for tracing the origin and quality of goods	The aim of the project is to develop and implement an integrated workflow management system that allows for transparency of technological production processes and provides up-to-date information on the product cultivation process (resources used and product processing). The priorities that will be followed in the	Bulgaria

	implementation of the project are to use blockchain technology to test how transparency in the ecosystem of the food / food supply chains leads to increased trust among actors in the supply chain, including the use of blockchain technology, and targeting demographic groups that are willing to pay a higher price with guaranteed origin and quality of the food offered.	
Devoleum	Devoleum is an open-source project that allows to trace companies steps on Blockchain of Ethereum and Algorand. Devoleum is a web app that transforms the linked open data of physical or digital supply chains into meaningful stories, making each step immutable on blockchain or other distributed systems. Each story shows in a clear and detailed way the steps that contributed to making the product unique and precious. Devoleum automatically creates a product storytelling, easily accessible on our platform from any device simply by scanning a QR code. Devoleum is an open source project, free and open to everyone.	Italy
DLTM (Distretto Ligure delle Tecnologie Marine)	SmartBol (Smart Bill of Lading)- blockchain in shipping document to create a paperless circuit	Italy
DNABlockchain	DNABlockchain aims to connect DNA science with machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI) to create a genetic barcode for every bottle of extra virgin olive oil (EVOO). The system works by incorporating the DNA profiles of the olive groves and the EVOO they produce in a blockchain system, ensuring full traceability from olive grove to shelf. The blockchain framework will also include geo-locus, yield, harvesting and milling time and other quality parameters.	Greece
DNV-GL	My Story is a blockchain powered digital assurance solution to trace the wine from grape to the bottle, applied on 3 wine makers (Ricci Curbastri, Ruffino and Torrento). Consumers, using their smart device to scan the QR-code on the bottles they can instantly browse product facts, the wine's timeline and locations from grape to store for every bottle.	Italy
DNV-GL	The Certification and Assurance Company grant the record of its certificates in a Blockchain to allow the control of the validity and the update of the document in object. DNV records the certificates on the public VeChain Blockchain where it has the right to creates new certificates and to update all the information. Simultaneously, DNV takes advantage from the authentication, decentralization and encryption of the technology.	Italy
Downstream Beer	BCT to inform consumers about beer ingredients and brewing methods. Goal: Trust through transparency, empowering the consumer by giving them an immutable trace and trace on their beer cans	Ireland
Dyagora	certify and ensure the quality and authenticity of wines, protecting producers and consumers.	Portugal
eAgronom	We bring together world-class experts from IT, agronomy, and environmental sciences to help farmers return carbon back into the soil, grow crops sustainably and profitably while leading the world toward cleaner nature and healthier food. Blockchain based transparent tracking and scientifically proven carbon sequestering methodology ensures high quality authentic carbon credits for the buyers.	Estonia
Electrocoin	The company Electrocoin d.o.o. deals with mediation in cryptocurrency trading and crypto payment processing. We buy and sell cryptocurrencies from physical, legal and institutional clients and enable merchants to accept payments in cryptocurrencies in Croatia and the rest of the European Union.	Croatia
Endemic	Endemic is a local startup. It is a digital gallery built on blockchain technology, in fact an infrastructure for artists that allows them, in addition to their standard visibility, to have galleries in the form of NFT where they can exhibit their works of art.	Croatia
Esselunga	To guarantee the project "Sustainable Fair Trade Cocoa", all chocolate tablets branded Esselunga will be traced by Blockchain by 2025. GOALS: guarantee to the consumers the transparency through traceability of the raw material and help the local community involved into Cocoa cultivation For doing this, Esselunga collaborated with Altromercato (the main Fair-Trade company in Italy) and Gebana (his partner based in Togo)	Italy
EthicHub	EthicHub is a crowdlending marketplace. We connect small farming communities with international lenders and direct buyers. The protocol is similar to DeFi, has a native token (Token Ethix), and is deployed on Celo and Ethereum blockchain. They operate through smart contracts deployed on blockchain and they do not operate their own network.	Spain

EZ Lab	Developer of the Blockchain Tech designed for Agrifood sector. The aim is to build a radically better agrifood system through traceability, transparency and certification. The developed platform is AgriOpenData, and supports farmers in the traceability and certification of agricultural products through BCT and Smart Contracts	Italy
EZ Lab Blockchain Solutions WINE BLOCKCHAIN	EZ Lab is an innovative PMI specialized in Smart Agrifood solutions to support farms, agronomists. WINE Blockchain builds trust and transparency between the producer and the final consumer, by controlling the wine production chain from the origin of grapes to the transformation into the bottle.	Italy
FACT	BCT on sparkling water. Consumers will access supply chain information with the aim to build more transparency	France
FAIRCHAIN	CERTH: FAIRCHAIN will contribute to the development of intermediate food value chains, which combine elements from both short and long value chains, to achieve food systems that are more sustainable from an environmental, social and economic perspective. The scope of the FAIRCHAIN will be the fruit and vegetable and dairy sectors. The fruit, vegetable and dairy sectors are strategic in Europe, yet small-scale producers are in a weak and vulnerable position. The sector is nevertheless prone to a large variety of innovations and there's an increasing consumer demand for nutritious, healthy and sustainably produced food. The project will cover the entire value chain, with a focus on postharvest steps as power imbalances are mainly attributed to concentration in the processing and retail sectors in conventional supply chains.	Greece
Farmeye	technology offers a secure, blockchain-enabled digital chain of custody for agricultural soil samples with environmental laboratories as the customer. However, what's also notable about Farmeye is the fact it was spun out from Ireland's active university research sector and received funding from one of the new incubators there that is supporting ag-tech startups.	Ireland
FarmSustainaBI	This is a EU funded program implementing a holistic approach to reduce greenhouse gas from livestock farming. IoT devices monitor the animals' behaviour. A blockchain-based platform for collecting and analysing data for providing recommendations and managing decisions for livestock.	Greece
Ferrero	Sap Ariba Strategic Sourcing Suite, Sap Ariba Supplier Risk, Sap Ariba Spend Analysis and others solutions. The aim in 2017 was to create an integrated platform to consolidate all expenses and to create a global partner network to manage supply, orders, invoices and payments	Italy
Filedgr	Blockchain backed system to support Cargo Insurance. With our project we will help insurance companies pinpoint where and when the damage occurred, in the complex network the supply chain is. We will employ perception sensors of smartphones, and environmental sensors combined with blockchain persistence. Cargo and the container conditions will be monitored consistently with Filedgr.	Luxembourg
Food Chain	Sweden BCT startup that aims to create a traceable food production from seed to fork preventing food fraud, infected food, food related diseases and several other problems in the food industry. Things that's messing things up for the producers and finally the consumer.	Sweden
Food Insights	– a range of supply chain solutions – from carbon monitoring, digital passports, digital food buying, and “data driven storytelling” – based on blockchain technology.	Netherlands
FoodChain spa	Foodchain SPA is an Italian company that works on food supply chain traceability through blockchain solutions. In 2028 the case study realized to Torrefazione San Domenica was included into the mapping of Osservatori Digitali Innovation of Politecnico di Milano. Foodchain traces food products from origin to final consumer using blockchain technology. Blockchain is a public, distributed and decentralized ledger, where information is encrypted and stored in a tamper-proof and secure way. Once data is entered into the system and validated, it becomes unalterable. Thanks to IoT (Internet of Things) devices it is possible to implement traceability that covers each phase of the supply chain including production, logistics and distribution. It uses QR codes, NFC and RFID for physical support.	Italy
Fratelli Corrà	Blockchain on Mortandela della Val di Non via the platform ITEMx of the startup Genuine Way (Switzerland) to grand traceability of the production chain	Italy
Géant Vert	BCT application through the French start-up Connecting Food. The goal is to ensure the veracity of brand commitments through the verification of documents and	France

	processes. By acting as a transparency third party, Connecting Food enables brands and manufacturers to strengthen consumer confidence.	
Glauco Trapanese Apicoltura	Tokenizaion on blockchain of the whole honey production process. The Blockchain implemented is the one from AgrichaINitalia (an italian IoT startup specialized in the Agrifood and Chemical fields)	Italy
GMerits	P2P technologies, such as DLTs, including blockchains, are providing completely new opportunities to organise our society. However, technologies are just enablers. We must set a direction for these developments. We must proactively conduct large scale experiments with alternative economic structures. The future of our society must rely not solely on ideologies, bu on solid experiments and data. Our Generalised Merits (GMeRitS) endeavour aims to tackle this huge predicament by taking baby steps towards wide scale experiments with alternative economic structures. In particular, our aim is to try and evaluate various anti-rival compensation and governance structures. Our vision is base on intimate interconnection of three themes: money and debt shaping our collective thinking, market failures especially in the data markets, and the invention of DLTs.	Finland; Italy; Spain;
GO BLOCKCHAIN MADERA	Wood supply chains in Spain are highly inefficient and lack transparency impacting costefficiency and sustainability among others, while there are major IT advances nowadays to improve these by making use of outstanding software technologies as Blockchain. "Blockchain" comprise a stack of technologies that introduce distinguished elements not available before that can play a key role in final solutions, among them are: decentralization, shared-governance and extreme granularity. On the other hand, at wood supply chains there are so many interested players taking part as well as so many devices and sensors that software becomres absolutely necessary as an orchestrating tool.	Spain
Golden Sparrow Technologies	Start-up in Latvia that provides tools in order to achieve fair trade and enhance market access opportunities for small and middle farmers in need. Smart Contracts are on Polygon blockchain. The blockchain is for tracing purposes.	Latvia
Group Fercam	Group Fercam (Logistic Group) Deal with Art Right startup platform for artwork transport, taking advantage of the innovatie artwork passport developed by the platform and based on the Blockchain and the AI	Italy
Gruppo Felsineo	The historical company producer of Mortadella Bologna IGP will sell on the market the firsts product traced by Blochckain. Via QR-code framing, the consumer can get access to all production chain information. Other aims of the technology are to increase the overall quality and safety of raw materials and to reduce waste.	Italy
Gruppo Grigi	Blockchain application on Pasta supply chain to certify the 100% organic origin of the pasta brand Aliveris. The project aims to trace the whole chian form the supply up to the distributions	Italy
Herta	The farmers, suppliers, slaughterhouses, and other producers in Herta's supply chain are now able to digitally and automatically audit all their products in real-time, automatically produce digital twins in a GS1-compliant standard, manage internal traceability and compliance to product specs more efficiently, and share tamperproof data equitably with major manufacturing clients.	France
Iberchain	Tracking of origin of black pork	Spain
Ifin Sistemi	Development of TrustedChain, a private blockchain platform run only form TSP (Trust Service Provider). TrustedChain®, the first blockchain network of European Trust Service Providers specifically designed for highly sensitive sectors, with cutting-edge applications for public administration, e-government, banking, e-health and industry. Emphasis is thus placed on systemic trust, law compliance, adequate technical performance, confidentiality of transactions and long-term preservation of data.	Italy
Impactbuying	have a 'powerchain' built on HyperLedger Fabric (not to be confused with the Estonian project by the same name) which "combines value chain mapping, supply chain risk analysis and risk mitigation with the opportunities offered by blockchain technology ... to enhance traceability in (food) supply chains)"	Netherlands
Infratab	BCT study (RFID Tags & Blockchain) for fish products belonging to the cold-chain. Infratab Freshtime is a temperature monitoring software solution to provide product managers with real time shelf-life status	France
Ingrédia	BCT on milk to henhence consumers' trust. The system records data flows making them tamper-proof. The flows are computerized and the platform verifies in real time that each product complies with its specificaions. At the end of the chain, the	France

	traceability information and the proof of the audit are made accessible to the end consumers.	
Isotopic	Isotopic Brings together Web 3.0 Game Developers, to host their applications on a unified platform built for everyone to enjoy. The Isotopic development team is a family of innovators that believe in a unified web 3.0 of the future	Greece
Istituto Superiore di Sanità Italiana	The Italian platform for the study of liver therapies will be the first Italian ledger realized by Blockchain technology. By doing this, all infectious-disease specialists will have data on over 12,000 patients and over 100 clinical studies	Italy
itTaxi	Together with the Italian start-up Chainside has developed a system that allows the race payment in Bitcoin	Italy
Konzum	Through the Konzum d.d. web shop, enables payment with cryptocurrencies	Croatia
Labeyrie Fine Foods	Blockchain technology application on 2 references of Norwegian smoked salmon (le Saumon Fumé Grandes Origines Cercle Polaire Norvégien 4 tranches et le Saumon Fumé de Norvège 4 tranches) in order to let the consumer verify product's quality and animal welfare care	France
Lancement	Blockchain on flour "Savoir Terre" to trace flour's origins and production steps	France
Lavazza	Blockchain applied on the new Speciality Blend Noble Volcano to guarantee coffee sustainability and production chain traceability. QR-code is placed on the package to get access to all production chain information	Italy
Leilão a Bordo/Lota Digital	Digital Auction house for fish	Portugal
Linear IT	Blockchain to the "Smart Mobility" applicable to pay parkings and other urban services	Italy
MMAon	Our vision is to put the power in the palms of the fans. MMAON will digitize the stadium and make combat sports more interactive and engaging for the fans. We bring the fan closer to the fighter, to the fight and to the sport - they become a true insider. Our innovative and customized features give the fan a unique experience.	Croatia
Mondelez	Blockchain technology application on the biscuit Véritable Petit Beurre of LU brand. Consumers can access to supply chain information. The project is a cooperation of 4 cooperatives and 2 millers	France
Mondelez International	BCT to trace USA exports. The first project will regard the crackers brand Triscuit. The aim was to grant the transparency on wheat quality and origin	France
Moyee Coffee	BCT pilot project to provide supply chain transparent while making real-time payments to Ethiopian farmers for coffee beans	Ireland
Mulino Val D'Orcia	Collaborating with Ifin Sistemi and OSItalia, thanks to the platform TrustedChain the consumer can access data as grain milling date, ton/hectars of grain and other process information traced by Blockchain technology	Italy
Nest egg	stock and process monitoring and management. Not agri-food specific but applicable: "our system simplifies stock organization and process tracking, no matter what industry you operate in"	Netherlands
Nestlé and Carrefour	Blockchain experiment on Mousline purée (National and European brand). Consumers will get access to potatoes varieties used, date and place of production, quality control information, place and date of storage before price placing.	France
Nestlé Italia	Pilot project with Microsoft about traceability certification about Bacio Perugina export: from the Italian establishment to the importers and the distributors. GOAL: avoid and monitor falsification	Italy
NumAgri use case : Interceréale	Traceability of French Corn for animal feed. The aim is to trace French corn precisely from its production to its use as feed for animal. Therefore, the French corn could be valorized for human consumption of the final animal product.	France
nutrasign	The solution Food Track is a platform, powered by blockchain, that enables the creation of unique digital records in a safe and immutable way of every product, offering traceability from origin to table. Food Journey TM is a digital platform, powered by blockchain, that tracks the history of food products. It validates the origin of the product as well as the processes associated to them. It guarantees product authenticity throughout the supply chain.	Spain
Nutrisafe	SECURITY IN FOOD PRODUCTION AND LOGISTICS WITH DISTRIBUTED LEDGER TECHNOLOGY. The project aims to analyze the resiliency of the food supply chain and explore the potential of increasing transparency in regional food supply	Germany

	with the implementation of DLT into practice. This is further examined through knowledge transfer via consumer experiments.	
OBEC (one block for educational credential)	New technologies such as blockchain may offer to revolutionise the educational field by simplifying and facilitating the issuing and validation of learning credentials across European countries in a unified and enforceable manner. In this way, OBEC hopes to contribute to the creation of a barrier-free education system that can prosper through enriched diversity and increased transnational mobility.	Sweden; Croatia; Italy; Belgium
okelchain	Development of a tool for data security that allows certifying biometric and animal health data, from the birth of the animal to the consumer, this will seek to eliminate food fraud in the meat sector. Batura mobile is the leader of this project where Enkoa has taken part as a technological partner and also Agents of the Basque Science and Technology Network of the Basque Country, such as Ikerlan, Isea S.Coop or Neiker. This project is included within Enkoa's diversification efforts towards the bio-agri-food sector, which is expected to have great growth in the upcoming years.	Spain
Oleificio Zucchi	Blockchain to increase the traceability already existing in the company, with the focus on the environmental carbon foot print reduction. Feasibility study began in 2019	Italy
Olivacoin	Helping olive tree growers and oil producers to manage and finance their ventures while bringing transparency to the market.	Spain
OLWay	OLWay is an ecosystem that connects works, suppliers, carriers and customers in a single network allowing its participants to track & trace an entire path of order, payment and delivery flows.	Poland
Open Food Chain	public layer-1 blockchain solution that tracks products from farmer to the end-consumer	Netherlands
Organic Chain Networks	Origin Chain Networks is a startup that provide proof-of-origin services to enterprise customers tailored to market needs. Traceability, transparency and trust are the foundation of global digital trade. Focused on optimising supply, Origin Chain Networks bring the benefits of emerging technology to the agri-food sector.	Ireland
Origin Trail	OriginTrail, with its eponymous solution, enables easy tracking of the origin of dairy and meat products, and is expected to make a real revolution in food safety. Using blockchain technology, OriginTrail enables the monitoring of traceability in supply chains from the source to the point of sale of food, thereby ensuring the credibility of the collected information.	Slovenia
OURZ	OURZ Blockchain Plattform for purpose & sustainability-driven to provide transparency, trust & sustainability for food & beverage brands	Germany
Pasta di Gragnano IGP	Blockchain application on the first Pasta IGP for no use of pesticides and glyphosphate (any fito-sanitary product application. The collaboration with Authentico allow the consumers to access to all supply chain information	Italy
Pasta ValentiniA32	Use of the Blockchain to certify company's value: quality, safety and raw materials origin of the fresh pasta supply chain	Italy
Pastificio Agricolo Mancini	By collaborating with Apio start up and basing on IBM Food Trust technology, it has been created the digital ID of pasta. The aim is a clear communication with the final customer of the whole supply chain	Italy
peaq	peaq is the Web3 network powering the Economy of Things (EoT) on Polkadot, the most environmentally-friendly blockchain network. peaq enables entrepreneurs and developers to build decentralized applications for vehicles, robots, and devices, while empowering users to govern and earn as connected machines provide goods and services. Together with leading consortia, including Gaia-X and MOBI, peaq is co-creating the standards that will power the future of mobility and other connected industries while working to democratize abundance in the Age of Automation.	Germany
Pilot 4.2 Consumer Awareness: Milk Quality and Animal Welfare Tracking Management	Pilot action from the H2020 DEMETER project. The pilot aims to optimise the flow of information among the breeding farm and the processing company and to improve communication between actors right up to the consumer, implementing a traceability system, increasing food liability and trust.	Italy
Pomologik	BCT to trace APPLE JUICE production "Äppelmust Spårbar" from the Pomologik craft store comes in a KRAV-marked version, based on Swedish KRAV apples from the apple growers Lundmark and Callenbring in Österlen	Sweden
Ponti SpA	Blockchain for apples vinegar traceability. Consumers, by QU-code framing can know on real time the type, date and municipality of apples picking	Italy
Poseidon	Climate positive purchase.	Malta

	Gamified ESG engagement is a way of using games and rewards to encourage people to be more aware of and take action on environmental, social, and governance (ESG) issues.	
PoSeID-on	PoSeID-on will develop and deliver an innovative intrinsically scalable platform, as an integrated and comprehensive solution aimed to safeguard the rights of data subjects, exploiting the cutting-edge technologies of Smart Contracts and Blockchain, as well as support organizations in data management and processing while ensuring GDPR compliance.	Italy; Belgium; Spain; France; Portugal; NL; Malta
pOsti	Startup focused on Agrifood sector born to help producers and restaurants to tell to the consumers the quality and the value its products have by the supply chain transparency	Italy
Princes Industrie Alimentari	Blockchain application (by Abaco Group technology) to monitor field data such as water, nitrogen and pesticides on tomatoes. Moreover it was applied a GPS mapping system to trace tomatoes movement on the supply chain during the annual collection phase. This was done via localization devices on the truck.	Italy
rec(R) (Real Economy Currency)	The rec (Real Economy Currency) is Barcelona's social currency, a type of social or local currency. It is a citizen exchange system complementary to the euro, allowing transactions in a community between individuals, institutions and businesses that accept it. It provides an alternative to the globally dominant financial and monetary system. Social currencies favour local businesses and the profits revert to the community. The rec (R) is an exclusively digital currency and can be used with a mobile app, a payment card or via the website.	Spain
Regione Lombardia	Blockchain Prototype system development for Dairy and Beef to trace all controls carried on the supply chain - 2019. The study was made with the participation of Latteria Sociale Valtellina and Consorzio Lombardo Produttori carne Bovina	Italy
Regione Lombardia "Nidi Gratis"	Blockchain application in Cinisello Balsamo Municipality to reduce bureaucracy time for applications (ex. Fee KinderGardens application) – 2019 Collaboration between the Municipality and the INPS	Italy
Regione Piemonte	VisitPiemonte project, developed with the support of the University of Turin. GOAL: make sure that the potential tourists can access discounts, offers and coupons while doing online research to organize their stay without intermediation costs.	Italy
Round T Block srl	IT company specialized into blockchain solution development to grant traceability and efficiency. The 2 main solutions are: - BEAD; anti-counterfeiting solution that grants to brands and customers the safety and the certifications of their products. - PA:K; it is the solution for public and private parking management allowing flexible payments	Italy
RUMORE	The RUMORE project is a European project in 4 different countries facilitating rural-urban cooperation and partnerships. CERTH, as a partner, provided the infrastructure (node) for the network and the application built on blockchain for recording and monitoring the entire rice value chain to support the Greek pilot. The agricultural product under the application's focus was rice.	Greece
San Daniele	Blockchain application to trace the pre-sliced product trays. The goal is to digitalize the current paper-based traceability system linked to the DOP Italian product. The main goal is to improve the organization and product flows inside the company. The database will be exclusively accessible from the operators	Italy
Savio Firmino	For every product made by Savio Firmino's artisans, a "digital twin" is created that goes on the blockchain. Information such as year and place of production as well as materials are recorded on the blockchain. Everything is visible to the customer via QR code or NFC technology. Certifying the quality of the information provided is the fact that the nodes on the blockchain are monitored by the Chamber of Commerce and industry regulators. The blockchain in this case is an 'Italian Distributed Ledger'. All the information is then notarized in a second layer that uses Bitcoin's blockchain, considered one of the most authoritative and secure. Essentially, the system runs on a double-layer blockchain. In addition, Savio Firmino wants to offer its customers a guarantee called Circle Life, a certification designed to follow the entire life cycle of the product, from production to manufacture, through restoration to disposal. This certifies authenticity, uniqueness and sustainability.	Italy
Seeds srl	It is an innovative startup that was born as an academic spinoff of the University of Palermo. They use Blockchain and DLT technologies to create solutions in the field of agri-food tracking, enhancing the methodologies concerning both tracking and	Italy

	tracing of products in the course of their life and production cycle, through their platform named seedsbit.	
senken	Senken is an easy-to-use platform to access the largest selection of climate assets for transparent climate actions and finance. To ensure the quality and integrity of each project, senken provides additional security and transparency at the data level. Confidently invest in climate projects that meet the values of your company. For verifiable climate impact, purchase, trade and retire carbon credits to offset your companies' emissions.	Germany
SenseFinity blockchain	Sensefinity's trackers and sensors collect location and environment conditions from the transportation and storage of cargo.	Portugal
S-Group	Finnish retail cooperative S-Group, will test their Pike-perch radar solution, which is based on IBM Blockchain technology, during the summer season as part of the retail group's strategy to improve customer experience. The aim is to increase transparency in the food chain and to provide customers with greater information about the food route all the way from the source to the store shelves.	Finland
SilKe	Secure food chain through the application of blockchain technology	Germany
SmartBlockChainGateway Platform	New innovative blockchain platform developed for the Winery. The platform dynamically collects and manages all data and documents to support company business (invoices, production data, analysis, certificates, delivery notes, photos, ...)	Italy
SmartShortChain	SmartShortChain provides a configurable farm2fork platform that helps companies on creating transparency in the food supply chain. Registers activities and partnerships within the food chain from harvest to consumer; monitors soil and product values; aims to incorporate other values such as CO2 storage, water collection, biodiversity, etc within product information.	Netherlands
SolidWorld	provide forward-contracts to 'derisk' carbon-based financing of agricultural projects.	Estonia
Spinosa SPA	Mozzarella traceability certified by Blockchain technology to protect the PDO from frauds. Blockchain can protect the Made in Italy	Italy
Stella Wines	Case History of the SmartBlockChainGateway platform, to monitor and collect data in the vineyard via the App 4Grapes, and the calculation of the Bigot index (patented evaluation method of qualitative potential of a vineyard)	Italy
Supreme Green Cotton	The traceability system allows you to follow the way from the cotton seed to the yarn by scanning the QR-Code on the label or entering the code on our website. Resources (water, energy, CO2) can be saved from the application. Blockchain is an enabler for a trustless multistakeholder environment.	Greece
Survcoin	The survcoin is a decarbonisation coin being launched as a pilot project in Luxembourg to demonstrate that dedicated currencies can contribute to both individual and collective efforts to reduce our carbon footprint.	Luxembourg
t3rn	An open hosting platform for smart contracts, that enables trustless, multi-chain execution and composable collaboration. t3rn creates frictionless multichain smart contract execution, that's accountable, scalable, and completely trust-free for investors, users, and developers.	Germany
TE-Food	Farm-to-Table Food Traceability Solution using Blockchain technology. TE-FOOD provides the full spectrum of tools and solutions to enable complete supply chains to track and trace their products. Tailored to processes, data sets, and technical environment, it provides a secure and scalable solution to improve transparency.	Germany
TERRA+	TERRA+ is an innovative solution for delivering trust in Agri-Food supply chain through blockchain technology. Consumers are able to verify the authenticity of a single product's characteristics accompanied with full product history, by a simple QR code scan.	Greece
Terres du Sud	BCT on duck supply chain branded "Delmond l'Originel" with the aim to grant to the consumer the traceability and quality of the products	France
The Gepek	The Gepek is a new platform for package delivery based on a carpooling model. It's intended exclusively for the carriage of packages, not people!	Croatia
TITAN	The new innovations will deliver transparency solutions in the areas of food safety and authenticity, traceability, health and sustainability and improving information to the consumer. TITAN will provide an extensive platform for the development of a wide range of innovations that aid transparency and address key challenges identified in the European Green Deal (EGD); including exploiting Blockchain, AI and IoT	Italy; Greece; Spain; Portugal; Morocco; UK; France; Germany; Belgium; NL;

		Poland; Norway; Finland; Serbia; Switzerland
TNO	TNO has made a significant investment in Blockchain Technologies with an emphasis on the following key areas of research and application expertise: Business Models and Governance Identity and Access Management Smart Contracts interactions and security Performance and Scalability Interoperability and Standards Blockchains in Society - Policy, Ethics and Regulation Areas of application currently include logistics, banking and insurance, agriculture and supply chains, health and cybersecurity.	Netherlands
Toucan	- tokenization of Verra-issued carbon credits, including agricultural credits.	Germany
Tracifier	Tracifier is a blockchain-based traceability application used for food and certificate verification that supports the accuracy and transparency of customer claims with monitoring and inspecting of products. The Solution covers the whole value chain of food from the early stage of harvesting product in farms, sampling the product for quality assurance, testing in laboratories, and monitoring and auditing the supplying process of goods to the final consumers in the market. It is a start-up. From EU-Startup article: There are identities for the platform (Each user will have a unique cryptographic-encoded key (token) that guarantees access, tracks their data input history.) From LinkedIn post hash: The blockchain technology used is Hyperledger Fabric	Germany
Track Blockchain	Agriculture and agri-food industry represent a very important sectors in all countries involved in the project. In the last years, more and more knowledge is required in the disciplines necessary to support innovation in the sector: innovative technologies, innovative models, innovative designs etc. Everyone in the sector must have increasingly specialized skills: digital, more useful than ever for certifications, supply chain traceability, online transactions (blockchain, value chain). Even in the food sector many companies have to deal with the mismatch between real skills possessed by their workers and skills actually required. Blockchain adoption in agri-food industry has the potential to simplify and integrate agriculture supply chains but the level of its application is still very low in all EU countries. It has been demonstrated that Blockchain technology can positively influence two relevant aspects of the food supply chain: Traceability and Crop Insurance.	Lithuania; Spain; Greece; Croatia
TrustDelivery	TrustDelivery was born from the collaboration among pOsti, FIPE and EY. The Food Delivery traced by Blockchain. The platform allows to trace all food preparations steps accordingly to Fipe and Assodelivery provisions. The system will grant the rigid hygienic/sanitary measures required for the food delivery.	Italy
UBIRCH	Securing IoT Data on Blockchain via Blockchain-on-a-Sim. UBIRCH offers data trust: data is sealed at the source, anchored into multiple public blockchains and made verifiable through an API.	Germany
Umbria Food Cluster	Umbria food cluster is a project born from the collaboration of 4 food companies based in Umbria: I Potti de Fratini, Grigi Alimentari, Molitoria Umbra and Agribosco with the aim to create together products granted by blockchain technology.	Italy
VarGroup	VarGroup develop and create vertical solution based on Blockchain technology to B2B and B2C companies with the aim to improve efficiency, trust and security of business processes. It covers logistic, food, fashion & luxury, real estate, energy, insurance & fintech.	Italy
VeraCruz amêndoas	Tracking of almonds from the farm to the final consumer	Portugal
We.Trade	we.trade uses IBM Blockchain to create a connected platform to simplify international trade. Cross-border trade can resemble the Wild West with its inherent risks and the difficulty of navigating complex and difficult processes. Founded by a consortium of major banks in Europe, we.trade connects buyers, sellers and their banks in a network that uses IBM blockchain technology to help simplify international trading. The blockchain technology provides an immutable, single record of all transactions, reducing risk and automating transactions among trusted, vetted trading partners. Working with IBM Services, we.trade brought the platform to market quickly – from launch and pilot to full production – using iterative and agile development processes.	Sweeden; Italy; Germany; The Netherlands; Spain; France

Eco Trail	The purpose of the project implementation is to develop and demonstrate a standardized information solution for the establishment of a just-in-time production environment (JiT environment) and to use the opportunities offered by blockchain technology, IoT (Internet of Things) and management of a large amount of data. The goal of the project is to develop products that will enable traceability, management and optimization of production, be cheaper than the current offer and can be installed on different systems in production. In the pilot part of the project, a system will be developed that will measure the impact of production on the environment, monitor material and energy flows, and enable transparent interaction with stakeholders (consumers, business partners, regulatory authorities and other stakeholders). Additionally, it will enable transparency throughout the entire production chain from raw material to product using blockchain technology.	Slovenia
Augmented reality process control platform	The aim of the project is the development and demonstration of the ARGO process management platform, which represents a suitable solution for the virtualisation of the management and maintenance procedures of infrastructure and industrial systems through the use of distributed reality technologies. The result of the project will be the ARGO platform as a unique network of solutions that enables digitised inventory and infrastructure management, unified and real-time identification of potential problematic situations based on real-time data, accurate navigation to the location of failures or malfunctions, and virtualisation and implementation of the management protocol using augmented reality software.	Slovenia
ECTA Blockchain Portal for Providers and Customers	The project is based on open-source software design, blockchain technology, and AI systems. Blockchain technology enables traceability, transparency, simplicity, and equity. The main idea of the project is to connect the people offering their skills (providers) and the people wanting to make use of said skills (customers) in an efficient and fair manner. The project connects several areas that have not yet been connected before: the field of human resources, the area of blockchain enabling technologies, and artificial intelligence. The ECTA ecosystem operating in this manner represents the service which is the common denominator of social networks for professionals (e.g. LinkedIn), online portals for freelancers (e.g. Fiverr), employment agencies, notaries and lawyers, and courts. ECTA will facilitate the verification of most information through blockchain.	Slovenia
SiChain	Designed and built by HashNET and partners, EU-Chain was established to provide one of a possible solution to European blockchain needs. With active cooperation with European governments, public and private sector, dozens of blockchain projects in various business scenarios, such as electronic data and document eDelivery, energy supply chain and others have been accomplished on a pilot Slovenian national project SI-Chain, on which EU-Chain builds its foundations. With its pioneering features, the EU-Chain can provide blockchain solutions with the speed of over 20.000 transactions per second.	Slovenia
Blockchain Association of Slovenia	We connect blockchain enthusiasts with universities and companies working with blockchain.	Slovenia
Blockchain Think Tank Slovenia	Blockchain Think Tank Slovenia is a non-profit association open to all stakeholders interested in blockchain technology. The Think Tank acts as a single point for collecting ideas and proposals, and at the same time has access to relevant representatives from the government, regulators and other institutions of the public sector, to whom it forwards ideas and proposals from the economy, entrepreneurs, academics and individuals in an open manner.	Slovenia
Blocksquare	Blocksquare is a developer of blockchain-based tokenization system for commercial real estate properties. Our vision is to provide real estate businesses the world's best real estate tokenization system with all required tools and modules for creation, issuance, sale, distribution, management, tracking, and trade of tokenized properties.	Slovenia
Eligma	Eligma is a global facilitator of seamless and secure crypto payments.	Slovenia
Viberate	As the worlds' largest resource of reliable information on all things music, we aim to map and standardize the entire global music ecosystem.	Slovenia
HashNet	HashNET main net is alive and kicking, featuring scalable, fast, secure and fair transactions. It employs Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) and consensus algorithm that keep all the positive characteristics of a blockchain technology while increasing throughput and lowering time to finality.	Slovenia
Geton	Geton is a blockchain solutions platform secure and transparent environment for web applications that use cryptocurrencies for operations.	Slovenia

Hiveterminal	Blockchain-based invoice financing platform	Slovenia
SmartCargo	SmartCargo offers a solution for the cargo industry that ensures transparency and gives everyone overview over the logistics process.	Slovenia

Table 6 Non-EU and International Use Cases

Industry/Project	Description	Country
Aber	Project Aber was an initiative launched by the central banks of Saudi Arabia and United Arab Emirates to explore the viability of a single dual-issued digital currency as an instrument of domestic and cross-border settlement between the two countries.	Saudi Arabia; Bahrain
Abu Dhabi Digital Authority	ADDA has been developing a government blockchain platform to enable and support a secure, trusted dataexchange mechanism between Abu Dhabi government entities and any other external organizations. The blockchain platform is being designed with a unique abstraction layer that acts as a connector to enable communication between various blockchains, while minimizing the underlying complexities of each individual system. The project is aimed at allowing government stakeholders to share and exchange data across government departments and with external private-sector participants, including individuals, to facilitate seamless transactions, and to enable efficient delivery of government services. The concept then led the bank to create a digital financial instrument with a legal framework in place: the e-cheque.	UAE
Addenda	Insurance payment settlement platform	UAE
Afyarekod	digital health data platform that allows health facilities to capture, store, and have realtime access to the patient's health data. The patient maintains the sovereign right of ownership of their health data by employing blockchain modules.	Kenya
AgriChain	AgriChain supports traditional, well-established agricultural supply chains with a dynamic and seamless management software solution. Our product is a simple-to-use, secure, independent platform that connects and transfers information between supply chain participants. To manage agricultural products as they move across the globe, businesses need a transparent, trustworthy platform to facilitate those transactions. AgriChain builds networks amongst key stakeholders and improves time to market, while reducing supply chain costs and inefficiencies. Combining user-friendly native mobile software for farming, logistics providers and receival sites with a powerful web application for business administration, AgriChain provides end-to-end visibility of the agricultural supply chain. Our product automates the delivery process, from the paddock to end user. As each load is picked up and delivered, data is collected and time-stamped at each point along the supply chain. All parties are updated in real-time as each transaction takes place. Through this process, AgriChain improves productivity, increases visibility, manages stock, automates freight orders and eliminates manual paperwork.	Australia
AgriDigital	Process complex agricultural transactions through smart contracts. Your inventory, data and access to supply chain finance, all in one place. We connect you with your network, from farmer to consumer. With us, grain management is easy.	Australia; USA
AgriLedger	Supporting farmers in tracing food origins, transactions. AgriLedger uses DLT for the gathering and analysis of information on small-holder farms, determining crop yields, establishing provenance, and facilitating payments and governance, with transparent end-to-end record-keeping.	UK
Agriota E-Marketplace	The Agriota platform will connect Indian farmers directly with the entire food industry in the UAE, including food processing companies, traders as well as wholesalers	UAE; India
Agriwallet	Agri-wallet is a digital wallet, a mobile financial tool, for the agricultural sector providing a business account for farmers, which they can use to save, buy, and earn. Financial platform: Agriwallet provides a financial platform to serve the agricultural value chains world-wide. It is easy to use for your customers, provides real-time insights and creates financial transparency.	Kenya
AgroChain	Agrochain is the most complete marketplace of agriculture commodities in Brasil. It increases comercialization efficiencies for agriculture commodities. It connects farmers, buyers, distributors and exporters in a digital environment that is easy, secure and optimizes results.	Brazil

	Your contracts and transactions are registered in the blockchain, with privacy, security.	
Agrotoken	Agrotoken transforms grains into a digital asset (an "Agrotoken"), to store or exchange for inputs, services and other assets. Agrotokens (i) allow commercial and financial transactions with the direct backing of the grains; (ii) are tradable digital assets backed by grain, as their value is linked to the price of grain. Agrotoken is the first global tokenization infrastructure for Agro-Commodities. Their value proposition will satisfy all financial needs in superior ways by creating tokens and connecting them to all farmer world. Also, they plan to tokenize different natural resources using this infrastructure. The company use Blockchain (multichain) for transaction with smart contracts. They connected "CEFI world" with "Defi world" between VISA and other banks, creating efficient products	Argentina; Brasil
AgUnity	providing a smartphone based blockchain service to small-holders farmers to facilitate financial inclusion	Australia
Aid:Tech	Decentralized Digital ID Infrastructure to facilitate Onchain Reputation via Proof of Reputation Protocol (PoR). PoR is a decentralised ecosystem built on a Proof of Stake (PoS) Network which is designed to facilitate trust-based interactions. The protocol rewards contributions through proven state-of-the-art blockchain architecture and Volunteer And Earn (VAE) tokens. It supports 3 services: Kaulana: volunteer and earn with PoR and VAE token Kokua: disbursements for disaster relief via Digital ID Valise: Web3 Digital Wallet where mobile banking meets crypto	Singapore
akaChain	Blockchain-backed enterprise platform for Digital ID akaChain, is an end-to-end, permissioned, multi-chain network based on the Hyperledger Fabric. The Privacy Preserved Bridge Protocol cryptographically stores private data to ensure transparency and security with a focus on empowering business innovations and creating a fair and objective network environment. It supports loyalty programs, transparency for finance (ex. eKYC, credit scoring) and trust for the supply chain (ex. food traceability and vehicle traceability)	Singapore; Japan; Vietnam
Antica Masseria Caroli	Project in collaboration with Blocksyte (US software house). Blockchain application to guarantee oil traceability and quality during the export in US by temperature, time, UR and light exposition via IoT sensors.	USA
Arabian Chain Technology	ArabianChain allows for self-executing, secure and globally accessible smart contracts and decentralized Apps to be developed, and for digital tokens to be built, transacted, tracked and safeguarded over a network of thousands of connected devices.	UAE
Arc-net	The European Horizon 2020 programme and the Chinese Ministry of Science and Technology (MOST) programme are jointly funding the project which will be led by Queen's University Belfast's Institute for Global Food Security (IGFS) and MOST. Project's aim is to use Blockchain to fight food fraud on meat sectors	Ireland-China
Auchan alimentos	Allows users to transparently get information about the food products they consume.	Portugal; France; Italy; Spain; Senegal and Vietnam
Authena	Authena uses more advanced sensor solutions to track and trace food products from the first to the last mile.	Switzerland
Avenews	supply chain transparency. The financial super app for Africa's agriculture industry. The Avenews app is a one-stop-shop for everything an agribusiness needs, from money management tools to digital payments and access to financing. With Avenews, agribusinesses can finally make informed financial decisions and unlock their full business potential. Avenews is building the first financial super app for the agricultural industry. We bring to the 2.5 million agricultural SMBs across Sub-Saharan Africa the tools that allow them to understand their business better, access capital, manage it, and source all the business services they need – all in one place.	Israel; Africa
BBChain	Blockchain Lab - a SaaS solution for creating and governing corporate blockchain networks/consortia	Brazil
BEACON research project	BEACON is a blockchain-fueled toolbox that couples leading Earth Observation technology with weather intelligence to deliver cost-efficient and actionable insights for the agri-insurance industry. BEACON offers an end-to-end solution to comprehensive risk and damage assessment, smart contract monitoring, and more. BEACON services enable the Agricultural Insurance sector to alleviate the effect of weather uncertainty when estimating risk of Agricultural Insurance products, reduce	Global

	the number of on-site visits for claim verification, reduce operational and administrative costs for monitoring of insured indexes and contract handling, and design more accurate and personalized contracts.	
BeefLedger SA	verification and traceability system that validates the providence and authenticity of its beef products, including credible sale history and consumer feedback	South Africa
Bext360	Bext360 provides comprehensive and measurable accountability for global supply chains. Our SaaS platform provides blockchain traceability and sustainability measures, including worker pay, carbon, water, and electricity, from farm to retail. Bext360 is a SaaS platform that provides ESG Intelligence, Traceability and Sustainable Finance. Bext360 focuses on supply chains such as coffee, seafood, timber, minerals, cotton and palm oil to provide a traceable fingerprint from producer to consumer.	USA; Burkina Faso
Binance	The world's leading blockchain and cryptocurrency infrastructure provider. First crypto-asset service provider to be granted full category 4 license from Central Bank of Bahrain, allowing it to offer a full-suite of crypto exchange services in Bahrain	Global; including Bahrain
Binkabi	Decentralized agricultural commodity trading	UK
Bitosis	Bitosis Cryptocurrency exchange platform	UAE
Bitsika	remittance app allows users to send money from one country to another	Cameroun
Bitt	Payment system/digital assets exchange.	Barbaros
Blockchain Climate Risk Crop Insurance	Blockchain Climate Risk Crop Insurance is a digital platform for standardized crop insurance for smallholder farmers in Africa, which increases their resilience to climate change by enabling transparent, timely, and fair payouts in extreme weather events.	Kenya
Bom Valor	BomValor is a solutions ecosystem based on blockchain specialized in of goods buying and selling. It promotes a more secure, authentic, neutral, trustable and accessible market, negotiation environments and transactions for people and enterprises. It is an auction house. To access Bom Valor platform, you'll need a blockchain powered digital id solution, called bviD. It uses OriginalMy blockchain ID solution and enables you to sign documents, authorize transactions and access to the BomValor Auction platform.	Brazil
Building Blocks		Global
Bypa-ss	Blockchain based health records management	Egypt
Cardano	Blockchain in Coffee supply chain	Ethiopia
Cardano	Blockchain in Coffee supply chain	UK
Cargill	"Hyperledger Grid To help make food and agricultural supply chains more inclusive – creating new markets for farmers and developing economies,"	USA
Cargo X- Egypt Advance Cargo Information System (ACI)	The Government of Egypt has made Advance Cargo Information (ACI) declarations mandatory and authorized CargoX as the blockchain document transfer gateway service provider in its national single window for trade facilitation NAFEZA. Cargo data and shipment documents (commercial invoices, final or initial bill of lading) are registered electronically in a secure manner before a shipment arrives at an Egyptian port to ensure that import security screening and customs procedures on the Egyptian side can be accomplished prior to shipment arrival to Egyptian seaports. Registration procedures involve data input by both the import and exporter of the shipment.	Egypt; Global
Celo-Mercy Corps Ventures Pilot	Delivering Stablecoin Loans Using DeFi for African Farmers	Kenya
Centrifuge	Centrifuge is an open, decentralized operating system to connect the global financial supply chain. It represents a decentralized bank, which can provide liquidity for farmers. Agri-SME financing.	Germany; USA
Cerviero	Cerviero, a plant cultivation system which is using latest technologies including Ethereum blockchain and others, is operating what is called Hydroponics. It uses DLT (Distributed Ledger Technology). Organization using Cerviero would be able to connect all of the hardware and software, the irrigation algorithms, data processing systems, production, fertilizers and supply chain management tools on the blockchain.	Italy; UAE
CheeseChain	The CheeseChain project targets the development and implementation of a platform to improve transparency and trust along the Tête-de-Moine value chain. This major advance for proof of origin, immutability, and transparency is achieved by combining biological data with storage in a Blockchain, combined with partner-specific databases.	Switzerland
Chekkit	Chekkit is a blockchain-powered technology that assists pharmaceutical and FMCG companies in fighting counterfeits and connecting them directly to their end consumers.	Nigeria

Decapolis	Compelio and NSCE: Decapolis is a Jordan and UK based global leader in food safety and quality traceability technology. The Decapolis platform, Decapolis Food Guard (DFG), ensures the safety and quality of food worldwide. Decapolis helps food producers to provide premium goods for which the end-to-end supply and production chains comply with strict safety and quality control standards.	UK; Jordan
Defimable - Farmbit	Farmbit is an open marketplace that brings investors and traders together, allowing crypto-financiers to discount trade invoices in exchange for a stable yield. This, in turn, provides working capital to the entrepreneurs on the platform.	Kenya
Ecotrace	Company composed of entrepreneurs with more than 10 years of experience in the agribusiness, offering a unique traceability solution, which brings trust, security and transparency in a platform based on technology. Thus, we establish a trust-based relationship in the entire value chain, from the origin to the final consumer. We started with Animal Protein, and expanded to any product that is produced in the farm and has to be traced, with the company's principles, all the way to the final consumer's table.	Brazil
Emirates NBD	NBD decided to use blockchain for Cheque fraud after testing blockchain for cross-border transactions and trade finance documentation in partnership with ICICI Bank in India. The initial pilot was launched in early 2017, first reaching the headlines when the bank partnered with the Central Bank of the UAE on a blockchain trial focused on cheque fraud. Under the pilot, Emirates NBD worked with the Central Bank to prove the technology was capable of production volumes. Next, it issued chequebooks with unique QR codes on each cheque registered on the bank's blockchain platform. Additionally, a string of 20 random characters was generated and added to the MICR (magnetic ink character recognition) band of the cheque. After a successful pilot, the bank rolled out the project across the UAE in March 2018 for all customers, becoming the first bank in the region to do so.	UAE
E-procurement Blockchain	B2B e-Procure is a trading name of Saudi Procurement Services, a company registered in Riyadh, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. Empowering B2B buyers and suppliers to manage, streamline and automate B2B payments, procurement and B2B e-commerce operations through a secure blockchain network from anywhere and anytime. Offering complete security and transparency to online business operations, whether transactions or general data	Saudi Arabia
Etherisc	Start-up using blockchain to provide decentralized insurance, has conceptualized how they can help the plight of farmers in the developing world. A developing world farmer would be insured for one or two dollars a month, too cheap for a traditional insurance provider to offer. Etherisc would execute a smart contract so that if the rainfall is below a threshold specified by insurance, it would be paid out to them automatically. Little human intervention for claims processing keeps costs low. More importantly, the farmer would receive timely payment, without having to deal with potentially corrupt bureaucrats	Germany; Kenya
Etisalat Digital UAE/ UAE Trade Connect (UTC)	The first commercialized blockchain platform aimed to digitize trade & trade finance in the United Arab Emirates, one of the largest and most important trading hubs in the world. UTC is built through a co-creation approach with a consortium of 9 banks. With more banks already planning to join the platform, UTC will soon become the national trade platform, paving the way for other trading actors to enter the network. Challenge of fraud where duplicate invoices UTC brought together eight major banks in the UAE, including First Abu Dhabi Bank (FAB), RAKBANK, Emirates NBD, Commercial Bank of Dubai, National Bank of Fujairah, Mashreq Bank, Abu Dhabi Islamic Bank and Commercial Bank International.	UAE
Evercity	Evercity is a blockchain, AI and IoT-based platform for impact measurement, management and investment. We help to attain UN Agenda 2030 by enabling impact funds & banks to increase impact measurement accuracy, efficiency of portfolio management & liquidity of impact investments.	Luxembourg; Singapore; Russia
Everex	start-up using blockchain to offer microfinancing to the developing world. By offering transparency, automating processing using smart contracts, and speeding up money transfers, Everex can significantly lower costs for the lender, which could lead to better terms being offered to borrowers, who then can take on larger loans to drive business growth beyond subsistence.	Thailand
Everledger	Everledger is the digital transparency company, providing technology solutions to increase transparency in global supply chains. Our purpose is to contribute greater	Australia; United Kingdom;

	clarity and confidence in the marketplaces where transparency is a strategic imperative.	United States; India; China; Israel
EY Skye	The Norwegian IT consulting firm acquired by EY last November, has developed a salmon tracing blockchain solution. The project was built on SAP's Cloud Platform and tracks each fish as it goes through the supply chain – from egg to fillet. An app will allow consumers to see where their fish has been, what 'batch' it is from, and even if the fish has been used in another product. This solution would give consumers more confidence in the product and help Norwegian producers protect themselves.	Norway
Farm to Plate	Compelio With Farm to Plate, Blockchain technology features like immutability prevent data duplication or modification of transactions unless validated by stakeholders thus addressing the gap that traditional food supply chain systems have. INOv: solve food supply chain problems with increased transparency, access to immutable and trusted data, and manage food quality and wastage, with Blockchain.	USA
farmer connect	Traceability platform composed of 3 components: - farmerid: digital wallet solution based on Self-Sovereign Identity, which allows farmers to connect to the agriculture supply chain, empowering them with their own digital identity and record of financial transactions; - connecthub: portal to all the farmer connect tools that enable the management of data across multiple stakeholders throughout the supply chain. It gives visibility across the product and fund journeys. - thankmyfarmer: web-based app that allows your customers and business partners, by scanning a QR code on pack, to trace the origins and quality of a product and learn about origin communities and sustainability programs. The solution enables:	Switzerland
Farmer Connect	farmer connect is an innovative supply chain technology provider, driven to empower and grow the entire supply chain. Roles in the supply chain are: farmers, traders, roasters and brands. The technologies referred in the site are: IBM Blockchain, SSI, Microsoft Azure, Twilio	Switzerland
FCE Platform	FCE Group AG is a full-fledged Blockchain for digitizing business processes, aimed to increase the efficiency and add value for food producers, distributors and end customers. This is achieved through resolving three fundamental issues of food industry: 1. Cultivate food supply chain traceability 2. Reducing administrative costs 3. Establishing direct marketing and communication with end customers	Switzerland
Fishcoin Project	Creating a blockchain based incentivized, traceability system for the first mile of seafood supply chains.	Singapore
Fjord Maritime	The platform is called FJORD HYBRID. The platform is deployed on an Ethereum layer 2 solution (nahmii). The platform is on measuring the carbon footprint using IoT devices.	Norway
FlexID	platform enables the issuance, storage, and sharing of verified digital identities, replacing paper-based physical credentials. The FlexID Wallet allows users to receive and share official credentials from various institutions. As a result, the FlexID solution enables individuals to gain access to financial, insurance, healthcare, and agricultural services.	South Africa
Food Trust	Improve the companies' ability to identify issues involved with food recalls. Deployed in several companies: Walmart, Nestlé, Dole, Driscoll, Golden State Foods, Kroger, McCormick, McLane, Tyson Foods, Unilever	Global
FoodLogiQ	Food supply chain management. FoodLogiQ® LLC is the leading SaaS provider of traceability, food safety and supply chain transparency solutions. FoodLogiQ Connect is the most comprehensive, data-driven software solution that enables supplier management, food safety compliance, quality incident management, recall management and whole chain traceability – all on a single platform built exclusively for the food industry. To meet mounting regulatory requirements and consumer demands for transparency, food companies are leveraging FoodLogiQ Connect to validate supplier compliance with food safety and act with confidence in the event of a food safety or quality issue.	USA
FoodQualiTrace	The project will increase the participation of digital innovation hubs (DIH) of Southeast Europe in the digital transformation of the agri-food sector with an emphasis on food traceability using blockchain technologies. The project focuses on support services that can significantly improve business operations with the help of	Romania; Croatia; Israel; Bosnia and Herzegovina

	digitalization, using blockchain technology, and creating a transparent supply chain from farm to table, as well as allowing the customer to know the history of a particular package or piece of food they are buying. The focus of the project is on food processors, buyers, regulators, local government officials and representatives of consumer protection associations. As a result of the project, participating DIHs are able to offer a range of new digital services: ecosystem analysis, technology plan, proof of concept, workshops and seminars, laboratory facilities, support for innovative business models.	
Global Mangrove Trust	A Singapore consortium consisting of commodity broker Marex Spectron, Kumi Analytics and the Global Mangrove Trust (GMT) is working towards the issuance of “blue bonds”. These are called blue because they finance coastal mangrove reforestation and conservation efforts in South East Asia, initially in Indonesia. The consortium is an example of financial innovation in the carbon space. Kumi Analytics is developing an automated system to verify and validate carbon sequestration in forests using remote sensing through satellites and machine learning. The estimated carbon that is being sequestered in growing or protected forests can be tokenised on GROVE, a blockchain application consisting of a series of smart contracts that has been developed by GMT with the help of the Disruptors, a group of elite developers working for DBS Bank and NUS blockchain spinoff Zilliqa. Together with Marex, the consortium partners are creating a digitally powered, ultra-scalable solution for carbon credits, specifically targeted at the commodity markets and primary industries.	Singapore
Gochain&SMARTKAS	Blockchain entity Gochain, a subsidiary of HBK Department of Projects in Abu Dhabi UAE has signed a joint venture agreement with SMARTKAS B.V. The agreement between His Highness Sheikh Hamad bin Khalifa Al Nahyan, member of the Ruling Family of Abu Dhabi, UAE, and his business HBK Department of Projects and SMARTKAS, an agricultural company based in the Netherlands, will provide a smart agriculture based on zero energy; zero water and zero waste	UAE; Netherlands
Grainchain	GrainChain creates innovative solutions to solve the complex challenges facing the global agricultural industry at every stage of the supply chain. We use cutting edge technology to make the process easier, faster and safer for all participants. GrainChain is capable of managing all pre and post-harvest processes through a cloud-based, blockchain and IoT-enabled platform consisting of a suite of complimentary products: Trumodity - transaction platform Seed audit - preharvest tools SiloSys - inventory management siloSys - transformation/complex processing HarvX – Logistics	USA
Grassroots Economics	Grassroots Economics is a non-profit foundation that seeks to empower marginalized communities to take charge of their own livelihoods and economic future. We focus on community development through economic empowerment and are dedicated to helping communities realize and share their abundance through Economic Commons with Instruments like Vouchers that can act as a medium of exchange and become Community Inclusion Currencies (CICs). While core beneficiaries of our programs include businesses and people living in informal settlements as well as rural areas, the documentation and tools have been broadly applied worldwide.	Kenya
Green Earth Agro	Greenearth Agro Industries Limited is an environmentally conscious company with focus on production of Palm Kernel Oil and its subsidiary products such as Palm Kernel Shell and Palm Kernel Cake.	Luxembourg; Ghana
Greenfence	Greenfence is the first decentralized blockchain ecosystem servicing farm to fork supply chains and TIC industry services. Greenfence provides simple and scalable cutting edge blockchain solutions that empower all stakeholders to build their own supply chains on the world’s first self-serve blockchain. The control to quickly and cost-effectively build and manage complex supply chains and compliance now lies in the hands of each participant, not the IT specialist, establishing the integrity of assets, processes, data and certification on the blockchain, protecting brand equity and securing consumer trust.	USA
hiveOnline	Fintech and Financial Inclusion for the Unbanked. myCoop.online is the first Decentralised Finance platform for African farmers, helping them grow better crops, aggregate and increase revenues, with access to credit, markets, farming inputs, and simple accounting. Our blockchain based no-touch vouchers facilitate efficient, secure, low-cost distribution of agricultural inputs, emergency aid and much more.	Denmark; Sweden; Rwanda;

	They're fully traceable and self-auditing, slashing administration costs and increasing donor confidence. vsla.online digitises community savings groups such as Village and Savings and Loan Associations (VSLA), SILCs, ROSCAs, Tontines and more. Built with blockchain technology, for better record-keeping, transparency and security.	
HouseAfrica	HouseAfrica is building a modern property record system powered by blockchain technology to help verify legitimate land and property ownership and create more efficiency and oversight throughout the entire real estate value chain.	Nigeria
Hungry Coin	Restaurants, traceable tokens.A smarter universal reward system based on Blockchain technology. Hungry Coin enables Merchants to divert their marketing dollars into smarter reward points for their consumers. Our Tokens secure the transactions and make Universal reward points worthy again.	USA
International Foods	A DApp that allows users to purchase food on the blockchain, as Non Fungible Tokens.	
Kezzler	Kezzler's cloud-based traceability platform enables parties to view product information along each step of the supply chain process, and is able to be integrated into existing blockchain ledger and database systems.	Norway
KrmTKT	connect the event organizer who wants to attend the event this process is linked to smart contracts.Each ticket is created using blockchain and non-fungible token (NFT) technology and is linked to the buyer, providing traceability and helping to prevent fake tickets from being placed on the secondary market.	Jordan
Kvarøy Fiskeoppdrett	BCT to combat fraud on norwegian salmon. Additionally, having more transparency and traceability increases the value of his salmon and the price that customers are willing to pay for it	Norway
Land LayBy	LayBy is building a trusted shared distributed ledger for recording land buying and selling transactions that can never be altered, corrupted, forged or replicated in error.	Australia, Ghana, UK, USA
Mazzuma	Mazzuma is a mobile money payment system that utilizes distributed secure infrastructure and cryptocurrency to enable seamless payments.	Ghana
MedFood TTHubs	INESC ID + INOV and CERTH: MED Food TTHubs is a PRIMA project that seeks to support the implementation of full-path tracing practices through the whole distribution channel from seed to shelf in order to achieve safer and more sustainable Mediterranean food products for people all around the world. Aiming to implement full transparency concerning the traceability and authenticity in the food supply sector, MED Food TTHubs taps into cutting edge technologies and "Internet of Things" (IoT) solutions and builds on standardised approaches to food production processes and location identification, transparent monitoring procedures and innovative business partnerships. Therefore, MED Food TTHubs establishes and operates seven pilot Trace & Trust Hubs forming a transnational network playing the role of a one-stop-shop for traceability and authenticity for "added value" Mediterranean food products.	Portugal; Greece; Italy; Tunisia; Spain; Jordan; Egypt
Morpheus.Network	Morpheus.Network was built to make logistics easier using blockchain technology. Combining the most brilliant minds in global trade, information security, blockchain, and artificial intelligence, Morpheus.Network aims to fix the inefficiencies that the World Economic Forum has identified in a \$15 trillion USD industry.	Canada
MyHealthMyData	Blockchain software infrastructure to allow data subjects for direct access to clinical data form any personal device	Italy; UK; Romania; Greece; Switzerland; Austria; Germany; France
National Fisheries Institute	The National Fisheries Institute (NFI) has announced that it's working with IBM's Food Trust to spearhead the first multi-company attempt to introduce blockchain technology to the seafood supply chain. The pilot project is being funded by the Seafood Industry Research Fund (SIRF).	Norway
Omnichain	Enabling consumer brands to combine algorithmic forecasting with dynamic inventory and supply modeling to meet omnichannel consumer demand throughout the supply chain.	USA

OnePercent	We create customized business and technology solutions, by developing blockchain products that connect businesses and people to create a new, more democratic global economy.	Brazil
OpenPort	OpenPort's smart contract platform enables our real-world transport management technology to record shipment events in real-time. OpenPort has built a neutral and digital network for enterprise logistics in emerging markets. The Open Enterprise Logistics (OEL) model features a neutral marketplace for transport procurement where transporters publish rates and collaborate directly with large shippers for tenders, both for smart contracts and on-demand ad-hoc transport procurement.	Pakistan
OQOD	Smart Contract Development & Management Portal for Tokenized Real Estate Securities	Saudi Arabia
OriginalMy	PACWeb: blockchain certification functionality that enables you to have legally valid proof of content posted on the internet. It enables proof of authenticity of webcontent, enabling the proof that the content existed in some point in time. This solution is has already been recognized on courts.	Brazil
Owlchain	A tracing system for pork. Through blockchain's immutability, transparency, and traceability, OwlTing Blockchain Services™ can drive substantive improvements to the agricultural supply chain, enhancing customer trust and brand value.	Taiwan (HQ); United States; Japan; Hong Kong; Singapore; Thailand; Malaysia
PharmaLedger (Horizon EU)	The PharmaLedger project will create a scalable blockchain platform validated through reference use cases in supply chain, clinical trials and health data that will serve trendsetters in the industry, thus enabling early adopters.	Spain; Switzerland; Portugal; Romania; Israel; UK; Greece; US; Sweden Germany; Belgium; Denmark; Luxembourg
Project Unblocked Cash	Project Unblocked Cash: a Cash and Voucher Assistance program pilot built on the Ethereum blockchain main net. It connected disaster victims with "cash" aid faster while providing real-time visibility into the flow of funds.	USA; Australia; Belgium; Brasil; Canada; Colombia; Denmark; France; Germany; Great Britain; Hong Kong; India; Spain; Ireland; Italy; Mexico; New Zealand; Netherlands; Canada; South Africa and Turkey.
Provenance	Provenance Blockchain is a public open source blockchain designed and developed to deliver material business benefits to financial services participants and developers through its ledger, registry and exchange capabilities across multiple financial assets and markets. The Provenance Blockchain community consists of individuals and organizations that identify projects like: DeFi applications, tools to teach and educate students about the Provenance Blockchain network and its SDK. The Community identifies projects that bring diverse communities together.	UK
Raw Seafood	Raw Seafoods and its partners along the supply chain have joined the IBM Food Trust blockchain platform. The firms aim to use the traceability solution to increase efficiency, reduce fraud, and provide customers with trustworthy provenance	Norway

	information. Raw Seafoods has collaborated with its global clients, including fisheries, distributors, and wholesalers, to create a fully traceable supply chain focusing on scallops	
Red Cab LLC	Blockchain based peer to peer transportation system. RedCab LLC. offers a decentralized peer-to-peer transportation solution to individuals. Utilizing the power of Blockchain technologies and a unique business model for a transparent, affordable, and innovative future.	Egypt
RiginO	RiginO is an end-to-end food traceability platform targeting the MENA region, enabling food value chain players to log every interaction across the supply chain leading to the full provenance and journey of products. Answering the need for enhanced supply chain transparency and trust, businesses will be able to generate business growth, access new markets, improve brand perception and comply with regulations. A real-time traceability platform for Agro-food for the MENA region	Lebanon
Ripe.io	Transparent digital food supply chain. ripe.io is transforming the food supply chain by enabling data transparency and transfer from farm to fork to answer what our food is, where has it been and what has happened to it. We're exposing the journey of our food to create new analytics, automation and business models through blockchain technology and the Internet of Things. We provide solutions for every actor in the food supply chain.	USA
RiskBlock	Mitigating Risks in Temperature-controlled Supply Chains Using Blockchain Technology	Germany; Singapore
Sical edição limitada	Tracking of coffee beans through all the steps of the supply chain, up to the consumer	Portugal; Brasil
Sjømatbedriftene	The Norwegian Seafood Association is collaborating with IBM and local IT services provider Atea to use blockchain for traceability in seafood supply chains.	Norway
Skuchain	Our Currency Agnostic Blockchain links procurement and contract management, financing arrangements, direct enterprise control of corporate payments and inventory tracking in a buildable manner. The result is a Liquid Supply Chain, where data flows downstream in real time and early payments flow upstream in a risk-mitigated manner from new pools of capital.	USA
Smart Dubai	Settling payments for Dubai Pay	UAE
SOL	SOL is an app developed for cooperatives to improve and secure their buying processes. It was first developed for the familiar farming associations located in Bahia and Rio Grande do Norte States, Brazil, so the organizations benefiting from Bahia Produtiva and Governo Cidadão projects could manage their buying processes in a secure and easy way.	Brazil
Spectrocoin Block chain explorer	SpectroCoin is an all-in-one solution for cryptocurrencies, ranging from exchange to e-wallets, crypto loans with IBAN + block chain explorer/ blockchain wallet has been added for users to check their transactions	UK based company but its services is across 150 countries including Kuwait; Algeria; Bahrain; Djibouti; Jordan; Kuwait; Morocco
Swiss Food Chain	The Foodchains project targets at evaluation and a prototypical design of a blockchain-based approach toward the digitization of the food chain within the Swiss agricultural sector. Specifically, the use case of a dairy product tracking approach – "from the cow to the cheese" – was investigated and supported by a newly prototyped IT system, representing by an Android App-based, distributed system, which can collect in an easy-to-use manner raw product data, transport data, manufacturing data, and sold product data – once collected and made available in a digital representation –, such that these are traceable in a customized and stakeholder-defined manner.	Switzerland
swvl	Blockchain based Ridesharing in collaboration with concordium.Concordium will provide a blockchain-based technology platform that aims to upgrade the mass transit travel experience for Swvl's customers. The platform is intended to help solve	Egypt;UAE

	the highly-complex logistical challenges inherent in mass transit, while advancing Swvl's efforts at decarbonization and smart, green mobility.	
SyncFab	SyncFab offers NPI & OEM parts production procurement for agile supply chain management & parts pedigree with digital thread compliance & blockchain cybersecurity.	USA; Canada
TagOne	End-To-End Traceability The TagOne Solution Suite comprises of three core modules, TagOne Cultivate, TagOne Enterprise, and TagOne Engage, covering your entire supply chain from the first mile to the last.	USA
TE Food	Farm-to-table Food Traceability Solution Using Blockchain Technology	Germany; Hungary; Vietnam
topl	Decentralized protocol designed to unlock the next wave of inclusive, sustainable innovation across supply chains and markets. Case studies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ethical Chocolate • Nutmeg & Coffee Traceability 	USA
Trace-Rice	TRACE-RICE targets the adoption of cost-efficient and environmentally safe tools for traceability, authenticity, contaminant mitigation and conversion of by-products to innovative rice base food produced in the Mediterranean.	Portugal; Spain; Egypt
TraceX	TraceX is a blockchain powered traceability platform that builds climate resilient and sustainable supply chains to enhance trust and maximize long term value for your business.	Bangalore
Tracr	Diamond traceability and authenticity	Canada
TradeLens	TradeLens is an open and neutral supply chain platform underpinned by blockchain technology. We are enabling true information sharing and collaboration across supply chains, thereby increasing industry innovation, reducing trade friction and—ultimately—promoting more global trade.	USA
Transparent Path	Farm-to-distributor traceability. Transparent Path is a social purpose corporation focused on supply chain visibility. Our mission is to reduce food waste, financial risk, and food insecurity by creating more trust and transparency in our most critical supply chains. Powered by IoT sensors, blockchain security, and artificial intelligence, Transparent Path's secure, scalable platform provides food manufacturers, processors, logistics partners and retailers with the ability to see and act on supply chain issues in real-time. As a result, Transparent Path's customers know immediately when something goes wrong, can act to prevent risk, and can anticipate supply chain issues before they occur.	USA
UAE Malafi	Malaffi (Arabic for 'my file') has been developed in a strategic partnership between Department of Health – Abu Dhabi (DOH) and Injazat Data Systems, a wholly owned subsidiary of Mubadala. With universal, Emirate-wide participation, the initiative will facilitate the meaningful exchange of health information between healthcare providers, healthcare professionals and government authorities. Every medical interaction a patient has, from a routine checkup, consultation or emergency treatment, to laboratory tests or radiology reports, will now be collated in their personal file, with their medical history safely and securely stored and instantly accessible when needed.	UAE
UAE's "Hayat" donor registry	Aimed at improving the transplant process for donors and patients: improving access to organ transplant treatments; accelerating and securing the transplant process; improving transplants with advanced organ allocation; and organ provenance verification with regulations.	UAE
UAE's Ministry of Health and Prevention (MoHAP) blockchain platform for storing healthcare and pharmaceutical data.	Designed for secure storage of data for health, pharmaceutical government and private facilities, health practitioners and drug information manufacturer, active substance, the price, method of use). Used to better regulate the healthcare industry, track outcomes and provide life-saving information throughout the region, It will help streamline the search for health facilities and its licensed medical and technical personnel, and their expertise, in 3 steps using MoHAP App.	UAE
Unilever	GreenToken by SAP Ariba for palm-oil supply chain tracking - pilot project. SAP GreenToken allows to Unilever's suppliers to create token that reflects the product flows during the whole supply chain and allow to identify the origin linked product features. In this way the main goal is to improve traceability and transparency during the palm oil supply chain.	Indonesia

Using DLT/blockchain to developing a reliable Assurance system for Gluten Free Oats	Oats are actually naturally gluten free, but they can become contaminated by other cereals that contain gluten as they pass along the supply chain and this can be, for people who suffer from Coeliac Disease or have sever gluten intolerance, critical so proof of assurance of gluten-free oats is becoming increasingly important. A small group of gluten free oat growers in the NE of Scotland will test the use of using a digitally twinned record, secured by distributed ledger technology (DLT) and blockchain, to provide a traceable, assured and immutable record of the crop from the field into the rest of the supply chain.	UK
VeChain	VeChainThor is a public blockchain that is designed for mass adoption of blockchain technology by business users of all sizes. It is intended to serve as the foundation for a sustainable and scalable business blockchain ecosystem. From a technical point of view, the VeChainThor blockchain is built upon existing proven blockchain innovations and novel technologies that are created for achieving mass adoption. These technologies include the Proof-of-Authority (“PoA”) consensus algorithm, meta transaction features, protocols of transaction fee delegation, on-chain governance mechanism, built-in smart contracts as well as tools for developers.	China
Wine Protocol	BlockChain application on winery. Each bottle has a NFT on its label, that tell all steps that led to the creation of the specific bottle; from the harvest to the bottling. Thanks to the NFT each bottle is certified and guaranteed.	Switzerland
Webisoft	Webisoft is digital transformation and product development consulting firm with core expertise in blockchain and SaaS and software development.	Canada
Wow Blockchain Labz	Bunch of motivated guys joined together to make a difference and build something. We worked tirelessly to create a kick@\$\$ team to provide customer delight to our exhilarating customers. Day in and day out, there were late nights, lots of coding, lots of partying – work hard, play harder was the motto. After 10 years, it’s still the same motivation and passion that drives the team.	India
Evolt	Evolt is a collaborative group of industry and technology veterans designing the best technology and workflow solutions for tomorrow’s tech leaders. Partnering on projects around the globe, we are setting a new standard for creative problem-solving for forward thinking businesses all over the world. Our team of experienced professionals deliver customized solutions to your most complex development needs. Possessing a variety of backgrounds and professional expertise, Evolt creates solutions that will elevate and revolutionize your business.	BiH

Annex 5 List of digital resources

Assessment of sector's adoption of blockchain technology: References

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